

Reactome User Guide

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The Pathway Browser

The Pathway Browser is the primary means of viewing and interacting with pathways in Reactome.

See our Youtube Video explaining [navigating the Pathway Browser](#) for more information.

The Pathway Browser includes tools for analysing datasets and exploring pathways. These tools allow several types of analysis:

- Pathway over-representation analysis and pathway topology-based analysis
- Comparison of a pathway with its equivalent in another species
- The overlay of user-supplied expression data onto a pathway
- The overlay of protein-protein or protein-compound interaction data from external databases or user-supplied data onto a pathway

See the section [Reactome Analysis Tools](#) for details of the analysis tools.

The Pathway Browser is launched by clicking the Browse Pathways button on the Homepage:

Pathway Browser

Visualize and interact with Reactome
biological pathways

When the Pathway Browser opens, it displays an overview of all Reactome pathways. Pathways are organized hierarchically and often have sub-pathways. At the highest hierarchical level, all pathways are represented in an Overview. At intermediate levels, pathways are often represented as interactive illustrations, with selectable regions that act as links to the lower levels, which are represented as detailed Pathway Diagrams. Reactome's Overview uses a unique graphical visualization of the hierarchy, representing pathways at the uppermost hierarchical level as central nodes (circles) with subpathways arranged concentrically (in rings) around them. Many have further concentric rings of 'child' subpathways. Pathway nodes are connected to their subpathways by edges (lines). This overview displays all pathways and allows rapid zooming to details. As you zoom in, labels appear for the subpathway nodes. This view is also used to display data analysis results.

Nodes in the overview link to detailed pathway diagrams that use a style based on Systems Biology Graphical Notation. They have several features intended to ensure an appropriate level of information detail, including subpathway shading and fade-in of labels, commonly occurring small molecules and structures.

To see the details of a specific pathway, select and click (or double-click) the node representing the pathway. Alternatively select and click on the name in the Pathway Hierarchy panel on the left.

Features of the Pathway Browser are labelled in the diagram below.

Home – the Reactome logo is a button linked to the homepage.

Species – Reactome is a database of curated human biological pathways. These human pathways are used to computationally infer equivalent pathways in model organisms (described in detail [here](#)). Use the Species drop-down to select a species and view the predicted pathway. Note that infectious disease pathways that show the interaction of pathogens with human proteins are included in Homo sapiens.

Layout – The pathway browser is divided into 3 main sections. These are: the Hierarchy Panel, on the left, the Details Panel, bottom right, the Pathway Panel, top right. The layout buttons allow you to show or hide these panels.

Analyse Data – Opens a panel where analysis can be performed.

Key – this opens a key explaining the objects present in the pathway panel.

Zoom/Move Toolbar - Click on the arrows to move the diagram. Click on the plus and minus buttons to zoom in and out. Alternatively, click and drag the diagram, and use your mouse scroll wheel to zoom.

In-Diagram Search – click the button to open the search panel. When the Overview or a Pathway Diagram is displayed, objects represented in the displayed diagram or all diagrams are searchable.

Fit to Page - resizes the Pathway Overview or Diagram to fit the available space.

Open Diagram – when a pathway node is selected in the Pathway Overview, this button opens the corresponding Pathway Diagram

Illustrations – some Reactome pathways have a corresponding high-quality graphic. Select this button to view.

Export – use this button to download the visible region of the Pathway Overview or Diagram, including any analysis overlay, as a PNG file or upload it to GenomeSpace.

Thumbnail – Provides an overview of the entire pathway when zoomed in so that only a region of the pathway is displayed.

Pathway Panel - This is where Pathway Diagrams are displayed when they are selected in the Pathway Hierarchy or in search results. If no pathway is selected, this panel displays a brief Reactome help guide.

Details Panel - Contains details of objects when they are selected in the Pathway Diagram. The content depends on the type of object, i.e. pathway, reaction, complex, set, protein or small molecule (see the Details section).

Event Hierarchy Panel – Shows the hierarchical organisation of Reactome pathways and pathway events or steps, known as reactions. When the Pathway Browser is opened, only the top level of the hierarchy is shown, as an alphabetical list of Reactome’s main topics (superpathways). Most topics are split into sub-pathways, which may be further divided into sub-sub-pathways. Most topics in Reactome are organised in this hierarchical manner. Sub-pathways can be revealed by clicking on the + icon to the left of the pathway name, and hidden by clicking on the - icon.

Settings Sidebar – Used for context-sensitive help, to configure colour schemes and the default source of interactors.

Event Hierarchy

The order of reactions from top to bottom in the Event Hierarchy Panel usually follows their order as steps in the pathway so that the preceding reaction is above and the subsequent reaction below, but this is not always the case. Pathways may not be linear; they can be circular or branched. Consequently, reactions often have multiple preceding or subsequent reactions. To view a complete list of the events that precede or follow a reaction, refer to the Preceding and Following Events section in the Details Panel, as described in the Details Panel chapter below.

The event hierarchy panel provides a nested structure containing large topics that are organised as pathways and subpathways and can be expanded to show individual events and steps. The icons next to the event describe the event.

You can hover over the icon in the Event Hierarchy panel to show a tool-tip that describes the event, as illustrated in the figure below.

This table shows a legend of the icons and their respective descriptions in Reactome:

Icon	Description
	Pathway
	Pathway with an enhanced diagram
	Updated
	Black Box Event
	Reaction
	Inferred from a non-human event
	Is a disease
	Failed reaction
	Depolymerization
	Polymerization
	Negative regulation
	Positive regulation

Pathway Diagrams

Pathway Diagrams represent pathways as a series of connected molecular events, known in Reactome as 'reactions', which can be considered as steps in the pathway.

Cellular compartments are represented as pink/orange boxes with a double boundary. A typical diagram has a box to represent the cytosol, bounded by a double-line that represents the plasma membrane. The white area outside this box represents the extracellular space. Other organelles are represented as additional labelled boxes within the cytosol.

Molecules, represented in diagrams as blue/green boxes, are placed in the physiologically-correct cellular compartment, or lie on the boundary of a compartment to indicate that they are

in the corresponding membrane, e.g. a plasma membrane protein will be placed on the boundary of the cytosol.

Reactions typically include:

- Input and output molecules, and when relevant a catalyst (see diagram A below)
- Inputs, outputs and catalyst are represented as boxes or ovals
- Green boxes with rounded corners are proteins
- Green boxes with square corners are proteins that have no UniProt accession (or did not at the time the reaction was created).
- Green ovals are small molecules or sets of small molecules
- Blue boxes with a double boundary are sets, i.e. proteins or small molecules that are functionally equivalent.
- Blue boxes with cut corners are complexes, i.e. proteins and/or other molecules that are bound in a multimolecular entity.
- Green boxes with a white inner box are sub-pathways.
- Reaction input and output molecules are joined by lines to a central 'reaction node' (surrounded by a green box in Figure A below). Clicking this node selects the reaction.
- The outputs of a reaction have an arrowhead on the line connecting them to the reaction node.
- Reaction inputs/output molecules are often connected by arrows to preceding or subsequent reactions (i.e. the preceding/subsequent steps in the pathway).
- Catalysts are connected to the reaction node by a line ending in a circle.
- Numbered boxes on the line between an input/output and the reaction node indicates the number of molecules of this type in the reaction (when $n > 1$).
- Molecules that regulate a reaction are connected to the reaction node by a line ending in an open triangle for positive regulation or a 'T'-shaped head for negative regulation (see B below).
- A white box labelled P on the boundary of an object indicates a phosphorylation event.
- Proteins or small molecules that are also part of a displayed set may be connected to the set object by a line of short dashes.
- Sets with overlapping content may be connected by a line of long dashes.
- Reactions that represent a disease process use red connecting lines. Objects associated with a disease are bordered in red.

Enhanced high-level diagrams and Subpathway icons

Many pathways at the higher levels of the hierarchy are too large to represent as a single, detailed pathway diagram. Instead they are often represented as an illustration, known as an enhanced high-level diagram, which graphically represents the subpathways as selectable regions of an illustration. When the mouse pointer is moved over a region, it becomes surrounded by a blue highlighting 'halo'. When you click on a region it becomes selected and outlined in dark blue, the corresponding subpathway is selected in the Hierarchy panel and the Details panel updates to show details of the subpathway. Double-clicking on a region opens the corresponding detailed Pathway Diagram.

In the Hierarchy panel, pathways that have an enhanced high-level diagram have a blue icon to the left of their name.

reactome Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Analysis: Tour: Layout:

Event Hierarchy:

- Cell Cycle
- Cell-Cell communication
- Cellular responses to external stimuli
- Chromatin organization
- Circadian Clock
- Developmental Biology
- Digestion and absorption
- Disease
- DNA Repair
- DNA Replication
- Extracellular matrix organization
- Gene expression (Transcription)
- Hemostasis
 - Platelet homeostasis
 - Platelet Adhesion to exposed collagen
 - Platelet activation, signaling and aggregation
 - Formation of Fibrin Clot (Clotting Cascade)
 - Dissolution of Fibrin Clot
 - Cell surface interactions at the vascular wall
 - Factors involved in megakaryocyte development and platelet production
- Immune System
- Metabolism
- Metabolism of proteins
- Metabolism of RNA
- Mitophagy
- Muscle contraction
- Neuronal System
- Organelle biogenesis and maintenance
- Programmed Cell Death
- Protein localization
- Reproduction
- Signal Transduction
- Transport of small molecules
- Vesicle-mediated transport

PLATELET HOMEOSTASIS

PLATELET ADHESION TO EXPOSED COLLAGEN

PLATELET ACTIVATION, SIGNALING AND AGGREGATION

FORMATION OF FIBRIN CLOT (CLOTTING CASCADE)

DISOLUTION OF FIBRIN CLOT

CELL SURFACE INTERACTIONS AT THE VASCULAR WALL

FACTORS INVOLVED IN MEGAKARYOTE DEVELOPMENT AND PLATELET PRODUCTION

EXPOSED COLLAGEN

ADP

ATP

FIBRIN

FIBRINOGEN

PLASMIN

IPA

IPA PAI

ENDOTHELIUM

EXTRACELLULAR MATRIX

P-Selectin

ICAM3

JAM3

Description

Molecules Structures Expression Analysis Downloads

Hemostasis Id: R-HSA-108062.1 Species: Homo sapiens

Summation

Hemostasis is a physiological response that culminates in the arrest of bleeding from an injured vessel. Under normal conditions the vascular endothelium supports vasodilation, inhibits platelet adhesion and activation, suppresses coagulation, enhances fibrin cleavage and is anti-inflammatory in character. Under acute vascular trauma, vasoconstrictor mechanisms predominate and the endothelium becomes prothrombotic, procoagulatory and proinflammatory in nature. This is achieved by a reduction of endothelial clotting agents: adenosine, NO and prostacyclin; and by the direct action of ADP, serotonin and thromboxane on vascular smooth muscle cells to elicit their contraction (Becker et al. 2000). The chief trigger for the change in endothelial function that leads to the formation of a haemostatic thrombus is the loss of the endothelial cell barrier between blood and extracellular matrix components (Ruggeri 2002). Circulating platelets identify and discriminate areas of endothelial lesions; here, they adhere to the exposed sub endothelium. Their interaction with the various thrombogenic substrates and locally generated or released agonists results in platelet activation. This process is described as possessing two stages, firstly, adhesion - the initial tethering to a surface, and secondly aggregation - the platelet-platelet cohesion (Savidge & Cattaneo et al. 2001). Three mechanisms contribute to the loss of blood following

A few higher level pathways use an older visualization of large topics, where subpathways are represented by a box with a green boundary, the subpathway icon (see example below). Selecting a subpathway icon has the same result as selecting a region of an enhanced-level pathway diagram as described above.

reactome Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Search for a term, e.g. pten ...

Analysis: Tour: Layout:

Event Hierarchy:

- Cell Cycle
- Cell-Cell communication
- Cellular responses to external stimuli
- Chromatin organization
- Circadian Clock
- Developmental Biology
- Digestion and absorption
- Disease
- DNA Repair
- DNA Replication
- Extracellular matrix organization
- Gene expression (Transcription)
- Hemostasis
- Immune System
- Metabolism
 - Metabolism of proteins
 - Metabolism of RNA
 - Mitophagy
 - Muscle contraction
 - Neuronal System
 - Organelle biogenesis and maintenance
 - Programmed Cell Death
 - Protein localization
 - Reproduction
 - Signal Transduction
 - Transport of small molecules
 - Vesicle-mediated transport

Metabolism of amino acids and derivatives

Metabolism of vitamins and cofactors

Metabolism of nucleotides

The citric acid (TCA) cycle and respiratory electron transport

Biological oxidation

Metabolism of lipids

Integration of energy metabolism

Metabolism of fatty acids

Incretin phosphate metabolism

Mitochondrial iron-sulfur cluster biogenesis

Reversible hydration of carbon dioxide

Pyrophosphate hydrolysis

Cytosolic iron-sulfur cluster assembly

Abscise transport and metabolism

Description

Molecules Structures Expression Analysis Downloads

Metabolism Id: R-HSA-1430728.8 Species: Homo sapiens

Summation

Metabolic processes in human cells generate energy through the oxidation of molecules consumed in the diet and mediate the synthesis of diverse essential molecules not taken in the diet as well as the inactivation and elimination of toxic ones generated endogenously or present in the extracellular environment. The processes of energy metabolism can be classified into two groups according to whether they involve carbohydrate-derived or lipid-derived molecules, and within each group it is useful to distinguish processes that mediate the breakdown and oxidation of these molecules to yield energy from ones that mediate their synthesis and storage as internal energy reserves. Synthetic reactions are conveniently grouped by the chemical nature of the end products, such as nucleotides, amino acids and related molecules, and porphyrins. Detoxification reactions (biological oxidations) are likewise conveniently classified by the chemical nature of the toxin.

At the same time, all of these processes are tightly integrated. Intermediates in reactions of energy generation are starting materials for biosyntheses of amino acids and other compounds, broad-specificity

In some pathways, Reactome links to other related pathways through green boxes. In order to differentiate between related subpathways that are children of the same parent pathway

(subpathways) and related subpathways that are children of a different parent pathway (interacting pathways), the Pathway Browser uses slightly different glyphs as illustrated in the figure below.

Subpathway Shading

When a Pathway Diagram contains subpathways, the area containing each subpathway is overlaid with a coloured box, labelled with the subpathway name, to help locate it in the larger diagram. Below is the diagram for ERBB4 signaling. The four subpathways are represented as 4 boxed and shaded areas.

Pathway Diagram zoom detail level

The pathway diagram represents different levels of detail, depending on the zoom level. When fully zoomed-out, regions corresponding to subpathways are shaded. The boxes representing molecules or groups of molecules have no text labels and trivial molecules, such as water and ATP, are not represented. At the next level of zoom, subpathway shading disappears, while trivial molecules and the circular red icon indicating that a protein has known interactors fade into view. At closer levels of zoom the reaction nodes appear, as do boxes containing a number on the lines connecting molecules to the reaction node if stoichiometry is greater than one. At this level of zoom, if interactors are displayed their names appear. At the highest level of zoom, if available, proteins, small molecules and interactors display structural diagrams from PDBe or ChEBI with associated details.

Navigating Pathway Diagrams

The Pathway Diagram, Hierarchy and Details Panels are interactively connected. Selecting an entity (molecular object) or event in the diagram will reveal relevant information in the Details Panel. Clicking a pathway name in the Hierarchy will open the corresponding Pathway Diagram in the Pathway Diagram Panel, and reveal details of the pathway in the Details Panel. If a subpathway is contained within the diagram that is displayed, clicking its name in the hierarchy will cause all the reactions in the pathway to be highlighted in blue. In the figure below, the diagram for Platelet homeostasis is displayed in the Pathway Panel, and the sub-pathway Prostacyclin signalling through prostacyclin receptor has been selected in the Hierarchy, causing all the reactions in this sub-pathway to be highlighted (blue) on the Pathway Diagram.

Similarly, selecting a reaction in the Hierarchy causes that reaction to be highlighted in the pathway diagram and updates the Details Panel to show details of the reaction. If the reaction is not in the visible region of the diagram, the view will re-centre and zoom to show it. If instead of clicking an event, you hover the mouse pointer over its name, it will be highlighted in yellow. In the figure above, the sub-pathway Platelet calcium homeostasis is highlighted in yellow.

Getting Started

Hierarchy Panel Exercises

This exercise is to check that you understand the organisation of the Hierarchy Panel. You don't need to look at the Diagram Panel.

From the Home page, search for PDGF signaling.

In the results page, open the expandable hierarchy in the section Locations in the Pathway Browser by clicking on the + button. **DON'T** click on the location before expanding the hierarchy! This will open the pathway diagram in the Pathway Browser.

Look at the Hierarchy Panel on the left.

1. How many sub-pathways does this pathway have?
2. How many reactions are in the first sub-pathway?

3. What reaction(s) follow 'Translocation of PDGF from ER to Golgi'? *Hint: Look in the Details Panel, bottom-right. If it is hidden, use the layout buttons in the top right corner, above the diagram, to reveal it.*

Subpathway Exercises

This exercise is to check that you understand Subpathway icons and the relationship between the Pathway Hierarchy and Pathway Diagram.

Open the pathway Hemostasis in the Pathway Browser.

Select the subpathway 'Platelet Hemostasis'.

1. What happens if you hover your mouse pointer in the Hierarchy on the sub-pathway 'Platelet calcium hemostasis'?
2. What happens if you click in the Hierarchy on the sub-pathway 'Platelet calcium hemostasis'?
3. What happens if you click in the hierarchy on the reaction 'Binding of ATP to P2X receptors'?

More Information

There are 5 subtypes of reaction node, indicating reaction subclasses.

- Open squares represent 'transition', i.e. a change of state that is not one of the defined subclasses.
- Solid circles represent 'association', i.e. binding
- Double-bordered circles represent 'dissociation'
- A square with two slashes represents an 'omitted process'. This is used when the full details of a reaction have been deliberately omitted. This is most commonly used for events that include representative members of a large family to illustrate the general behaviour of the group. It can be used for reactions that occur with no fixed order or stoichiometry, or for degradation events where the output is a random set of fragments.
- Squares containing a question mark represent an 'uncertain process', where some details of the reaction are known, but the process is thought to be more complex than represented. Explanatory details are typically included in the Description.

Reaction Node Exercises

This exercise is to check that you understand reaction node subtypes.

From the Home page, search for the pathway 'Effects of PIP2 hydrolysis' and open it in the Pathway Browser (in any of the several locations)

1. What symbol represents the reaction for 'Binding of IP3 to the IP3 receptor'?
2. What symbol represents the reaction 'IP3R tetramer:I(1,4,5)P3:4xCa²⁺ transports Ca²⁺ from platelet dense tubular system to cytosol? What subtype of reaction is this?
3. Open the subpathway 'Arachidonate production from DAG'. What is the name of the catalyst for '2-AG hydrolysis to arachidonate by MAGL'? Can you name the three outputs of this reaction?
4. Can you find the UniProt ID for the catalyst? Hint: There are several ways to find this, two require you to select something!

Searching Reactome

See our Youtube Video explaining [Reactome's Main Search Feature!](#)

Simple text search

The simple text search tool is located top right of the Home page. To search type a word, phrase or identifier in the search box. The search has an auto-complete function; if the text you wanted to use appears in the drop-down list, select it and results will be displayed. For other text click Search.

Search results are presented in categories with grey headers, representing the molecular entity or event types.

Below the header is a list of items from the named type that match your search terms. Matching words are highlighted in grey. Click on the name of an item to go to a page of details.

On the left side of the search results page are groups of checkboxes. These can be used to change defaults and add filters. Check or uncheck boxes for types that you do/don't want to see, e.g. if you want to see results for *Mus musculus*, under Species uncheck *Homo sapiens* and check *Mus musculus*. In the Type, Compartment and Reaction Type filter groups, select to only see results that fall into the selected category, e.g. to see only reactions, select Reaction in the Types filter group. To see only Reactions that occur in the cytosol, also select Cytosol in Compartments.

protein kinase

Go!

Search results for protein kinase

Showing 20 results out of 32993

Species

- Homo sapiens (32248)
- Entries without species (745)
- Danio rerio (37640)
- Drosophila melanogaster (32461)
- Mus musculus (26962)
- Rattus norvegicus (25177)

[More...](#)

Types

- Protein (23869)
- Reaction (5934)
- Pathway (1082)
- Complex (363)
- Regulation (670)
- Set (370)

[More...](#)

Compartments

- cytosol (9120)
- plasma membrane (6661)
- nucleoplasm (5147)
- extracellular region (4604)
- endoplasmic reticulum lumen (1247)
- endoplasmic reticulum membrane (1117)

[More...](#)

Reaction types

- binds (1282)
- regulates (640)
- phosphorylates (532)
- transports (118)
- ubiquitinates (111)
- activates (90)

[More...](#)

Reaction (2 results from a total of 5934)

▶ Activation of conventional Protein Kinase C

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** plasma membrane, cytosol
 The conventional Protein Kinase C (cPKC) isoforms have two membrane-targeting domains, a C1 domain which binds to the membrane lipid diacylglycerol (DAG) and a C2 domain which binds membrane phosphol... [Read more](#)

▶ cGMP stimulates Protein Kinase G

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** cytosol
 Protein Kinase G (PKG) is a homodimer held together by a leucine zipper present in the N terminus. Each member of the dimer has two cyclic GMP (cGMP) binding sites, one low affinity and one high affin... [Read more](#)

Set (2 results from a total of 370)

□ Protein Kinase A, catalytic subunits

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** nucleoplasm

□ Protein Kinase A, catalytic subunits

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** cytosol

Genes and Transcripts (2 results from a total of 24)

◆ unidentified protein tyrosine kinase

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** cytosol

◆ protein

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** endoplasmic reticulum lumen

Chemical Compound (2 results from a total of 14)

○ protein

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** lysosomal lumen
Primary external reference: ChEBI: [protein: 36080](#)

○ protein

Species: Homo sapiens **Compartment:** cytosol
Primary external reference: ChEBI: [protein: 36080](#)

Click on any of the results to go to a page of information about it. The contents of these Results Detail pages will depend on the type, but all have a section named 'Locations in the PathwayBrowser'.

CALM1

Stable Identifier	R-HSA-9016871
Type	Protein [EntityWithAccessionedSequence]
Species	Homo sapiens
Compartment	nucleoplasm
Synonyms	Calmodulin

Locations in the PathwayBrowser

[Expand all](#)

- Immune System (Homo sapiens)
- Neuronal System (Homo sapiens)
- Organelle biogenesis and maintenance (Homo sapiens)
- Signal Transduction (Homo sapiens)

This contains an expandable hierarchy that identifies the locations of the item in Reactome pathway diagrams. Click the plus symbol to open the hierarchy.

This hierarchy reflects the organization of events in Reactome. 'Top-level' pathways representing a broad area of biology typically contain one or more levels of subpathways, becoming more specific with each level. The levels of the hierarchy are represented here by indentation; the most general pathways are closest to the left-hand edge of the screen, the most specific subpathways have the greatest indentation to the right. Note that some search result items (e.g. proteins) can be in more than one pathway, which may be in different broad areas of biology, resulting in representation in multiple hierarchies. Note that you can open all the hierarchy levels with a single click on the Expand all link, on the right side. Select any event name to open the corresponding Pathway Diagram. The diagram will open with an animation that shows you where the pathway is located in the Pathway Overview. If the selected item was an event it will be highlighted in blue in the Pathway Diagram. If it was a protein, all instances of it will be highlighted in pink.

Icon Search

Elements of the Icon Library are accessible to the main website search. In the screenshot below, the results of a search for the term: "liver" are displayed.

liver

Go!

Search results for liver

Showing 5 results out of 5

Species

- Homo sapiens (4)
- Entries without species (1)

Types

- Icon (5)
- Reaction (494)
- Pathway (130)
- Protein (77)
- Regulation (34)
- Complex (32)

[More...](#)

Search properties

- clustered Search

Reset filters

Icon (5 results from a total of 5)

Liver

Species: Homo sapiens
 Curator: [Bijay Jassal](#)
 Designer: [Cristoffer Sevilla](#)
 Representation of a liver

Hepatocyte

Species: Homo sapiens
 Curator: [Bruce May](#)
 Designer: [Cristoffer Sevilla](#)
 Cell of the main parenchymal tissue of the liver

VLDL particle

Species: Homo sapiens
 Curator: [Steve Jupe](#)
 Designer: [Cristoffer Sevilla](#)
 Very-low-density lipoprotein is a type of lipoprotein made by the liver

Below the header is a list of items from the "icon" type that match your the "liver" search terms. Matching words are highlighted in grey. Click on the name of an item to go to a page of details. In the following image, selecting the first search result is shown

Liver

Categories	Human tissue
Curator	Bijay Jassal
Designer	Cristoffer Sevilla
Description	Representation of a liver

Icon preview

Locations in the PathwayBrowser

- [Digestion and absorption \(R-HSA-8963743\)](#)
- [Metabolism \(R-HSA-1430728\)](#)
- [Transport of small molecules \(R-HSA-382551\)](#)

External References

UBERON | [0002107](#)

The metadata associated with the selected icon is displayed, including the icon category, the curator and designer, and a brief description of the icon. To download the image icon files, click the links to the right of the preview image. Further down the page is a series of expandable hierarchy links that identifies the locations of the icon in Reactome pathway diagrams. Click the plus symbol to open the hierarchy. Clicking the external link, towards the bottom of the page, will link out to the referencing database for the named icon.

In-Diagram Search (Searching in the Pathway Browser)

Searches can be performed within the Pathway Browser using the In-Diagram Search panel (top left corner of the Pathway Panel). When the Pathway Overview, Diagram is Enhanced High Level Diagram (EHL) is displayed, all of Reactome is searched.

Searching the Pathway Overview

In the example below, as the search term, 'IL6' has been entered. The search tool has predicted results that match this search term and displays a drop-down list of these matches.

The screenshot shows the Reactome search interface. At the top, the Reactome logo is on the left, followed by version information (3.6 and 66) and a dropdown menu set to 'Homo sapiens'. Below this is a search bar containing the text 'il6'. To the right of the search bar are several icons: a magnifying glass, a search icon, a list icon, a refresh icon, and a network icon. A dropdown menu is open below the search bar, displaying a list of search results. Each result is preceded by a small icon representing its type: a blue circle for the first result, a double-helix for the second, and a reaction arrow for the third. The results listed are: 'il6:il6r-2', 'il6r', 'il6r-2', 'il6rb:activated', 'il6st', 'il6st-201', 'il6st:il6st', 'il6st:jak1', and 'il6st:p-jak1:p-jak2'. In the background, a network diagram of biological pathways is visible, with labels for 'Immune System', 'Metabolism of RNA', 'Digestion and absorption', 'Circadian Clock', 'Developmental Biology', 'Signal Transduction', and 'Metabolism'.

Note: the deep blue bar, which indicates that there are 23 results shown. Only the three results are clearly shown in the results window. To view additional results, move the cursor over the window and scroll down. Each result term has a symbol (to the left) representing the type of molecule or event it is. The first result, with a blue circle icon to the left of the name, represent matches to the IL6R protein, located in the plasma membrane. The second result, with a double-helix icon to the left, is the IL6R gene. The third result is a reaction, with icon showing above/below boxes on left connected by a right-pointing arrow to box on right, representing the binding of IL6 to IL6R. The Reactome stable identifier and cell compartment annotations are also provided for each molecule or event type that is displayed.

The image shows the Reactome website interface. At the top left is the Reactome logo. To its right, the version number '3.6' and the number of pathways '66' are displayed. A dropdown menu shows 'Pathways for: Homo sapiens'. Below this is a search bar containing 'il6r'. To the right of the search bar are icons for search, history, and other functions. A 'Results (23)' window is open, listing the following items:

- IL6R**
R-HSA-197824
Plasma membrane
- IL6R gene**
R-HSA-8948459
Nucleoplasm
- IL6 binds IL6R**
R-HSA-1067667
Plasma membrane, Extracellular region
- IL6R-2**

The background features a network diagram of biological pathways, with labels for 'Immune System', 'Metabolism of RNA', 'Metabolism', 'Signal Transduction', 'Circadian Clock', 'Developmental Biology', and 'Digestion and absorption'.

In the following image, the recent search results are displayed at the bottom of the search results window. Clicking the "Clear History" button will remove the search terms from the history.

In the next image, selecting an item in the Search Results Panel also causes a second drop-down Search Results Details Panel to appear. The additional annotations displayed include the molecule or event type, the Reactome stable identifier, an external reference database identifier, and the cell compartment. Clicking the "Filter" button (to the right of the search bar) will display options to filter the search results by molecule or event type, e.g. Pathway, Reaction, Complex, Protein, DNA Sequence, Set, etc. Selecting one or more of the filters will restrict the Search results viewed. Deselecting the filter(s) will alter the search results display. Selecting an item in the initial Search Results Panel causes the Overview to zoom and recentre, focusing on the region that represents pathways containing the selected item. This identifies the selected item and lists the pathways that contain the selected item.

reactome 3.6 66 Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Search: il6r

Filter your results by specific type(s):

- Reaction (9)
- Complex (7)
- Pathway (3)
- Protein (2)
- DNA Sequence (1)
- Set (1)

Results (23)

- IL6R**
R-HSA-197824
Plasma membrane
- IL6R gene**
R-HSA-8948459
Nucleoplasm
- IL6 binds IL6R**
R-HSA-1067667
Plasma membrane, Extracellular region
- IL6R-2**

Details

IL6R

Reference Gene Product: R-HSA-197824 UniProt:P08887

Plasma membrane

Present in 3 pathways

- Interleukin-6 family signaling GO >>>
- Interleukin-4 and Interleukin-13 sign... GO >>>
- RAF-independent MAPK1/3 activation GO >>>

Immune System

Circadian Clock

In the following image, moving the cursor over a pathway name (under the "Present in X pathway") will highlight the corresponding in the Overview, if it is visible in the viewport. The tooltip will display the name of the pathway.

reactome 3.6 66 Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Search: il6r

Filter your results by specific type(s):

- Reaction (9)
- Complex (7)
- Pathway (3)
- Protein (2)
- DNA Sequence (1)
- Set (1)

Results (23)

- IL6R**
R-HSA-197824
Plasma membrane
- IL6R gene**
R-HSA-8948459
Nucleoplasm
- IL6 binds IL6R**
R-HSA-1067667
Plasma membrane, Extracellular region
- IL6R-2**

Details

IL6R

Reference Gene Product: R-HSA-197824 UniProt:P08887

Plasma membrane

Present in 3 pathways

- Interleukin-6 family signaling GO >>>
- Interleukin-4 and Interleukin-13 sign... GO >>>
- RAF-independent MAPK1/3 activation GO >>>

Immune System

Circadian Clock

Interleukin-6 family signaling

Clicking a pathway name (under the "Present in X pathway") in the Search Results Detail Panel will select the corresponding object in the Overview. If it is not visible, the Pathway Diagram will re-centre to show it. Double-click a pathway name in the Search Results Detail Panel or pressing the "GO >>>" button will open the corresponding Pathway Diagram. If you need to return to the Overview, you can use the browser back button. **Note** that in the image above, the Search Results Detail Panel extends beyond the limits of the Overview window, consequently some results are hidden. This explains why the results details title says Present in 3 pathways but only 2 are visible. To see all the matching pathways, click in the pathway list in the Search Results Detail Panel.

In the following image, the "Flag" button in the Search Results Details Panel (to the right of IL6R) has been clicked and the events that contain the selected molecule are highlighted blue and the connected events are highlighted purple. Clicking the "Flag" button for a second time will remove the event highlighting.

The screenshot shows the Reactome search interface. At the top, it says "reactome 3.8" and "Pathways for: Homo sapiens". The search bar contains "il6r". Below the search bar, there are filters for "Reaction (9)", "Complex (7)", "Pathway (3)", "Protein (2)", "DNA Sequence (1)", and "Set (1)". The "Results (23)" section lists several items: "IL6R" (R-HSA-197824, Plasma membrane), "IL6R gene" (R-HSA-8948459, Nucleoplasm), "IL6 binds IL6R" (R-HSA-1067667, Plasma membrane, Extracellular region), and "IL6R-2". The "Details" section for "IL6R" shows "Reference Gene Product" (R-HSA-197824, UniProt:P08887) and "Plasma membrane". It also lists "Present in 3 pathways": "Interleukin-6 family signaling", "Interleukin-4 and Interleukin-13 sign...", and "RAF-independent MAPK1/3 activation". The pathway diagram on the right shows a network of events, with the "Immune System" and "Circadian Clock" pathways highlighted in purple. A "Flag" button is visible next to the "IL6R" entry in the details panel.

Searching a Pathway Diagram

In the example below, the search has identified IL6R and produced a dropdown list of matches. The first match is to a protein, as indicated by the icon on the left. The second match with the icon showing a double helix is a DNA sequence or gene. Note that if IL6R was represented in two cellular compartments in this diagram it would appear twice in this initial search result. The Reactome stable identifier and cell compartment annotations are also provided for each molecule or event type in the search results. **Note:** as the search term is entered, the search tool will predict results that match this search term and displays a drop-down list of these matches.

Although not shown below, when a new search is performed, the recent search results are displayed at the bottom of the search results window. Clicking the "Clear History" button will remove the search terms from the history.

The deep blue highlighted bar, which indicates that there are 3 results shown in "This diagram". Only the two results are clearly shown in the results window. To view additional results, move the cursor over the window and scroll down. Each result term has a symbol (to the left) representing the type of molecule or event it is. The first result, with a blue circle icon to the left of the name, represent matches to the IL6R protein, located in the plasma membrane. The second result, with a double-helix icon to the left, is the IL6R gene. The Reactome stable identifier and cell compartment annotations are also provided for each molecule or event type that is displayed.

In the next image, clicking the "Filter" button (to the right of the search bar) will display options to filter the search results by molecule or event type, e.g. Pathway, Reaction, Complex, Protein, DNA Sequence, Set, etc. Selecting one or more of the filters will restrict the Search results viewed. Deselecting the filter(s) will alter the search results display.

In the next image, selecting an item in the Search Results Panel also causes a second drop-down Search Results Details Panel to appear. The at the top of the Details Panel, additional annotations are displayed that include the molecule or event type, the Reactome stable identifier, an external reference database identifier (if applicable), and the cell compartment. Additional annotations are listed below describing the involvement of the protein within complexes, sets and reactions within the diagram. Selecting names in the Search Results Detail Panel will select the corresponding object in the Pathway Diagram. If it is not visible, the Pathway Diagram will re-centre to show it.

In this example query, clicking the "Flag" button in the Search Results Details Panel (to the right of IL6R) will highlight all (15) the objects in the diagram that contains IL6R. Clicking the "Flag" button for a second time (or the "X" button toward the bottom of the pathway viewport) will remove the object highlighting. To see all the matches, it is necessary to resize the Pathway Diagram panel.

In the following image, selecting the second item in the Search Results Panel (IL6 binds IL6R) causes a second drop-down Search Results Details Panel to appear. At the top of the Details Panel, additional annotations are displayed that include the event type, the Reactome stable identifier, and the cell compartment. Additional annotations are listed below describing the involvement of the reaction within the diagram, and participants of the reaction. Selecting names in the Search Results Detail Panel will select the corresponding object in the Pathway Diagram. If it is not visible, the Pathway Diagram will re-centre to show it. In this image, the IL6 binds IL6R reaction is blue highlighted.

In the next image, clicking the "All diagram" tab will present a different set of results when selecting an item in the Search Results Panel. As before, at the top of the Details Panel, additional annotations are displayed that include the molecule or event type, the Reactome stable identifier, an external reference database identifier (if applicable), and the cell compartment. Instead of displaying objects within the currently displayed pathway, the pathways not shown in the pathway viewport that contain the search term are displayed.

Selecting the hyperlinked pathway name in the Search Results Detail Panel ("Present in n pathway diagram") will open the new pathway diagram in the Pathway Browser and select the corresponding object in the new diagram.

Searching within an Enhanced High Level Diagram (EHL)

In the example below, the search has identified IL6R and produced a dropdown list of matches. The first match is to a protein, as indicated by the icon on the left. The second match with the icon showing a double helix is a DNA sequence or gene. Note that if IL6R was represented in two cellular compartments in this diagram it would appear twice in this initial search result. The Reactome stable identifier and cell compartment annotations are also provided for each molecule or event type in the search results. **Note:** as the search term is entered, the search tool will predict results that match this search term and displays a drop-down list of these matches.

Although not shown below, when a new search is performed, the recent search results are displayed at the bottom of the search results window. Clicking the "Clear History" button will remove the search terms from the history.

The deep blue highlighted bar, which indicates that there are 23 results shown in "This diagram" and 30 results shown in "All diagrams". Only the two results are clearly shown in the results window. To view additional results, move the cursor over the window and scroll down. Each result term has a symbol (to the left) representing the type of molecule or event it is. The first result, with a blue circle icon to the left of the name, represent matches to the IL6R protein, located in the plasma membrane. The second result, with a double-helix icon to the left, is the IL6R gene. The Reactome stable identifier and cell compartment annotations are also provided for each molecule or event type that is displayed.

In the following image, selecting the first item in the Search Results Panel (IL6R) causes a second drop-down Search Results Details Panel to appear. The at the top of the Details Panel, additional annotations are displayed that include the molecule or event type, the Reactome stable identifier, and the cell compartment. Additional annotations are listed below describing the involvement of the object within the EHL. Selecting pathway names in the Search Results Detail Panel will select the corresponding object in the EHL. If it is not visible, the EHL will re-centre to show it in the

Getting Started

Search Exercises

This exercise encourages you to find information via the menu bar and Search

1. What's the latest news item on the Reactome Home page?
2. How many human proteins are represented in Reactome?
3. What's the first item listed that will be included in the next release?
4. Is VAV2 in Reactome?
5. How many reactions involve VAV2?
6. Are there any complexes that include VAV2?

7. Is CRB2 in Reactome?

Details Panel

The Details Panel is the bottom right panel of the Pathway Browser. It displays the details of molecular objects or events when selected in the Pathway Diagram or Hierarchy. The details shown depend on the type of molecule or event selected. The Details Panel can be revealed/hidden using the middle Layout button.

The Details Panel has several tabs:

The Description tab

This tab contains the defining details of the selected diagram object. These details vary, depending on what is selected in the diagram. For example, reaction details always describe the input and output molecules, and where relevant, the enzyme catalyst. Other items in the Description tab may include:

Summation – a summary of the molecular event, often with background information and additional literature citations

Preceding/Following Events - Links to reactions that precede/follow this reaction.

Cellular Compartment - Identifies the cellular compartment for the reaction, with the associated Gene Ontology (GO) term.

Inferred from another species - Reactome represents human biology. Wherever possible key references contain experimental data obtained using human reagents. If the only data available is from model organisms, a human event may be inferred from this data, if the Author, Curator and Reviewer agree that this inference is valid. The inferred event is labelled with an icon 'Inferred from another species' in the Hierarchy and in the Details panel, where there is a link to the molecular details of the event as it occurs in the model organism and the supporting literature references. A description of the inference process can be found [here](#).

Computationally Inferred To – This drop-down list represents the species available for computationally predicted pathways, inferred from Reactome's human pathway. References – all events in Reactome include links to original research publications containing experimental data, the evidence that the event has been shown to exist.

Authored - an expert biologist who contributed materials allowing construction of the reaction/pathway. All Reactome pathways are authored by an expert biologist.

Reviewed – all Reactome pathways are peer reviewed by an expert biologist who verifies the content provided by the Author.

Details are organised into panels. Panels that have a plus icon on the right hand side can be expanded to reveal further levels of detail by clicking on the icon or the detail name.

Clicking the plus icon reveals further details:

Panels that represent molecules have an icon on the left hand side that represents the molecule subtype, e.g. the protein icon is a green circle. Mouse-over the icon to see an explanation of the subtype. The icon is a selection button; clicking the icon replaces the current details with a new panel of details specific to the selected molecule, which is highlighted on the pathway diagram.

The Molecules Tab

This tab details all the molecules involved in the pathway displayed in the panel above. When a pathway name is highlighted in the hierarchy, the total number of molecules in that pathway is shown in a bubble on the molecules tab.

Molecules are grouped into the subtypes Protein, Chemical Compound, Sequences (for DNA/RNA) and Other.

If an item is selected in the diagram, the corresponding molecules are highlighted in the details panel, and the bubble next to the 'Molecules' tab enumerates the fraction of the total pathway molecules that are represented in that item.

The screenshot shows the Reactome pathway viewer interface. The main window displays a pathway diagram for 'Toll Like Receptor 3 (TLR3) Cascade' in Homo sapiens. The diagram is set in the cytosol and shows the following components and interactions:

- TLR3** (Toll Like Receptor 3) binds to **viral dsRNA:TLR3**.
- SARM-1** binds to **viral dsRNA:TLR3**.
- TICAM1** (TICAM1) binds to **viral dsRNA:TLR3**.
- TRAF3** (TRAF3) binds to **viral dsRNA:TLR3**.
- The complex **TRAF3:TICAM1:viral dsRNA:TLR3** is formed.
- TLR3 ligand** is also shown.
- SARM:TICAM1:viral dsRNA:TLR3** is another complex shown.

Below the diagram, the 'Molecules' tab is selected, showing a list of proteins:

Chemical Compounds (0/10)	Proteins (3/97)
O15455	UniProt:O15455 TLR3 (26x)
Q6SZW1-1	UniProt:Q6SZW1-1 SARM1 (2x)
Q8IUJ6	UniProt:Q8IUJ6 TICAM1 (25x)
O00206	UniProt:O00206 TLR4 (1x)
O14733	UniProt:O14733 MAP2K7 (3x)
O14920	UniProt:O14920 IKKB (6x)
O15111	UniProt:O15111 CHUK (6x)
Q43187	UniProt:Q43187 IRAK2 (2x)

The Download button to the right of the pathway name and species buttons allows details of the molecules to be downloaded in several formats. Click on the buttons to select the fields you want included in the output file, and the format of the file. Click Download to save the file.

The Structures Tab

The content displayed in this tab depends on the type of object or event selected in the pathway diagram. For Reactions it will display equivalent reaction diagrams from the [Rhea](#) database if available:

The panel has a link top-left to details in the Rhea database.

The molecular structures are linked to the [ChEBI](#) database:

ChEBI

Home | Advanced Search | Browse | Documentation | Download | Tools | About ChEBI

ChEBI > Main

CHEBI:15589 - (S)-malate(2-)

Main | ChEBI Ontology | Automatic Xrefs | Reactions | Pathways | Models

ChEBI Name: **(S)-malate(2-)**

ChEBI ID: **CHEBI:15589**

ChEBI ASCII Name: (S)-malate(2-)

Definition: An optically active form of malate having (S)-configuration.

Stars: ★★★★★ This entity has been manually annotated by the ChEBI Team.

Secondary ChEBI IDs: CHEBI:11066, CHEBI:13140, CHEBI:18784

Supplier Information: No supplier information found for this compound.

Download: Molfile | XML | SDF

For Proteins or pathway objects that represent sets or complexes, corresponding structure information from [PDB](#) is represented if available:

Overview Molecules **Structures (1/1)** Expression Processes Downloads

UniProt: O15519 CFLAR Chain: A Resolution: 1.90 Coverage: 0.57 PDB Range: [1, 272]
 UniProt Range: [209, 480]

3h11

 All other structures for O15519

For simple molecules, the structures tab represents information from the ChEBI database:

ChEBI Name 3-phospho-D-glyceroyl dihydrogen phosphate

ChEBI ID CHEBI:16001

Definition The (R)-enantiomer of 3-phosphoglyceroyl dihydrogen phosphate.

Stars ★★

Secondary ChEBI IDs CHEBI:1658, CHEBI:11881, CHEBI:20189

The Expression Tab

This tab represents expression information obtained from the [Expression Atlas](#). Note that at the moment, only information from the first 50 genes in the pathway is displayed or available for download from the Expression Atlas widget.

[RNA-seq of coding RNA from tissue samples of 122 human individuals representing 32 different tissues](#)

[See more expression data at Expression Atlas.](#)
 This expression view is provided by [Expression Atlas](#).
 Please send any queries or feedback to arrayexpress-atlas@ebi.ac.uk.

The Analysis Tab

This tab displays the results of analyses – see the section Reactome Tools for further details

The Downloads Tab

The Downloads Tab contains buttons to start a download of the currently displayed pathway in several human-readable or computationally reusable formats.

The screenshot shows a navigation bar with tabs: Description, Molecules, Structures, Expression, Analysis, and Downloads. The Downloads tab is active. Below the navigation bar, the pathway name 'Platelet homeostasis' is displayed. A green notification bar states: 'The download options below are for the selected pathway, not individual events or entities selected in it.' Below this, there are seven download buttons: 8ML, 8GN, BioPAX2, BioPAX3, PDF, DOC, and a button with a molecular structure icon.

Get Started:

Exercises:

1. Find the reaction 'Activated type I receptor phosphorylates SMAD2/3 directly'. What pathway does it belong to?
2. In which cellular compartment does this reaction take place?
3. What is the GO molecular function associated with the catalyst?
4. What reference has experimental verification of this reaction?
5. Is this reaction predicted to occur in *Canis familiaris*? In *C. elegans*?
6. Is this event likely to occur in liver?
7. Are 3D structures available for TGF-beta1?

More info:

Pathway Description tab:

The Description tab for a pathway includes:

- pathway name
- species

- stable identifier
- pathway summation
- a drop-down menu to select species for which the pathway is computationally predicted to be conserved, where appropriate. A description of the inference process can be found here.
- the GO biological process term for the pathway, where appropriate. Expanding the panel provides a link-out to GO.
- literature references

Reaction Description tab:

The Description tab for a reaction includes:

- reaction name
- a stable identifier
- pathway summation
- links to external identifiers, where appropriate. For instance, a reaction that describes a binding event may link out to IntAct records that corroborate the interaction.
- Input/Output: Identifies the input/output molecules, sets or complexes for this reaction. Icons to the right of these named items link to further information in Reactome.
- Catalyst (when relevant): The protein or complex that catalyzes the reaction. The Gene Ontology molecular function term that represents the activity of a catalyst or transporter within the reaction will be listed. If the catalyst is a complex, the component that enables the reaction to occur will be identified as the 'active unit'.
- Preceding event(s): A list of events that occur immediately before the event being viewed.
- Following event(s): A list of events that occur immediately after the event being viewed.
- Cellular compartment:
- Inferred from another species (when relevant): This indicates that event has not been experimentally demonstrated in humans, but has been inferred on the basis of data acquired for another species.
 - Clicking on the '+' button to the right of the reaction name in this panel reveals the summation and literature references for the supporting reaction in the other species;
 - clicking on the reaction icon to the left of the reaction name in this panel switches the user to the corresponding pathway of the species from which the

human reaction has been inferred. Note that the manually curated event in the non-human species is not currently displayed in this pathway; instead, a computationally-inferred reaction is shown. This will be addressed in future updates. The human representation of the pathway can be restored either by clicking on the back button of the browser or by re-selecting 'Homo sapiens' in the species selector in the top panel of the Reactome website.

- Computationally inferred to: Links to descriptions of the events in other species that are either confirmed to occur in a very similar way in both species, or have been electronically inferred.
- Positively (or Negatively) regulated by: The protein or complex that regulates the reaction.
- References that contain experimental data verifying the reaction, with a link-out to PubMed, when applicable.
- Authors: The expert biologists that contributed materials that allowed this reaction to be created in Reactome.
- Reviewers: The expert biologists that verified the content for this pathway.

Physical Entity Description tab:

The details of any protein, small molecule, complex or set represented in a pathway diagram can be displayed in the Details panel by selecting the object within the diagram. Clicking a '+' or '-' icon associated with the different displayed fields within the Detail panel tabs will show or hide more information about the protein, small molecule, complex and set.

The Description tab may display include the following information depending upon what physical entity is selected:

- Link to corresponding entries in other databases: Cross-reference to identifiers used for this molecule in external reference databases, with hyperlinks to the record.
- Cellular compartment: The cellular compartment that contains this molecule, with hyperlink to the corresponding GO term.
- Computationally inferred orthologues: Lists equivalent molecules in other species if these have been inferred to exist. A description of the inference process can be found here.
- Components: If a complex is selected in the diagram, its components are listed here.
- Produced by: If a complex is selected in the diagram, this tab in the details panel will list all the reactions in Reactome that produce it as an output. Clicking on the '+' reveals summation and literature references for these reactions.

- Consumed by events: If a complex is selected in the diagram, this tab in the details panel will list all reactions in Reactome that use it as an input. Clicking on the '+' reveals summation and literature references for these reactions.

Download tab:

The Download tab provides options for the user to download different files types for the selected pathways. These files include:

- SBML: An exchange format used by systems biologists for their models.
- SBGN: An exchange format used to represent pathway and network diagrams.
- BioPAX2: An exchange format used by systems biologists for their models.
- BioPAX3: An exchange format used by systems biologists for their models.
- PDF: Text dump of the pathway, organized to look like a research report.
- Word: A document format compatible with Microsoft and other word processor software.
- Protege: A format used for ontology exchange.

[SBML](#), [SBGN](#) and [BioPAX](#) are exchange formats of interest to bioinformaticians. [Word](#) and [PDF](#) are familiar document formats, providing you with a convenient "document" of the pathway. [Protégé](#) is an extensible, platform-independent environment for creating and editing ontologies and knowledge bases, this download is likely to be of interest to those wishing to extend Reactome functionality.

The complete Reactome textbook of biological processes in PDF or RTF format, the complete set of human reactions in Reactome (in SBML or BioPAX level 2 or 3 format), and a list of human protein-protein interaction pairs are available to download from the Download page, linked to the Menu Bar on the Reactome homepage.

To find out about how Reactome generates SBML, see [SBML At Reactome](#).

For general information about SBML, [click here](#). For more information about BioPAX [click here](#).

Analysis Tools

Jump to section:

- [Analysis Data](#)
- [Analysis Gene Expression](#)
- [Species Comparison](#)
- [Tissue Distribution](#)

See our Youtube Video that introduces our [Analysis Tools!](#)

Analysis Data

Click on the 'Browse Pathways' button on the Homepage. In the next page, click the 'Analysis' button on the top right:

Alternatively, select the 'Analyze Data' button on the Homepage:

Analyze Data

Merges pathway identifier
mapping,
over-representation, and
expression analysis

This opens a submission form, where you can select the analysis you want to perform, paste in or browse to a file containing your data, or use an example data set.

There are two sections to the submission form. The 'Analyse your data' section is selected by default to submit your data. Several different analyses can be performed, depending on the format of your data.

If your data is a single column of identifiers such as UniProt IDs, gene symbols or ChEBI IDs, they are mapped to pathways and over-representation and pathway-topology analyses are run. Over-representation analysis is a statistical (hypergeometric distribution) test that determines whether certain Reactome pathways are over-represented (enriched) in the submitted data. It answers the question 'Does my list contain more proteins for pathway X than would be expected by chance?' This test produces a probability score, which is corrected for false discovery rate using the Benjamini-Hochberg method.

Pathway topology analysis considers the connectivity between molecules that is represented by the pathway steps (which we refer to as reactions) in the pathway. It groups all the molecules represented in each reaction as a pathway 'unit'. If any of these molecules are represented in your query set, this is considered a match to that reaction. This may give a better indication of the proportion of the pathway that matches your data, rather than the number of molecules that are common between your data and the pathway. It may also indicate that your data matches the start, end or a particular branch of a pathway process. This test does not have a probability score.

If your data has one or more additional columns of numbers it will be recognized as expression data and expression data overlay will be performed. Note that this data format should include a header row. The first column header should start with the # symbol. The numbers are used to produce a scaled coloured overlay over Reactome pathway diagrams, as a means to visualize

relative expression levels. Note that the numeric values do not have to be expression data, for instance by using gene association scores the same analysis can be used to visualize genotyping results.

Identifier mapping

The submission process recognizes many types of identifiers. As part of the pre-analysis, they are mapped to Reactome molecules. The ideal identifiers to use are UniProt IDs for proteins, ChEBI IDs for small molecules, and either HGNC gene symbols or ENSEMBL IDs for DNA/RNA molecules, as these are our main external reference sources for proteins and small molecules. Many other identifiers are recognized and mapped to appropriate Reactome molecules. Accepted identifiers include HUGO gene symbols, GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ, RefPep, RefSeq, EntrezGene, MIM, InterPro, EnsEMBL protein, EnsEMBL gene, EnsEMBL transcript, and some Affymetrix and Agilent probe IDs. UniProt isoforms may be specified using the format P12345-2. If the -n suffix is omitted, this canonical form and all isoforms of it will be matched. Mixed identifier lists (different protein identifiers or protein/gene identifiers) may be used. Identifiers must be one per line. Protein-specific identifiers will typically map to protein entities, while gene-specific identifiers will map to the gene, transcript and derived proteins. If desired results can be filtered to show protein-specific or gene/transcript-specific results, details below.

Below is an example of the identifiers-only format:

Click the Continue button. A second options selection page appears:

Analysis tools

Analyse your data

Species Comparison

Tissue Distribution

Reactome v67

Click to learn more about our analysis tools

Your data Options Analysis

Step 1: Select a file from your computer or paste your own data and click on the corresponding "Continue" button.

Select data file for analysis: Choose File No file chosen Continue

Paste your data to analyse or try example data sets:

```
#GBM UniProt
P01823
Q99758
O15439
O43184
Q13444
P82987
P04083
Q725R6
P27540
Q13315
P36543
Q13535
Q96G04
Q13145
Q07812
P56945
P19415
P11274
P51587
```

Some examples:

- UniProt accession list
- Gene name list
- Gene NCBI / Entrez list
- Small molecules (ChEBI)
- Small molecules (KEGG)
- Microarray data
- Metabolomics data
- Cancer Gene Census (COSMIC)
- Tissue Specific Expression (HPA)

Clear Continue

Project to human is checked by default. With this option selected, all non-human identifiers in your query are converted by the analysis service to their human equivalents. In general, this

maximizes the chances of a successful match to Reactome's curated human pathways. However, if you want to use non-human identifiers and match these to our computationally-inferred non-human pathways, uncheck the box. You may also choose to uncheck this box if your query consists of a mixture of human and microbial identifiers and your goal is to find pathways that represent the processes of infection.

'Include Interactors' is unchecked by default. With this box unchecked, your query will consider only Reactome pathways. If you choose to check the box, your query will consider Reactome pathways that have been expanded by including all available protein-protein interactors from the IntAct database. This greatly increases the size of Reactome pathways, which maximizes the chances of matching your submitted identifiers to the expanded pathway, but will include interactors that have not undergone manual curation by Reactome and may include interactors that have no biological significance, or unexplained relevance. In practice it is preferable to query with 'Include Interactors' unchecked in the first instance, followed by a repeated query with 'Include interactors' selected, if a substantial proportion of the submitted identifiers do not match a Reactome pathway, to see if they can be identified as interactors.

Results for Identifier lists without associated numeric values

If you submit a single column of protein or small molecule identifiers they are mapped to pathways and over-representation and pathway-topology analyses are performed. The results will resemble the example below.

Analysis results are shown in the Analysis tab, within the Details Panel. All Reactome pathways are shown, in blocks of 20 pathways, ranked by the p-value obtained from over-representation analysis. If multiple pathways have the same p-value, they are ranked by the number of

identifiers in the query that match the pathway. The number of molecules matched/total number of molecules and FDR values are added to the right side of pathway names in the Hierarchy Panel. The names of reactions that match at least one identifier in the query, representing positive pathway topology analysis hits, are boxed in orange.

In the Analysis tab, clicking on the name of a pathway will select it in the Hierarchy, which if necessary will expand hidden hierarchical levels to show the pathway, while the name becomes highlighted in dark blue.

By default, molecules of all types (protein, small molecules, genes, transcripts) are used for over-representation analysis, but it is possible to restrict the analysis results to a specific subtype by using a drop-down list located top-left of the results table. Selecting one of the subsets will display results that consider only the selected molecular subtype.

The columns in analysis details represent:

1. Pathway name: Click the name to open the pathway.
2. Entities found: the number of curated molecules of the type selected with Results Type that are common between the submitted data set and the pathway named in column 1. Click on this number to display the matched submitted identifiers and their mapping to Reactome molecules.
3. Entities total: The total number of curated molecules of the type selected with Results Type within the pathway named in column 1.
4. Interactors found (if this option was selected). The number of interactor molecules of the type selected with Results Type that are common between the submitted data set and the pathway named in column 1. Click on this number to display the matched submitted identifiers and their mapping to Reactome molecules.
5. Interactors total (if this option was selected): The total number of interactor molecules of the type selected with Results Type within the pathway named in column 1.
6. Entities ratio: Put simply, the proportion of Reactome pathway molecules represented by this pathway. Calculated as the ratio of entities from this pathway that are molecules of the type selected with Results Type Vs. all entities of the type selected with Results Type.
7. Entities pvalue: The result of the statistical test for over-representation, for molecules of the results type selected.
8. Entities FDR: False discovery rate. Corrected over-representation probability.

9. Reactions found: The number of reactions in the pathway that are represented by at least one molecule in the submitted data set, for the molecule type selected with Results Type.
10. Reactions Total: The number of reactions in the pathway that contain molecules of the type selected with Results Type.
11. Reactions ratio: Put simply, the proportion of Reactome reactions represented by this pathway. Calculated as the ratio of reactions from this pathway that contain molecules of the type selected with Results Type Vs. all Reactome reactions that contain molecules of the type selected with Results Type.
12. Species Name.

When an analysis has run, the Pathway Browser will display the Pathway Overview. All pathways that contain identifiers from your submitted list are highlighted, using a coloured scale to indicate the corrected probability (FDR). The colour scheme can be changed using the colour profiles tab (artists easel icon) on the pop-out Settings panel, found on the right-hand edge of the pathway panel. Selecting coverage in the Overexpression panel will alter the Pathway Overview display to show additional event crosslinks corresponding to areas that are heavily covered vs regions that have lower coverage (as shown in the pValue view), and making it easier to visualize the pathways enriched within your dataset.

The highlighting of pathways in the Overview provides an at-a-glance representation of analysis results for all pathways. To see the details of a specific pathway, double-click the node representing the pathway in the overview or in the Pathway Hierarchy on the left. Alternatively, click it once to select it and use the Show All button (square with outward pointing triangles inside) in the top left corner of the Overview panel. The Overview can be navigated using the mouse scroll wheel to zoom in and out and click and drag to move it around. Alternatively, use the navigation buttons in the bottom right corner of the overview panel. At any level of the pathway, the diagram key can be found by clicking the compass symbol in the top right corner.

Enhanced high-level diagrams represent analysis results within the label for subpathways. The label background changes from blue to white, a yellow band is used to indicate the proportion of the pathway that is represented in the query dataset. A grey bar above the label indicates the number of pathway entities that are represented in the query dataset, the total number of entities in the pathway, and the FDR corrected probability score

In Pathway Diagrams, entities are re-coloured (yellow in the default colour scheme) if they were represented in the submitted data set. Complexes, Sets and Subpathway Icons are coloured to represent the proportion that is represented in the submitted identifier list. In the figure below, Insulin receptor is yellow indicating that it was in the submitted list. Insulin was not in the submitted list so it is not re-coloured. The complex of insulin:Insulin receptor is part re-coloured, part not, indicating that some molecules in the complex were represented in the submitted dataset while others were not.

If the Include Interactors option was checked, entities with interactors that were part of the submitted identifier list have a ribbon across the top right corner. In the example below, RASA1 is not a direct match with the submitted list of identifiers but has interactors that match the list. The interactors are displayed; the yellow overlay indicates the matching interactors. PTPN11 is a direct match and has interactors that match the list. A limited number of interactors are displayed to avoid crowding.

At the right side of the Analysis results details is a button indicating the number of submitted identifiers that were not successfully matched to molecules in Reactome. Click the button to produce a list.

Results for: TOTAL (1123) Type: Overrepresentation [Data: Uniprot_accession_list] Results Identifiers not found: 73	
Not found identifiers	
Q96KG3	
P3Q1308521	
P162O95P533967	
O15421	
P43P00751	
P106435	
P1P017326	
P18440861	
P064937	

Results for Identifier lists with associated numeric values (expression representation)

To run expression analysis, submit your data in a format that includes a first row of column headers. The header for column 1 must start with the # symbol. The first column must contain protein, compound or other suitable identifiers, such as probe IDs. All other columns must be numeric values, with no alphabetical characters. The analysis tool will interpret your data as expression data. The numeric values are used to colour objects in pathway diagrams. This view was created for microarray data, but any dataset that consists of a list of identifiers with associated numeric values can be used, e.g. quantitative proteomics, GWAS scores.

The tool is launched using the Analyse data button in the Pathway Browser header bar. Either paste your data into the submission form or browse to a saved file (or select an example file).

The figure below shows the correct data format. Each row must have an identifier in the first column (a header row is optional).

The submission process recognized many types of identifiers. As part of the pre-analysis, they are mapped to equivalent UniProt accessions or for small compounds to ChEBI IDs. These are the ideal identifiers to use with Reactome analysis tools. Other identifiers that are recognized and converted to UniProt equivalents include HUGO gene symbols, GenBank/EMBL/DBJ, RefPep, RefSeq, EntrezGene, MIM and InterPro IDs, some Affymetrix and Agilent probe IDs, Ensembl protein, transcript and gene identifiers. Identifiers that contain only numbers such as those from OMIM and EntrezGene must be prefixed by the source database name and a colon e.g. MIM:602544, EntrezGene:55718. Mixed identifier lists (different protein identifiers or protein/gene identifiers) may be used. Identifiers must be one per line.

By default, all non-human identifiers are mapped to their human equivalents, unless the Project to the human checkbox is unselected.

After column 1, all other columns must contain numbers, representing expression or other values. Comma-separated values(CSV) and tab separated value (TSV) files can be used. When submitted, columns of numbers are considered as separate samples or experimental conditions. The values are used to overlay colour onto pathway diagrams. An Experiment Browser tool allows you to select and view-overlays for each submitted data column. This tool is the panel that appears in the bottom-centre of both the pathways overview and the diagram viewer when expression data columns have been submitted. In that panel, the user can move through the different time series (and also play it as a "movie"). This is particularly useful for visualizing time-points or a disease progression.

The screenshot shows the Reactome v67 Analysis tools interface. The main area is titled 'Your data' and contains the following elements:

- Navigation:** 'Your data', 'Options', and 'Analysis' tabs.
- Instructions:** 'Step 1: Select a file from your computer or paste your own data and click on the corresponding "Continue" button.'
- File Selection:** 'Select data file for analysis: Choose File No file chosen' with a 'Continue' button.
- Data Entry:** 'Paste your data to analyse or try example data sets:'
- Example Data Table:**

#Probeset	10h_control	10h	14h	18h	24h
1053_at	8.840878	7.147358	6.786705	6.794622	7.475157
1735_at	6.869888	6.99184	7.129922	7.112222	7.64721
1861_at	6.437999	6.628892	6.28117	6.487735	5.717813
200000_s_at	9.381569	9.718802	9.874874	9.934639	9.495911
200001_at	12.555275	12.513865	12.564419	12.538642	12.439376
200003_s_at	12.481259	12.054883	12.275169	12.286342	12.015470
200005_at	9.468952	9.899299	9.73872	9.538097	9.194383
200012_s_at	12.486269	12.402275	12.382666	12.295653	12.282444
200014_s_at	10.371458	9.548578	9.978313	9.871472	8.753136
200016_s_at	12.110468	11.913288	11.938524	11.899243	11.458185
200022_at	12.205838	11.927471	12.464725	12.481422	11.932566
200023_s_at	10.177248	9.982753	9.998862	10.248412	9.513486
200024_at	12.41513	12.313568	12.422621	12.368337	12.178793
200032_s_at	12.364917	12.368961	12.563211	12.341325	12.278704
200034_s_at	11.882912	11.6947	11.817369	11.883983	11.527811
200038_s_at	12.392395	12.374689	12.46662	12.456494	12.388124
200039_s_at	10.485458	10.341833	10.429499	10.388328	9.818715
200044_at	10.247336	9.962542	10.152532	10.242334	9.744894
200051_at	9.87481	9.222119	9.159484	9.139284	8.863286
- Examples List:** UniProt accession list, Gene name list, Gene NCBI / Entrez list, Small molecules (ChEBI), Small molecules (KEGG), Microarray data, Metabolomics data, Cancer Gene Census (COSMIC), Tissue Specific Expression (HPA).
- Buttons:** 'Clear' and 'Continue' buttons are located at the bottom of the data entry area.

The results may take a few seconds to appear.

The results page is very similar to that seen following submission of a simple one-column list of identifiers, with extra columns in the Analysis details following column 9. These extra columns represent the submitted expression values.

Clicking on a pathway name launches the Pathway Browser and displays the relevant Pathway Diagram (see example below).

Objects in the Pathway Diagram are re-coloured according to the numeric values submitted. The colours are based on a scale as represented in a bar on the right-hand side. There are several colour schemes, selected using the Settings pop-out panel on the right side. The scale (on the right side) automatically adjusts to fit the range of values in the dataset.

Objects that were not represented in the input data are not re-coloured.

Objects with bands of colour represent complexes or sets containing more than one molecule. When zoomed out, the colour of the band reflects the average of the values submitted, for molecules represented in the dataset. The size of the band reflects the proportion of molecules that had submitted values. Zoom in to see individual bands, for each molecule that had a submitted value, arranged alphabetically by name. The bands of colour now reflect the values submitted. If multiple columns of values were submitted, representing multiple samples, e.g. time-points or a disease progression, the order of the bands will be the same for each sample.

To view details of the components of a complex or set right click it. This opens a Contextual Information Panel (CIP) (see figure above). This has two tabs - Molecules and Pathways. Molecules show the participating molecules, and if an expression analysis has been performed, their expression values. Pathways identify whether the selected object is present in any other Reactome pathways, with links to the appropriate Pathway Diagrams.

Multiple CIPs can be opened and pinned so they remain visible when other entities are selected.

The browser remembers CIPs that were pinned on the last visit (for up to 5 diagrams).

The orange Experiment Browser toolbar (bottom left in the figure above) is used to step through the columns of your data, e.g. time-points or disease progression. Move between them

by clicking the arrow buttons. The header of the data column (if present) is displayed between the arrows. The Pathway Diagram will re-colour to reflect the new values.

For an explanation of the results seen in the Identifier results tab see the explanation in the section Results for Identifier lists without associated numeric values.

Analysis Token

Once the analysis is finished, this data structure can also be serialised to a bin file to persist the result. In addition, associating the file to a token provides an easy way to access the data. You can keep the token once the initial analysis is finished and the results are only temporarily available for 7 days unless you re-perform your analysis with the same data. However, the analysis results will disappear after each quarterly update of the Reactome data. At this time, analysis result links and tokens will no longer work anymore due to the data update, we recommend you to save the analysis results report(PDF) for future use.

Analysis Report

For some of our users, it might be important to preserve a pathway analysis for the long-term. Following the pathway analysis, the results can be downloaded as an easy-to-read PDF report by clicking the 'Report (PDF)' button located at the bottom left corner of the Details panel. The first page of the PDF report will look something like this:

Pathway Analysis Report

Gene names from liver

This report contains the pathway analysis results for the submitted sample 'Gene names from liver'. Analysis was performed against Reactome version 65 on 30/07/2018 using any resource identifiers for the mapping. The web link to these results is:

<https://reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/#/ANALYSIS=MjAxODA3MTEzMzUwNDI0ODY%3D>

Please keep in mind that analysis results are temporarily stored on our server. The storage period depends on usage of the service but is at least 7 days. As a result, please note that this URL is only valid for a limited time period and it might have expired.

The sections of the analysis report represent:

1. Introduction: An overview of the Reactome project and the Analysis tool.

2. **Properties:** A summary details of the analysis output. For example, the number of identifiers that were found in Reactome.
3. **Genome-wide overview:** A genome-wide overview of the results of your pathway analysis.
4. **Most significant pathways:** A table of the top 25 pathway hits. Results are ranked based upon the most significant FDR value. The embedded links within the pathway name of the table will connect to the Pathway details (Section #5).
5. **Pathway details:** A summary view of each pathway hit. The pathway identifier in parenthesis when clicked will connect with the Pathway details page on the Reactome website. A pathway diagram, pathway summation, edit history, list of identifiers found, and references (when available) are also provided.
6. **Identifiers found:** A table of the synonyms or identifiers that were found in Reactome based upon the input list.
7. **Identifiers not found:** A table of the synonyms or identifiers that were not found in Reactome based upon the input list.

Analysis Gene Expression

ReactomeGSA is a new pathway analysis tool integrated into the Reactome ecosystem. Its main feature is that it performs quantitative pathway analyses (so-called gene set analyses). This increases the statistical power of the differential expression analysis, which is directly performed on the pathway level. More information click [here](#).

Species Comparison

The manually-curated human pathways in Reactome are used to predict equivalent pathways in 18 other species. This automated, computational process is based on orthology. A full description of the inference process can be found on the Home page under Documentation, Orthology Prediction.

The Species Comparison tool allows you to compare human pathways with computationally-predicted pathways in model organisms, highlighting the elements of the pathway that are common to both species and those that may be absent in the model organism.

Species Comparison is launched using the Analysis button in the Pathway Browser header bar. In the Species Comparison section, select one of the species in the dropdown list. Click the Go button:

The results are ready to view when analysis results appear (or are updated if already present) in the Pathway Hierarchy.

Clicking on a pathway name launches the Pathway Browser and displays the relevant Pathway Diagram (see example below).

The colour of reaction objects indicates the result of the comparison:

- Yellow indicates that the protein has an inferred equivalent in the comparison species.
- No overlay indicates that inference was not possible. This is always the case for small molecules, DNA and other objects that have no UniProt entry (or did not at the time the pathway was constructed).
- Objects with bands of colour represent complexes or sets containing more than one molecule. The bands of colour reflect the inference success for the molecules within the complex/set.

To view species comparison results for a complex or set hover your mouse over the object and a small blue triangle will appear on its right side. Select this to open the Contextual information Panel.

This reveals a table representing all the proteins involved in the complex/set. Each square in the grid represents one component of the complex/set, coloured as described above.

The species bar at the bottom of the Pathway Diagram (see example above) can be used to turn off species comparison colouring, by unchecking the box.

Refer to the Navigating Pathway Diagrams section for more information on the diagram content.

Tissue Distribution

Traditionally, reactions in Reactome represent events that occur within a single generic human cell. It would, however, be useful to classify reactions into different human tissue types, as to provide an evolving picture of the reactions and pathways in different cell- and tissue-specific environments. We have imported protein expression in different cell/tissue types from the [Human Protein Atlas](#) (HPA), overlaid these proteins on Reactome data, and extracted the subset of reactions for that particular cell type. The HPA data reflecting the expression of the protein-coding genes in 44 different human tissues can be visualized through the Analysis tools.

Tissue Distribution is launched using the Analysis button in the Pathway Browser header bar. In the Tissue Distribution section, select the one experimental tissue dataset [HPA (E-PROT-3) - Expression Atlas] in the dropdown list. Once the window refreshes, select the 'Available Tissues' in the left panel and hit the 'Add' button to add tissue expression data to the analysis tool. Press the "Add All" button, if you would like to adjoin all the tissue expression data. Use the 'Remove all' and 'Remove' buttons to delete tissue expression data from the filter list. Once you have selected all the appropriate tissues, click the Go button to start the analysis.

The results are ready to view when analysis results appear (or are updated if already present) in the Pathway Hierarchy and the Overview panel.

Clicking on a pathway name launches the Pathway Browser and displays the relevant Pathway Diagram (see example below).

Objects in the Pathway Diagram are re-coloured according to the numeric values submitted. The colours are based on a scale as represented in a bar on the right-hand side. There are several colour schemes, selected using the Settings pop-out panel on the right side. The scale (on the right side) automatically adjusts to fit the range of values in the dataset.

Objects that were not represented in the input data are not re-coloured.

Objects with bands of colour represent complexes or sets containing more than one molecule. When zoomed out, the colour of the band reflects the average of the values submitted, for molecules represented in the dataset. The size of the band reflects the proportion of molecules that had submitted values. Zoom in to see individual bands, for each molecule that had a submitted value, arranged alphabetically by name. The bands of colour now reflect the values

submitted. If multiple columns of values were submitted, representing multiple samples, e.g. time-points or a disease progression, the order of the bands will be the same for each sample.

To view details of the components of a complex or set right click it. This opens a Contextual Information Panel (CIP) (see figure above). This has two tabs - Molecules and Pathways. Molecules show the participating molecules, and if an expression analysis has been performed, their expression values. Pathways identify whether the selected object is present in any other Reactome pathways, with links to the appropriate Pathway Diagrams.

Multiple CIPs can be opened and pinned so they remain visible when other entities are selected.

The browser remembers CIPs that were pinned on the last visit (for up to 5 diagrams).

The Experiment Browser toolbar (bottom left in the figure above) is used to step through the columns of your data, e.g. time-points or disease progression. Move between them by clicking the arrow buttons. The header of the data column (if present) is displayed between the arrows. The Pathway Diagram will re-colour to reflect the new values.

Clicking on the illustration icon (photo-like icon in the top right of the Pathway Browser) displays the relevant Pathway Illustration (see example below).

Getting Started

Pathway Analysis Exercises

This exercise is to check that you understand the results of Pathway Analysis.

On the Home page, open the Pathway Browser. Click on the Analyse Data button. When the submission form appears, in the Analysis Tools section select 'Click here to paste your data or try example data sets...'

...and click on the UniProt accession list button on the right side.

Your submission page should look like this:

The screenshot shows the 'Analysis tools' interface with three tabs: 'Your data', 'Options', and 'Analysis'. The 'Your data' tab is active. It contains a 'Step 1' instruction: 'Select a file from your computer or paste your own data and click on the corresponding "Continue" button.' Below this is a 'Select data file for analysis:' section with a 'Choose File' button and 'No file chosen' text, and a 'Continue' button. A text area for pasting data is shown with a list of UniProt IDs: #GBM UniProt, P01023, Q99758, O15439, O43184, Q13444, P82987, P04083, Q725R6, P27540, Q13315, P36543, Q13535, Q96G04, Q13145, Q07812, P56645. To the right of the text area are several example data sets: UniProt accession list, Gene name list, Gene NCBI / Entrez list, Small molecules (ChEBI), Small molecules (KEGG), Microarray data, Metabolomics data, and Cancer Gene Census (COSMIC). 'Clear' and 'Continue' buttons are at the bottom of the text area.

Click Continue. Make sure that Project to human is checked, but Include interactors is not. When the results appear:

1. What pathway(s) is (are) most over-represented in this dataset?
2. How many IDs match the pathway at the top of the list?
3. Roughly what proportion of molecules in the pathway are matched?
4. What proportion of reactions are matched?
5. Repeat the analysis but this time check the box to Include interactors. Are the results the same? If not, why?

Expression Analysis Exercises

This exercise is to check that you can run and interpret the results of Expression Analysis.

Launch Expression Analysis and load the example dataset. Click GO When the results are displayed, find the pathway DNA Repair,

1. How many proteins are in this pathway?
2. What proportion of these had expression data?

3. What was the average expression at 24h?
4. Which subpathway has the highest average expression value at 24h? (Hint: move your mouse pointer over the pathway overview diagram, and look at the scale on the right side).

Species Comparison Exercises

This exercise is to check that you can run and interpret Species Comparison results.

Launch Species Comparison and select the species *Danio rerio*. When the results are displayed, use the Pathway Hierarchy to Navigate to 'Hemostasis', 'Dissolution of fibrin clot'.

1. Find PLAT(36-562) top-right of the diagram - what colour is it and why?
2. Find HRG - what colour is it and why?
3. Why is Zn²⁺ (upper left) uncoloured?

More information

Molecular Interaction Overlay

If the user is interested in analyzing the data with interactors from other sources (like IntAct), the 'Include Interactors' options must be selected in the 'Analyze Data' section. Once in the pathway diagram, the Molecular Interaction (MI) overlay allows protein-protein or protein-small molecule interactions to be superimposed onto the pathway diagram. The source depends on the currently selected interaction database. The default interaction database is IntAct (Static), which provides fast access to a quarterly updated and locally-hosted version of IntAct data. Access to the IntAct-hosted dataset and other PSICQUIC sources of interaction data (protein-protein and protein-small molecule) can be selected using the 'PSICQUIC' feature of the Interactor Overlays tab within the Settings panel in the middle-right of the Pathway diagram. A list allows selection of the source of interactors. This is automatically populated by querying the PSICQUIC Registry. If a new database is selected while interactors are displayed on the pathway diagram, the proteins represented by those entities will be used as queries in the new database and the display will automatically update. An 'i' ('information') button to the top right of the Interactor Overlays tab provides a quick tip about using the MI overlay. Selecting either 'Cyan' or 'Teal' in the 'Interactors Colour Profile:' drop-down menu within the 'Colour Palette' feature of the Settings panel will change the interactor colour.

Once a pathway diagram is displayed in the viewport, a small red circle with a white-lettered number in the top right corner of the entity will automatically appear for individual protein and chemical entities that have interactors. The number represents the number of known interactors for the given protein. Pressing the red circle with the cursor will display the interactors. A maximum of 10 interactors is displayed as a ring of blue-bordered boxes (protein interactors) or green-bordered ovals (small molecule interactors) connected by black lines to the selected protein. If the same interactor is connected to more than one entity it is re-used, i.e. connected to all the selected entities in the diagram. Furthermore, if the interactor is a protein or small molecule entity that pre-exists within the pathway diagram, a black line connects the two entities. Pressing the red circle a second time will remove the interactors from the pathway diagram. If an entity interacts with itself, a looping arrow is shown.

A number of actions provide additional information about the interactor and its relationship to the protein entity. These include:

- Hover the mouse pointer over a protein interactor to reveal a tool-tip containing its name and UniProt identifier.
- Click an interactor to open its database entry in a new window.
- Click the line that connects the interactor to the pathway molecule to open details of the interaction from the source database, in a new window.
- Right-click a pathway object, or select the blue triangle that appears on the right side when hovering the mouse pointer over it, to open a pop-up panel (the Contextual Information Panel). Select the Interactors (bottom) tab to display a table of all interactors for the selected object. This table is scrollable and provides additional information about the interactors. Click the 'Interactor' name or accession identifier to connect to UniProt or the interaction source database, respectively. Click the 'id' button to toggle the display of either the interactor name or its database identifier. Click the pin button to fix the open table in position on the pathway diagram. Click the 'X' in the top right corner to close the table view.

IntAct interaction_id: EBI-9468482
 Examples: BRCA1_Q0908_encl_1301411

Home | Advanced Search | About | Resources | Download | Feedback

IntAct > Interaction Details

Interactions (1) | Interactors | Interaction Details | Graph

Publication

PubMed Id: 24728074
 Title: Enhanced prediction of SH2 domain binding potentials using a fluorescence polarization-derived c-Met, c-KIT, ErbB, and androgen receptor interactome.
 Journal: Mol. Cell Proteomics (1535-9476)
 Year of Publication: 2014
 Author List: Leung K.K., Hause R.J., Barkinge J.L., Ciocco M.F., Chou C.P., Jones R.B.

Links
 Show all interactions

Cross References:

Database	Identifier	Secondary Identifier	Qualifier
pubmed	24728074	-	primary-reference
imex	IM-22269	-	imex-primary

Experiment (1006 interactions)

Accession: EBI-9451021 | Host organism: In vitro
 Name: lung-2014-1 | Interaction Detection Method: fms
 Participant Identification Method: tag fluorescence

Cross References:

Database	Identifier	Secondary Identifier	Qualifier
imex	IM-22269	-	imex-primary
pubmed	24728074	-	primary-reference

Annotations:

Topic	Text
data-processing	Some interactions in the experiment involve participants with identical sequences and may seem duplicated. They were kept separated by request of the authors, since they reflect independent replicates for unique pY sites despite being the same peptide sequence.
curation	imex curation
depth	

Interactions from the IntAct database have confidence scores that are generated as the cumulated sum of a weighted score that depends on the interaction detection method and the number of observations. The default lower threshold is 0.45. Interactions with a confidence level equal to or above this are shown. Move the slider bar in the Molecular Overlay toolbar (light grey bar with dark grey slider found at the bottom of the pathway diagram) to the right to raise the confidence level threshold. Interactors below the displayed confidence level will progressively disappear. Move the slider to the left and the interactors will reappear. Click the 'X' in the Molecular Overlay toolbar to hide it.

Zooming, either by using the controls in the bottom right corner of the Pathway Diagram or the mouse scroll wheel, increases the size of all objects displayed in the pathway diagram including interactors. When a sufficient size is reached, the crystal structure of proteins or chemical structure of small molecules will appear in the interactor object, if available.

The details of every interactor for every protein in the displayed pathway can be downloaded as a tab-delimited file by clicking the 'Cloud' button on the Molecular Overlay toolbar or from the Interactor Overlays tab in the Settings panel.

Molecular Interaction Overlay Exercises

This exercise is to check that you can use and interpret Molecular Interaction Overlays

Open the Pathway Diagram for Netrin-1 Signaling.

1. Find the protein NEO1 (top left of the cytosol). How many interactors does it have?
2. What is the confidence score for the interaction between NEO1 and GD3? How many times has this interaction been documented? Hint: This detail is not in Reactome.
3. Find the protein PTPN11 (below and to the right of NEO1). How many interactors does it have? Display interactors for this protein. How many are there? Can you get a list of all of them?
4. What is the easiest way to remove interactors?

ReactomeGSA

Quantitative, multi-dataset Pathway Analysis (ReactomeGSA)

ReactomeGSA is a new pathway analysis tool integrated into the Reactome ecosystem. Its main feature is that it performs quantitative pathway analyses (so-called gene set analyses). This increases the statistical power of the differential expression analysis, which is directly performed on the pathway level.

ReactomeGSA can analyse multiple datasets simultaneously resulting in a comparative pathway analysis. Thereby, it is possible to quickly assess whether the same effect was observed in independent experiments or studies.

ReactomeGSA currently supports quantitative proteomics, transcriptomics, and microarray data. Datasets from all of these methods can be combined in a single analysis. Thereby, ReactomeGSA can perform multi-omics pathway analyses.

Using ReactomeGSA

We currently offer three ways to access ReactomeGSA:

- Reactome's web-based pathway browser (see below)
- From R using our ReactomeGSA Bioconductor R package (see [here](#))
- Programmatically, using the ReactomeGSA API at <https://gsa.reactome.org>

Analyze Gene Expression using ReactomeGSA

You can visit ReactomeGSA [here](#). When you click on the "Analyse gene expression" tab of the Analysis Tools, you will be redirected to ReactomeGSA, where you can perform analyses.

The following tutorial will show you how to: navigate to ReactomeGSA, submit data for analysis, annotate your data, and perform your first analysis. This following tutorial shows a simplified analysis workflow.

ReactomeGSA Tutorial 01

Analyse Gene Expression using ReactomeGSA

This slideshow tutorial will enable you to:

- Navigate to ReactomeGSA
- Run your first analysis

Navigate this tutorial using the left and right keys

Full screen this tutorial by pressing Command/Ctrl + Shift + F

Background information:

ReactomeGSA can analyse multiple datasets simultaneously resulting in a comparative pathway analysis. Thereby, it is possible to quickly assess whether the same effect was observed in independent experiments or studies.

ReactomeGSA currently supports quantitative proteomics, transcriptomics, and microarray data. Datasets from all of these methods can be combined in a single analysis for multi-omic analysis.

Currently, we are working toward a fix for ReactomeGSA that affects certain data types.

If you have a dataset that contains “NA” values, you may encounter some issues.

Please contact our team at help@reactome.org for more information.

We apologize for the inconvenience!

Find Reactions, Proteins and Pathways

[Go!](#)

Pathway Browser

Visualize and interact with
Reactome biological pathways

Analysis Tools

Merges pathway identifier
mapping,
over-representation, and
expression analysis

ReactomeFIViz

Designed to find pathways and
network patterns related to
cancer and other types of
diseases

Documentation

Information to browse the
database and use its principal
tools for data analysis

Analyze gene list

Analyze gene expression

Species Comparison

Tissue Distribution

Reactome v86

Click to learn more about our analysis tools

Your data

Options

Analysis

Step 1: Select a file from your computer or paste your own data and click on the corresponding "Continue" button.

Select data file for analysis: No file chosen

Paste your data to analyse or try example data sets:

Paste your data here or select an example from the right >>

Some examples:

Analyze gene list

Analyze gene expression

Species Comparison

Tissue Distribution

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Some examples:

Welcome to Reactome Pathway Analysis

ReactomeGSA is a powerful tool for understanding the biological significance of gene sets and their expression. It allows researchers to uncover the functional relevance of a list of genes, associated with quantitative data, in the context of biological pathways and processes.

How to Get Started:

1. For your first time using ReactomeGSA, follow our guided tour.
2. Upload Your Gene Expression Dataset: Input a tabular data with gene or protein identifiers by row, and sample by column.
3. Run the Analysis: Start the analysis to identify enriched pathways and gain biological insights.
4. Explore Results: Visualize and explore the results to understand the functional context of your gene list.
5. Interpret Findings: Interpret the findings in the context of your research goals and biological questions.

Get started with ReactomeGSA analysis today and unlock the power of pathway enrichment analysis!

For detailed information, please see [[Griss J et al, MCP, 2020](#)].

 Guided Tour

START

Click on
“Reactome” to
go to the home
page

Welcome to Reactome Pathway Analysis

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[Guided Tour](#)[START](#)

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Click here to follow
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 Guided Tour

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Click here to start your analysis

 Guided Tour

START

Step 1: Select one of the available analysis methods

PADOG

Weighted gene set analysis method that down-weights genes that are present in many pathways.

Camera

A gene set analysis algorithm similar to the classical GSEA algorithm as implemented in the limma package.

ssGSEA

The ssGSEA approach to derive pathway expression values for every sample. Note: The Reactome visualization is only available for up to 15 samples.

Continue

Step 1: Select one of the available analysis methods

Select one of the available analysis methods.

Click "Camera" panel to select the Camera analysis method.

Camera is a good choice for a first analysis: it's the fastest to perform

gene set analysis method that down-weights genes that are in many pathways.

Camera

A gene set analysis algorithm similar to the classical GSEA algorithm as implemented in the limma package.

ssGSEA

The ssGSEA approach to derive pathway expression values for every sample. Note: The Reactome visualization is only available for up to 15 samples.

Continue

Step 1: Select one of the available analysis methods

Camera A gene set analysis algorithm similar to the classical GSEA algorithm as implemented in the limma package.

- i Use interactors
- i Include disease pathways
- i Max. missing values
- i Discrete normalisation function
- i Continuous normalisation function

Continue

ssGSEA The ssGSEA approach to derive pathway expression values for every sample. Note: The Reactome visualization is only available for up to 15 samples.

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- Use interactors
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- Discrete normalisation function
- Continuous normalisation function

Hover over the information icon for more information

Continue

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Step 1: Select one of the available analysis methods

Camera A gene set analysis algorithm similar to the classical GSEA algorithm as implemented in the limma package.

Use interactors

Include disease pathways

...ing values 0.5

...ormalisation function TMM

Continuous normalisation function none

Reset

Disease pathways in Reactome may lead to a skewed analysis result. Note: Excluding disease pathways currently prevents the visualization of results in the Reactome pathway browser.

Continue

ssGSEA	The ssGSEA approach to derive pathway expression values for every sample. Note: The Reactome visualization is only available for up to 15 samples.
---------------	--

Step 1: Select one of the available analysis methods

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Click the "Continue" to go to the next step

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

New Dataset

1 Select a dataset

Local Dataset

RNA-seq (raw counts)

Raw RNA-seq based read counts per gene (recommended).

RNA-seq (normalized)

log₂ transformed, normalized RNA-seq based read counts per gene (f.e. RPKM, TPM)

Proteomics (intensity)

Intensity-based quantitative proteomics data (for example, iTRAQ/TMT or intensity-based label-free quantitation). Values must be log₂ transformed.

Proteomics (spectral counts)

Raw spectral-counts of label-free proteomics experiments

Microarray (normalized)

Normalized and log₂ transformed microarray-based gene expression values.

Example Dataset

Melanoma RNA-seq example

RNA-seq analysis of melanoma associated B cells.

Melanoma proteomics example

Quantitative (TMT-labelled) proteomics analysis of melanoma associated B cells.

Public Dataset

Search

Search across Expression Atlas and GREIN dataset

species

Homo sapiens

keywords

Expression Atlas

EBI's Expression Atlas resource for consistently reprocessed 'omics data.

Single Cell Expression Atlas

EBI's Single Cell Expression Atlas resource for consistently reprocessed scRNA-seq data.

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Local Data
You can upload
your own data in
the following
section

Back

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

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Back

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Search
This option allow you to search across available datasets in Expression Atlas and GREIN

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Quantitative (TMT-labelled) proteomics analysis of melanoma associated B cells.

Example Dataset
The simplest way to perform quickly an analysis: use one of these examples

Public Dataset

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Search across Expression Atlas and GREIN dataset

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Back

Continue

Example Dataset
Click on "Melanoma RNA-seq example" to analyse this dataset

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Melanoma RNA-seq example

condition : MOCK vs. MCM

1 Select a dataset

2 Annotate your dataset

Dataset name:
Melanoma RNA-seq example

Please add the annotations for the given dataset. The minimum requirement is to specify one annotation (comparison group). For example, "Group" with values "Treatment" and "Control".

	patient.id	condition	cell.type
X195.13	P1	MOCK	TIBC
X195.14	P1	MCM	TIBC
X195.19	P2	MOCK	PBMCB
X195.20	P2	MCM	PBMCB
X197.11	P1	MOCK	PBMCB
X197.12	P1	MCM	PBMCB
X197.13	P2	MOCK	TIBC
X197.14	P2	MCM	TIBC
X197.1	P3	MOCK	TIBC
X197.2	P3	MCM	TIBC
X197.3	P3	MOCK	PBMCB
X197.4	P3	MCM	PBMCB
X197.5	P4	MOCK	TIBC
X197.6	P4	MCM	TIBC
X197.7	P4	MOCK	PBMCB
X197.8	P4	MCM	PBMCB

Add column

Back

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Melanoma RNA-seq example
condition : MOCK vs. MCM

Select a dataset

2 Annotate your dataset

Name Your Dataset
You can rename your dataset here

Dataset name:
Melanoma RNA-seq example

Please add the annotations for the given dataset. The minimum requirement is to specify one annotation (comparison group). For example, "Group" with values "Treatment" and "Control".

Back

	patient.id		condition		cell.type	
X195.13	P1		MOCK		TIBC	
X195.14	P1		MCM		TIBC	
X195.19	P2		MOCK		PBMCB	
X195.20	P2		MCM		PBMCB	
X197.11	P1		MOCK		PBMCB	
X197.12	P1		MCM		PBMCB	
X197.13	P2		MOCK		TIBC	
X197.14	P2		MCM		TIBC	
X197.1	P3		MOCK		TIBC	
X197.2	P3		MCM		TIBC	
X197.3	P3		MOCK		PBMCB	
X197.4	P3		MCM		PBMCB	
X197.5	P4		MOCK		TIBC	
X197.6	P4		MCM		TIBC	
X197.7	P4		MOCK		PBMCB	
X197.8	P4		MCM		PBMCB	

Add column

Continue

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X197.3	P3		MOCK		PBMCB	
X197.4	P3		MCM		PBMCB	
X197.5	P4		MOCK		TIBC	
X197.6	P4		MCM		TIBC	
X197.7	P4		MOCK		PBMCB	
X197.8	P4		MCM		PBMCB	

Add column

Upload table

Download table

Back

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Dataset Annotation

In this step, you need to provide meta-data on the different samples in the dataset, like condition, gender, etc.

Because you are using an example, the data is already annotated for you.

Minimum requirement is to specify one annotation (comparison group). For

	patient.id	condition	cell.type
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X195.14	P1	MCM	TIBC
X195.19	P2	MOCK	PBMCB
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X197.5	P4	MOCK	TIBC
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X197.8	P4	MCM	PBMCB

Add column

Upload table Download table

Back

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

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X197.4	P3	MCM	PBMCB
X197.5	P4	MOCK	TIBC
X197.6	P4	MCM	TIBC
X197.7	P4	MOCK	PBMCB
X197.8	P4	MCM	PBMCB

Add column

Upload table

Download table

Continue
Click on the "v" button once you finished annotating the dataset

Add Dataset

Back

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Melanoma RNA-seq example
condition : MOCK vs. MCM

Select a dataset

Comparison Factor
GSA analysis requires you to choose which factor, from the metadata, you want to compare between samples

Back

Select comparison factor

condition

Set 1st group

MOCK

Set 2nd group

MCM

Select covariates

- Select all
- patient.id
- cell.type

Save Dataset

Add Dataset

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Melanoma RNA-seq example
condition : MOCK vs. MCM

- Select a dataset
- Annotate your dataset
- 3** Statistical Design

Groups
Among the different values you provided for the comparison factor, you need to choose which group of samples will be compared to which other group.

Back

Select comparison factor

condition

Set 1st group

MOCK

Set 2nd group

MCM

Select covariates

- Select all
- patient.id
- cell.type

Continue

Save Dataset

Add Dataset

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Melanoma RNA-seq example
condition : MOCK vs. MCM

- Select a dataset
- Annotate your dataset
- 3** Statistical Design

Cofactor

The other factors you provided in the annotation step can have an impact on the result. If you want to remove the influence of those factor on the comparison, select them.

Select comparison factor

condition

Set 1st group

MOCK

Set 2nd group

MCM

Select covariates

- Select all
- patient.id
- cell.type

Save Dataset

Add Dataset

Back

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Melanoma RNA-seq example

condition : MOCK vs. MCM

1 Select a dataset

2 Annotate your dataset

3 Statistical Design

Select comparison factor

condition

Select 1st group

Select covariates

Select all

patient.id

cell.type

Save Dataset
Click on the "Save" button.
All datasets must be saved to
continue further the analysis

Save Dataset

Add Dataset

Back

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Add More Datasets
You can analyse several datasets simultaneously by adding a new one and saving them

Melanoma RNA-seq example
condition : MOCK vs. MCM

Back

Add Dataset

Continue

Step 2: Add and annotate your datasets

Continue
Click on the "Continue" button once the selection of datasets is finished

Back

Melanoma RNA-seq example
condition : MOCK vs. MCM

Add Dataset

Continue

Step 3: Analysis Options

Options

You can choose what type of output you want from your analysis using these options, and be warned by mail when the analysis is over by providing it below

- Create REACTOME visualizations
- Create reports
- E-Mail

Disclaimer: We use your email address to send you a message when your Gene Set Analysis request is completed, and your results are available to download. After this analysis is finished, we do not store your email address. Furthermore, we do not share your email addresses with any third parties and we do not subscribe your email address to any Reactome mailing list.

Back

Continue

Step 3: Analysis Options

Continue
Click on the "Continue" button once the selection of datasets is finished

Back

- Create REACTOME visualizations
- Create reports
- E-Mail

Disclaimer: We use your email address to send you a message when your Gene Set Analysis request is completed, and your results are available to download. After this analysis is finished, we do not store your email address. Furthermore, we do not share your email addresses with any third parties and we do not subscribe your email address to any Reactome mailing list.

Waiting for Results
The only thing left to do is wait for your results to be ready!

Step 4: Analysis

Analysis

Analysis loading: 5%

Converting dataset Melanoma RNA-seq example...

Back

Progress Bar
Your analysis progress will show here

Step 4: Analysis

Analysis

Congratulations, your analysis has finished!

 Results

 Start a new analysis

Back

Step 4: Analysis

Analysis

Congratulations, your analysis has finished!

 Results

 Start a new analysis

Back

View Your Results

Click on "Results" button to go to the Pathway Browser

ReactomeGSA Tutorial 01

Analyse Gene Expression using ReactomeGSA

You have learned how to:

- Navigate to ReactomeGSA
- Run your first analysis

Please reach out if you need any assistance by emailing our HelpDesk:
help@reactome.org

ReactomeGSA Analysis Algorithms

In this first screen, you need to select the algorithm to use for the differential pathway analysis. At the time of writing, ReactomeGSA offers three algorithms. PADOG and Camera perform a differential expression analysis between two groups of samples. ssGSEA is a so-called gene set variation approach that returns pathway-level quantitative data for each sample.

The detailed parameters for each algorithm can be adapted by clicking the blue icon on the left of the algorithm's box.

Adding datasets

After clicking "Next", you are presented with the now empty list of datasets. Click the "+ Add dataset" button to add a new dataset.

First, you have to select the type of dataset you want to load.

To upload your own data, select one of the options under "Select a file from a local folder". The file must be a tab-delimited text file (CSV or TSV file) where the first column contains the gene or protein identifiers and all subsequent columns the respective samples. The first row contains the sample names and all subsequent rows the genes / proteins.

To test the tool, it is possible to quickly load example data. Currently, ReactomeGSA provides three example datasets, two (matched) datasets on melanoma associated B cells (proteomics and transcriptomics measurements) and one scRNA-seq dataset on B cells.

Finally, it is possible to directly load datasets from ExpressionAtlas. To do so, first navigate to ExpressionAtlas (in a separate tab or window) at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gxa>. Once you have identified a dataset of interest, you can get the dataset's id by opening the dataset and copying the portion after "www.ebi.ac.uk/" and before the next "/".

For example, if you opened <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gxa/experiments/E-MTAB-6592/Results> the identifier of this dataset would be "E-MTAB-6592".

For single-cell experiments you additionally have to define the parameter "k" in order to define which clusters should be used. The effect of "k" on the results can be visualised on the first page of the respective single cell experiment in ExpressionAtlas (see <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gxa/sc/experiments/E-MTAB-7008/results/>). In this case, the dataset identifier would be "E-MTAB-7008" and a possible value for "k" would be 10.

Annotating experimental metadata

Once a dataset is added, you need to annotate the experimental metadata. This is necessary in order to define the groups for the differential expression analysis in the next step.

You can adapt the dataset's name in the "Dataset name" box at the top. This name will be used for all results. To increase the readability, we suggest to use as short names as possible.

In case you load data from ExpressionAtlas or choose one of the example datasets (as shown in the screenshot) the sample annotation table will already be pre-filled with certain metadata. In case you uploaded your own dataset, the table will only show the orange sample labels on the left.

To add an annotation, click the “plus” symbol on the right. This will add a new empty column to the table. First, add a heading to define the name of the property (for example, “treatment”). Next, add the values for every sample that you want to include in your comparisons. Samples without any values will simply be ignored.

Defining the experimental design

In the final step of adding a dataset, you have to define which groups to compare. The “comparison factor” drop-down menu contains all parameters that were annotated in the sample table before (if they contain at least two different values). “1st group” and “2nd group” define which groups of samples to compare against each other.

Depending on which “comparison factor” you select, the available values for the “1st group” and “2nd group” will change automatically.

Additionally, some gene set analysis methods allow you to define so-called “covariates”. These are parameters that might cause a bias in your result (ie. the sequencing facility used) that you would like to correct for. Simply select the relevant ones for your experiment.

Once you click “Continue” you will be returned to the list of datasets where you will now see your annotated dataset in the list. If you want, you can add any number of datasets to a single request.

Starting the analysis

“Create REACTOME visualizations” is always selected. If it is de-selected, the result cannot be visualised in Reactome’s pathway browser. This option is generally only relevant to users of the [ReactomeGSA R package](#).

If you select “Create reports” ReactomeGSA will automatically create a Microsoft Excel and PDF report of your results. Additionally, it will create a short R script that allows you to load your data directly into an R session.

In case you provide your email address, you are automatically notified as soon as the analysis is complete. The mail will contain direct links to the generated reports (if you chose to create them) and a link to the visualisation in the PathwayBrowser.

Launch the analysis by clicking the “GO” button.

If you provided an email address, you can also close your browser. The analysis will still continue on our servers and you will be notified as soon as it is done. Some analysis with many

large datasets (for example comparing five TCGA datasets in a single analysis) may require up to an hour to complete.

Citing ReactomeGSA

If you use ReactomeGSA in your research, please cite the following publication:

ReactomeGSA - Efficient Multi-Omics Comparative Pathway Analysis

Johannes Griss, Guilherme Viteri, Konstantinos Sidiropoulos, Vy Nguyen, Antonio Fabregat, Henning Hermjakob

Mol Cell Proteomics. 2020 Dec; 19(12): 2115–2124; [Link](#)

Diseases

Reactome can annotate and display pathways associated with disease. Reactome disease annotations include cancer, metabolic and immune disease as well as infectious diseases, among others. Where possible, Reactome disease pathways also include the interaction of relevant therapeutic drugs. (Disease pathways are contained in a separate top-level Chapter in the hierarchy, and are designated with a red “+” symbol to the left of the pathway name.)

Pathway Diagrams:

Disease events or processes are shown in the context of the normal pathway diagram to provide context to the disease event.

Disease events have red connecting lines; abnormal molecules involved in these processes are outlined in red.

For infection processes, events involved in the life cycle of the infecting agent and host interactions with the infecting agent have red connecting lines. Molecules derived from the infecting agent are outlined in red, while those derived from the host are outlined as normal in black.

Disease events may be loss-of-function or gain-of-function compared to the normal process.

For loss-of-function events (where a protein has lost all or most of its functional activity) the disease reaction is automatically overlaid on top of the corresponding normal reaction. The loss-of-function disease entity is outlined with a dashed red line, and products that are no longer made are greyed out with a superimposed red cross. These loss-of-function events represent “stop points” in the pathway.

For gain-of-function events (where a protein has acquired a novel function not performed by the wild-type protein), disease events are represented alongside the normal events.

When a gain-of-function mutant performs a normal function (either a higher rate or efficiency, or after being activated in a novel manner, for instance), these disease events are overlaid on the corresponding normal event in the pathway diagram.

Infectious disease events (which don't occur in the absence of the infectious agent and therefore have no normal counterpart) have their own diagrams.

Drug annotations:

Where applicable, the effect of drugs on disease pathways is annotated.

Details panel:

The details panel for a disease pathway/event has a number of extra panels in addition to those displayed in a normal pathway/event.

Disease tag:

Disease events and entities are tagged with a disease term, taken from the [Disease Ontology](#) and displayed in the “Disease” panel.

Individual proteins are labeled with all the relevant disease terms, while sets of disease entities are tagged with the most specific term that represents all of the set members.

Where possible, disease proteins are linked to [OMIM](#) (Online Inheritance in Man),

GFPT1 mutants [cytosol] Species: Homo sapiens

Members

- GFPT1 D348Y [cytosol]**
 - Species: Homo sapiens
 - Synonyms: GFPT1 D348Y, Glucosamine-fructose-6-phosphate aminotransferase (isomerizing) 1
 - Coordinates in the Reference Sequence: 2 .. 699
 - Reference Entity: UniProt:Q06210 GFPT1
 - Post-translational modification: L-aspartic acid 348 replaced with L-tyrosine
 - External cross-references:
 - OMIM >> [610542]
 - OMIM >> [138292]
 - UniProt >> [Q06210_GFPT1]

and cancer variants are linked to [COSMIC](#) (Catalogue of Somatic Mutations in Cancer).

AKT1 E17K [cytosol] Species: Homo sapiens

Stable Identifier
R-HSA-2219526.1

External identifiers

- COSMIC [33765](#)
- COSMIC [34142](#)
- UniProt [P31749_AKT1](#)

Functional status:

As described above, disease events are tagged as either gain- or loss-of-function, and this is displayed in the “Functional Status” panel.

AKT1 E17K mutant binds PIP2 Species: Homo sapiens

Functional status

gain of function of AKT1 E17K [cytosol]

Physical entity: AKT1 E17K [cytosol]

Functional Status: gain of function via non conservative missense variant

Structural Variant: non_conservative_missense_variant

Functional status type: gain_of_function

Normal Pathway/Reaction:

Where applicable, the corresponding normal pathway or reaction is identified in the details panel of the disease event.

AKT1 E17K mutant binds PIP2 Species: Homo sapiens

Normal reaction

PIP3 recruits AKT to the membrane [Homo sapiens]

Disease entities:

Disease entities are annotated in molecular detail. Changes to protein sequence that arise as a result of variation in DNA sequence in disease are displayed in the details panel when a disease

entity is highlighted in the diagram. Missense, nonsense, frameshift, deletion and fusion mutations are all annotated. See “More info”, below, for details of these annotations.

Primary references describing the identification of the mutants proteins are annotated, but this information is not currently displayed on the website. Note also that on the website, these genetic modifications are displayed in the same panel as post-translational modifications such as phosphorylations, and are therefore (mis)labeled as ‘Post-translational modifications’.

Missense mutation:

AKT1 E17K [cytosol] Species: Homo sapiens

Post-translational modification

L-glutamic acid 17 replaced with L-lysine

Reference Entity:

UniProt:P31749 AKT1

Deletion mutation:

CFTR mutants [plasma membrane] Species: Homo sapiens

CFTR F508del [plasma membrane]

Species: Homo sapiens

Synonyms: CFTR F508del, Cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator, CFTR_HUMAN

Coordinates in the Reference Sequence: 1 .. 1480

Reference Entity:

UniProt:P13569 CFTR

Post-translational modification:

Deletion of residues 508 to 508

Drugs:

Drugs are cross-referenced to [ChEBI](#) and to [IUPHAR](#) where possible and applicable, and this information is displayed in the details panel when a drug is highlighted in the diagram.

Get started:

Example 1 - drug-target interaction in disease:

The cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) is a low conductance chloride-selective channel that mediates the transport of chloride ions in human airway epithelial cells. Chloride ions play a key role in maintaining homeostasis of epithelial secretions in the lungs. Defects in CFTR can cause cystic fibrosis (CF), resulting in an ionic imbalance that impairs clearance of secretions, not only in the lung, but also in the pancreas, gastrointestinal tract and liver. More than 1500 mutations in the CFTR gene have been identified.

Gain-of-function events involving CFTR F508del:

Deletion of phenylalanine 508 in CFTR is the most prevalent mutation causing cystic fibrosis. F508 deletion causes destabilization and subsequent targeting for co-translational degradation by the ER-associated degradation machinery (ERAD). F508del is ubiquitinated by ERAD-

associated E3 ligases including RNF5 and RNF185, targeting it for VCP-mediated retrotranslocation and 26S proteasomal degradation. These events are novel for the mutant protein and are represented in the disease diagram “ABC transporter disorders”.

Loss-of-function events for CFTR mutants:

Some loss-of-function CFTR mutants are properly transported to the plasma membrane but are unable to transport chloride ions to the extracellular space. These are represented as a loss-of-function event in an overlay of the corresponding WT reaction, and displayed in the “ABC transporter disorders” disease diagram.

Drug interactions in Cystic Fibrosis:

CF patients with a particular mutation, G551D, have shown lung function improvements when given the drug Ivacaftor. Reactions showing ivacaftor binding the mutant protein (top right, above) and the following reaction (centre) showing channel functionality restored are displayed in the disease diagram.

Example 2 - diseases caused by accumulation of substrate over time:

Special case in Reactome where the reaction describing a particular substrate's metabolism occurs in normal physiology but over time, accumulation of the substrate leads to toxic consequences which can lead to disease. Examples are neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and retinal macular degeneration.

The bisretinoid A2E (di-retinoid-pyridinium-ethanolamine) is a major component of lipofuscin, a yellow-brown pigment grain composed mainly of lipids but also sugars and certain metals whose accumulation is associated with degenerative diseases. In the eye, A2E is the end-product of the condensation of 2 molecules of all-trans-retinal and phosphatidylethanolamine in photoreceptor outer disc membranes. Once formed, A2E is phagocytosed, together with outer segments, to retinal pigment epithelial (RPE) cells where it accumulates. There is no evidence as yet to indicate that A2E can be catabolised.

The relationship between lipofuscin accumulation and retinal degeneration is illustrated by Stargardt disease type 1. Because the reactions can be considered "normal" (they occur as part of the normal metabolism of retinoids) as well as disease-causing, they appear in the normal pathway diagram (Visual phototransduction) and coloured red.

To display in the disease view of the diagram, these reactions are added as components of the disease pathway "Diseases associated with visual transduction". These reactions will now display in both normal and disease diagrams.

Getting Started

Exercises:

1. Search for the pathway FGFR1 mutant receptor activation and open it. What disease(s) is/are associated with this pathway? (*Hint: look at the Description tab in the Details section*).
2. Search for the reaction Defective MMADHC does not bind MMACHC;B12r. What type of defect has caused this loss of function? (*Hint: look at the Functional Status category for the reaction*).
3. How many mutations of MMADHC are represented?

More info:

Annotating genetic alteration of protein sequence for disease pathways:

The following image shows the portion of the Reactome data model describing the relationship between possible modifications to protein sequence. The subclass "GeneticallyModifiedResidue" is used for the annotation of disease entities, while "TranslationalModification" is used to annotate the consequence of processes such as phosphorylation, acylation, cross-linking and other similar non-genetic events. TranslationalModifications will not be described further here.

- ▼ **C** AbstractModifiedResidue [9267]
 - ▼ **C** GeneticallyModifiedResidue [1634]
 - ▼ **C** FragmentModification [225]
 - C** FragmentDeletionModification [56]
 - C** FragmentInsertionModification [66]
 - C** FragmentReplacedModification [103]
 - C** ReplacedResidue [1409]
 - ▼ **C** TranslationalModification [7633]
 - ▼ **C** CrosslinkedResidue [763]
 - C** InterChainCrosslinkedResidue [719]
 - C** IntraChainCrosslinkedResidue [44]
 - C** GroupModifiedResidue [1430]
 - C** ModifiedResidue [5440]

The ReplacedResidue class is used for amino-acid substitutions. This class is also used for “simple” nonsense mutations that change a coding amino acid for a stop codon.

The FragmentModification class describes more extensive changes to the coding sequence through insertions and deletions in the gene, and includes three subclasses:

- FragmentDeletionModification is used for in-frame deletions of amino-acids
- FragmentInsertionModification is used for in-frame insertions of amino-acids, including genomic events that result in fusion proteins
- FragmentReplacedModification is used for frameshifts.

Examples of each annotation type are further described below.

Simple missense mutation: HHAT G287V

Hedgehog (Hh) is a secreted morphogen that regulates a number of developmental processes in vertebrates, including limb development and neural tube patterning, among others. Maturation of Hh ligand includes a number of proteolytic processing and lipid modification steps. These modifications are required for normal transit of the ligand to the surface of the secreting cell and mutations that affect these processes are associated with decreased Hh ligand secretion, abrogated Hh signaling and disease.

HHAT is an O-acyltransferase that palmitoylates the N-terminal fragment of Hh. A G287V loss-of-function mutation in HHAT was identified in a rare case of Syndromic 46 XY Disorder of Sex Development, which results in testis dysgenesis. This mutant is not able to palmitoylate the Hh ligand. Details of the amino-acid substitution are displayed in the details panel when the entity is highlighted in the diagram:

Simple nonsense mutation:

The disorder "Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, musculocontractural type 1" (EDSMC1) is caused by loss-of-function mutations in the carbohydrate sulfotransferase 14 (CHST14) gene. A nonsense mutation causing this disorder is a 205A-T transversion in the CHST14 gene, resulting in a lys69-to-ter (K69*) substitution. This is represented in the details panel as "L-lysine 69 replaced with unknown".

FragmentDeletionModification:

This class is used for in-frame deletions of amino-acids leading to internally truncated proteins. These variants are named "core protein name" [first amino acid of deletion_last amino acid of deletion]del, as shown below for PIK3R1 Y463_L466del, which has a deletion of residues Y463 to L466, inclusive:

FragmentInsertionModification

This class is used for in-frame insertions of amino-acids and for fusion proteins.

In-frame insertions:

These variants are named "core protein name" [aa prior to insertion_aa following insertion]ins[inserted aa's]. The amino-acid string of the inserted residues is added manually to the mutant protein name, as shown below for EGFR V738_K739insKIPVAI. This represents a variant where the amino acids 739-744 (KIPVAI) from EGFR are inserted at aa 739 of EGFR, and is thus a duplication of these residues:

Species: Homo sapiens

Synonyms: EGFR V738_K739insKIPVAI, Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor V738_K739insKIPVAI, EGFR Val738_Lys739insLysileProValAlaIle

Coordinates in the Reference Sequence: 25 .. 1210

Reference Entity:

UniProt:P00533 EGFR

Post-translational modification:

Insertion of residues 739 to 744 at 739 from UniProt:P00533 EGFR

Start position in Reference Sequence	739
End position in Reference Sequence	744
Name	Insertion of residues 739 to 744 at 739 from UniProt:P00533 EGFR
Coordinate	739

Reference Entity:

UniProt:P00533 EGFR

External cross-references

Fusion proteins:

The FragmentInsertionModification class is also used to annotate proteins that arise as the result of genomic changes that bring two genes together to result in a fusion protein, as in the ZMYM2-FGFR1 fusion described below. This fusion puts the ZMYM2 dimerization region (1-914) together with the kinase domain of the FGFR1 receptor (residues 429-822) and results in constitutive activation of the kinase domain by virtue of ligand-independent dimerization (for reference, the full length aa sequence of these two proteins are 1-1377 and 1-822 for ZMYM2 and FGFR1, respectively).

By convention, the N-terminal most partner of the fusion is set as the reference protein for the variant protein while the C-terminal fusion partner sequence is captured in the FragmentInsertionModification record, as in the example below for the ZMYM2-FGFR1 fusion:

The screenshot displays a bioinformatics database interface. At the top, a pathway diagram shows the following components and interactions:

- cytosolic FGFR1 fusion mutants** (blue box) leads to **cytosolic FGFR1 fusion mutant dimers** (red box) via a red arrow with a '2' in a yellow box.
- Tyrosine kinase inhibitors of FGFR1 fusion mutants** (blue box) leads to **cytosolic FGFR1 fusion mutant dimers** (red box) via a red arrow with a '2' in a yellow box.
- cytosolic FGFR1 fusion mutant dimers** (red box) leads to **FGFR1 fusion mutant dimers:TKIs** (red box) via a red arrow with a '2' in a yellow box.

Below the diagram, the interface shows a search bar with the query **cytosolic FGFR1 fusion mutants [cytosol]** and **Species: Homo sapiens**. The main entry details are as follows:

- Stable Identifier:** [R-HSA-1839029.2](#)
- Cellular compartment:** cytosol
- Members:**
 - ZMYM2-FGFR1 fusion [cytosol]**
 - Species:** Homo sapiens
 - Synonyms:** ZMYM2-FGFR1 fusion, ZMYM2(1-913)-FGFR1(429-822) fusion, t(8;13) ZMYM2-FGFR1 fusion, ZNF198-FGFR1 fusion, ZNF198(1-913)-FGFR1(429-822) fusion, t(8;13) ZNF198-FGFR1 fusion, FIM-FGFR1 fusion, RAMP-FGFR1 fusion
 - Coordinates in the Reference Sequence:** 1 .. 913
 - Reference Entity:** UniProt:Q9UBW7 ZMYM2
 - Post-translational modification:** Insertion of residues 429 to 822 at 914 from UniProt:P11362 FGFR1
 - External cross-references:** (none listed)

Post-translational modifications to either partner in the fusion protein are numbered according to each respective WT reference gene product and do not reflect the aa position in the fusion. For instance, if in the context of the fusion protein, the FGFR1 partner is phosphorylated at (WT FGFR1 position) Y766, the fusion EWAS would be ZMYM2-pY766-FGFR1, despite the fact that in linear sequence the phosphorylation occurs at residue 1250 of the fusion (913+(766-429)).

FragmentReplacedModification

This class is used to annotate frameshift mutations that alter the amino-acid sequence of the protein as in the case of EXT1, described below.

The disorder “Hereditary multiple exostoses 1” (EXT1) is caused by loss-of-function mutations in Exostosin 1 (EXT1). One such mutation is a 1-bp deletion at nucleotide 1469 in the EXT1 gene, resulting in a frameshift mutation with a premature stop codon nine amino acids downstream. Variants of this type are named “core protein name” [aa prior to insertion_fs*(number of aa to the first stop codon)]. The novel amino acids that occur as a result of the frameshift are identified in the mutant protein record, as shown below for EXT1 L490Rfs*9:

Description | **Molecules** | **Structures** | **Expression** | **Analysis** | **Downloads**

EXT1 mutants [Golgi membrane] Species: Homo sapiens

Stable Identifier
[R-HSA-3730938.1](#)

Cellular compartment
 Golgi membrane

Members

- EXT1 L490Rfs*9 [Golgi membrane]**
 - Species: Homo sapiens
 - Synonyms: EXT1 L490Rfs*9, Exostosin-1, EXT1_HUMAN
 - Coordinates in the Reference Sequence: 1 ... 497
 - Reference Entity:
 - UniProt:Q16394 EXT1
 - Post-translational modification:
 - Replacement of residues 490 to 497 by RSLSPSQC
 - External cross-references

For cancer-related processes, it is useful to view the altered disease events alongside their normal counterparts in the same diagram. The user can then see where normal processes diverge into ones that are implicated in cancer.

For metabolic processes, proteins that have lost all or most of their functional activity towards a substrate causes the majority of defects. The diagram displays these disease reactions as 'stop points' in the pathway. Defective enzyme catalysts are outlined by a red dashed line; products that are no longer made are shown greyed-out with a superimposed red cross.

Cytomics

Introduction

Human bodies are built of >30 trillion cells specialized to fulfill diverse roles within our tissues, organs, and organ systems. All these cells originate from a single cell, a zygote formed at conception. From zygote to fetus, and throughout childhood, adolescence, and adulthood, cells divide and commit to different fates in order for the organism to develop, sustain and regenerate. The series of steps that lead from an undifferentiated progenitor cell, such as a stem cell, to one of a number of possible specialized descendants constitutes a cell lineage path. Recent technological advances have allowed researchers to collect high-throughput omics data from single cells of multicellular organisms and use it to track and manipulate cell fates ([Burgess 2018; Saelens et al. 2019](#)). This opens the door to the possibility of deciphering cell lineage paths at single-cell resolution, a critical requirement for the advancement of regenerative medicine and cancer medicine.

Researchers who conduct experiments that involve cell lineage tracing through the study of genomic, epigenomic, transcriptomic, and proteomic features of single cells currently expend significant effort extracting information from published sources to create short-lived, limited-scope local annotations of biological markers that are needed to interpret and analyze their high-throughput experimental data. This creates the urgent need for an open source, comprehensive, continuously maintained reference repository of cell lineage paths framed on the pre-existing knowledge of tissue morphogenesis, as well as a cell type-specific pathway resource, which can serve as a framework for interpretation and integration of the latest experimental findings.

Cytomics Reactome aims to become an integrative systems biology resource of cell lineage paths and a toolset for the analysis of single-cell omics data. The Reactome web application and pathway visualization tools ([Croft et al. 2011](#)) have been extended to enable Cytomics Reactome visual display and search functions (Milacic et al. 2024) on the live website.

Database schema features to support Cytomics

The Reactome data model provides a robust framework for the annotation of biological entities and events ([Joshi-Tope et al. 2005](#)). The basic unit of the Reactome data model is a Reaction, an event that converts input to output physical entities. The participants in reactions are PhysicalEntities, which can be simple or complex molecules or molecular complexes. These PhysicalEntities can also act as reaction catalysts and regulators. Reactions are grouped into causal chains to form Pathways ([Joshi-Tope et al. 2005](#)).

The Reactome data schema was expanded as described below to accommodate new classes needed for Cytomics Reactome annotations.

- Cell: A subclass of PhysicalEntity, represents a type of cell in a particular state of development/differentiation (Figure 1A).
 - A Cell instance has CellType, TissueLayer, Tissue, and Organ as single-valued attributes which are populated using terms from public open source databases, the Cell Ontology ([Sarntivijai et al. 2014](#); [Osumi-Sutherland 2017](#)) and UBERON ([Haendel et al. 2014](#)), and cross-reference these databases.
 - Cell instances also have multi-valued ProteinMarker and RNAMarker attributes, which are specific to the cell type and/or the cell state or are differentially upregulated in the Cell. (Figure 1B). The markers (protein or RNA) are manually curated; each marker instance is associated with one or more literature references for evidence, including, if applicable, citations of CellMarker (Hu et al. 2022) and PanglaoDB databases (Franzén et al. 2019) (Figure 1B)

Figure 1. Cell Physical Entity class A and new attributes B

- Cell Development Step and Cell Lineage Path are two Event subclasses (Figure 2A), that describe developmental/differentiation relationships among Cells:
 - A Cell Development Step is a ReactionLikeEvent that contains Cell instances as its inputs and outputs. The input attribute represents the cell of origin, and the output attribute represents the destination cell type. Additional Cell Development Step attributes include regulators (molecules promoting or inhibiting the step) and required input components (input cell proteins required for the action of regulators) (Figure 2B).

- A Cell Lineage Path, organizationally similar to the preexisting Pathway subclass, is composed of other Cell Lineage Path instances or Cell Development Steps as subevents that are connected through shared input/output Cells (Figure 2C).
- Both Cell Development Step and Cell Lineage Path are associated with a relevant Gene Ontology (GO) biological process term ([The Gene Ontology Consortium 2019](#)) and with a “tissue” term from UBERON ([Haendel et al. 2014](#)).

Figure 2. Cell Development Step and Cell Lineage Path schema (A) and attributes (B,C).

The Cytomics content is searchable on the Reactome website. Running a search from the homepage search bar may list hits within various categories including pathway, reaction, complex, and cell. Clicking on an item in the search results list will redirect to a Details page, which displays more information about the specific record.

- For example, a details page for Cell (Figure 3A) includes information on location in the pathway hierarchy, cell type, and histological description of the given cell with ontology terms, a list of protein and RNA markers, and corresponding literature references for each marker. A scroll bar appears when there are more than 5 markers in the same category. The page also lists event(s) (i.e., Cell Development Step), in which the Cell participates as an input/output.
 - Clicking on marker or Cell Development Step, will redirect to the details page of the marker or event respectively.
 - Clicking on the Cell in the expanded hierarchical view of the Developmental Biology pathway (Figure 3B) in the details page, will redirect to the Pathway

Browser view highlighting the Cell Lineage Path in the hierarchy panel and showing the selected Cell in the pathway diagram.

keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer

Stable Identifier	R-HSA-9725559
Type	Cell
Species	Homo sapiens
Synonyms	keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis stratum basale

Locations in the PathwayBrowser

Developmental Biology (Homo sapiens) Expand All

Cytology

Organ	skin of body (UBERON:0002097)
Tissue	skin epidermis (UBERON:0001003)
Tissue Layer	stratum basale of epidermis (UBERON:0002025)
Cell Type	stem cell of epidermis (CL:1000428)

Markers

Protein	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CSPG4 [plasma membrane] (Homo sapiens) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Role of melanoma chondroitin sulphate proteoglycan in patterning stem cells in human interfollicular epidermis. <i>Development</i> 130, 6049-6059. Leigh, I., Broad, S., Legg, J., Watt, FM., Jensen, UB. LRIG1 [plasma membrane] (Homo sapiens) DLL1 [plasma membrane] (Homo sapiens) ITGA6(24-1130) [plasma membrane] (Homo sapiens)
RNA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LRIG1 mRNA [cytosol] (Homo sapiens) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single-cell expression profiling of human epidermal stem and transit-amplifying cells: Lrig1 is a regulator of stem cell quiescence. <i>Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A</i> 108, 1000-1005. Watt, FM., Jensen, KB. COL17A1 mRNA [cytosol] (Homo sapiens) CSPG4 mRNA [cytosol] (Homo sapiens)

Participates

as an input of Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)

Figure 3. Details page for Cell (A)

keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer

Stable Identifier	R-HSA-9725559
Type	Cell
Species	Homo sapiens
Synonyms	keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis stratum basale

Locations in the PathwayBrowser

Developmental Biology (Homo sapiens)

- Developmental Cell Lineages (Homo sapiens)
 - Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin (Homo sapiens)
 - Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)
 - keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer (Homo sapiens)

Figure 3. Expanded view of the Cell location in the Pathway Browser (B)

- See the details pages for marker instance (Figure 4), Cell Development Step (Figure 5), Cell Lineage Path (Figure 6) below.
 - The content of individual events can be exported from the event's details pages (Figure 5, 6) as SBML, PDF, SVG, PNG, PPTX, SBGN files.

● CSPG4 [plasma membrane]

Stable Identifier	R-HSA-9734933
Type	Protein [EntityWithAccessionedSequence]
Species	Homo sapiens
Compartment	plasma membrane
Synonyms	Chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4, CSPG4_HUMAN

Locations in the PathwayBrowser

- Developmental Biology (Homo sapiens)
 - Developmental Cell Lineages (Homo sapiens)
 - Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin (Homo sapiens)
 - Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)**
 - keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer (Homo sapiens)
 - **CSPG4 [plasma membrane] (Homo sapiens)**

External Reference Information

External Reference	UniProt:Q6UVK1 CSPG4
Gene Names	CSPG4, MCSP
Chain	signal peptide:1-29, chain:30-2322
Reference Genes	ENSEMBL:ENSG00000173546 C...

Participates

as a protein marker of [keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer \(Homo sapiens\)](#)

Other forms of this molecule

D2,4,4(S)3-CSPG4 [lysosomal lumen]	D2,4(S)2-CSPG4 [lysosomal lumen]
D4S-CSPG4 [lysosomal lumen]	CSPG4 [lysosomal lumen]
CSE-CSPG4 [lysosomal lumen]	C6S-CSPG4 [lysosomal lumen]
C4S-CSPG4 [lysosomal lumen]	CSE-CSPG4 [extracellular region]
C6S-CSPG4 [extracellular region]	C4S-CSPG4 [extracellular region]
CSE-CSPG4 [Golgi lumen]	C6S-CSPG4 [Golgi lumen]

Figure 4. Details page for Marker instance

➤ Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis

Stable Identifier | R-HSA-9725621
 Type | Reaction (transition)
 Species | Homo sapiens
 Compartment | extracellular region
 Tissue | skin epidermis (UBERON:0001003)
 ReviewStatus | 5/5

Locations in the PathwayBrowser

- Developmental Biology (Homo sapiens)
 - Developmental Cell Lineages (Homo sapiens)
 - Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin (Homo sapiens)
 - Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)**

General

[SBML](#) | [BioPAX](#) | [PDF](#)

[SVG](#) | [PNG](#) | [PPTX](#) | [SBGN](#)

Click the image above or [here](#) to open this reaction in the Pathway Browser

The layout of this reaction may differ from that in the pathway view due to the constraints in pathway layout

The keratinocyte stem cells differentiate into keratinocytes of basal layer epidermis, also known as transit amplifying cells (TA cells), in a process stimulated by the epidermal growth factor (EGF) (Jansen and Watt 2006). The keratinocyte stem cell must express the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) on its surface in order to be responsive to the EGF ligand (Jansen and Watt 2006). Still, responsiveness of keratinocyte stem cells to EGF is reduced because of low levels of EGFR (Fortunel et al. 2003) and high levels of LRIG, a negative regulator of EGFR signaling (Jensen and Watt 2006). TGF-alpha (TGFA), another ligand of EGFR, may also stimulate proliferation of keratinocyte stem cells (reviewed in Fuchs et al. 1990).

In interfollicular epidermis, keratinocyte stem cells are found in the basal layer, where they account for about 10% of cells (Potten and Morris 1988). Protein markers of keratinocyte stem cells are summarized in the table below, titled "Table of markers of keratinocyte stem cells in interfollicular epidermis". CSPG4 is the only marker undetectable in other basal cells of the human epidermis, while others are detectable, but a gradient of marker expression exists that is thought to be consistent with the gradient of stemness (Niemann and Watt 2002). ... [Read more](#)

Literature References

PubMed ID	Title	Journal	Year
17699601	Dual Role of alpha6beta4 integrin in epidermal tumor growth: tumor-suppressive versus tumor-promoting function <i>Janssen, H, Song, JY, Kreft, M, Sonnenberg, A, Raymond, K</i>	Mol Biol Cell	2007
11798957	[Epidermal growth factor induce the epithelial stem cell island formation in the regenerated epidermis] <i>Sun, T, Fu, X, Sun, X</i>	Zhonghua Yi Xue Za Zhi	2001
22522222	Yes-associated protein (YAP) transcriptional coactivator functions in balancing growth and		2011

Participants

- Input | keratinocyte stem cell of skin epidermis basal layer (Homo sapiens)
- Output | transit-amplifying cell of epidermis basal layer (Homo sapiens)

Participates

- as an event of | Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin (Homo sapiens)

Event Information

- Go Biological Process | keratinocyte development (0003334)

This event is regulated

- Positively by | Regulator EGF [extracellular region] (Homo sapiens)

Figure 5. Details page for Cell Development Step

🔗 Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin

Stable Identifier | R-HSA-9725554
 Type | CellLineagePath
 Species | Homo sapiens
 ReviewStatus | 5/5

Locations in the PathwayBrowser Expand All

- 🔗 Developmental Biology (Homo sapiens)
 - 🔗 Developmental Cell Lineages (Homo sapiens)
 - 🔗 Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin (Homo sapiens)

General SVG | PNG | PPTX | SBN

[SBML](#) | [BioPAX](#) | [PDF](#) reactome

Click the image above or [here](#) to open this cellineagepath in the Pathway Browser

The interfollicular epidermis is the skin surface layer in between the adnexa (hair follicles, sweat glands, and sebaceous glands). Going from the dermal epidermal junction, the interfollicular epidermis strata include the basal layer (stratum basale), spinous layer (stratum spinosum), granular layer (stratum granulosum), and the cornified layer (stratum corneum). The basal layer consists of keratinocyte stem cells and transit amplifying cells. The spinous, granular, and cornified layers consist of spinous keratinocytes, granular keratinocytes, and corneocytes, respectively. Interfollicular epidermis has a high cell turnover rate. Keratinocyte stem cells self renew throughout adulthood and give rise to transit amplifying cells. Transit amplifying cells undergo several cell cycles before committing to differentiation, first into spinous layer keratinocytes, then into granular layer keratinocytes, and finally into corneocytes. Corneocytes lose their nuclei and cytoplasmic organelles, forming... [Read more](#)

Literature References

PubMed ID	Title	Journal	Year
37832539	Single-cell RNA sequencing of human epidermis identifies Lunatic fringe as a novel regulator of the stem cell compartment <i>Philippeos, C, Haniffa, M, Watt, FM, Ganier, C, Louis, B, Ali, S, Reynolds, G, Zijl, S, Negri, VA</i>	Stem Cell Reports	2023
32187560	Defining Epidermal Basal Cell States during Skin Homeostasis and Wound Healing Using Single-Cell Transcriptomics <i>Cinco, R, MacLean, AL, Dai, X, Cang, Z, Gong, Y, Gratton, E, Kessenbrock, K, Nie, Q, Vu, R, Dragan, M, Nguyen, Q, Sun, P, Jin, S, Haensel, D</i>	Cell Rep	2020

Participants

Events

- Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell in the basal layer of interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)
- Transit-amplifying cell of basal layer differentiates into keratinocyte of spinosum layer in interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)
- Keratinocyte of spinosum layer differentiates into keratinocyte of granulosum layer in interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)
- Keratinocyte of granulosum layer differentiates into corneocyte of corneum layer in interfollicular epidermis (Homo sapiens)

Participates

as an event of | 🔗 Developmental Cell Lineages (Homo sapiens)

Event Information

Go Biological Process | keratinocyte development (0003334)

Figure 6. Details page for Cell Lineage Path

Navigation of a Cell Lineage Path in the Pathway Browse

Cell Lineage Paths are available under the “Developmental Biology” pathway in the Reactome Pathway Browser, where they are grouped in the “Developmental Cell Lineages” subpathway (Figure 7).

Although the pathway diagram depicts a selection of cell types that are planned for annotation, only one type has been annotated so far and this is indicated by a selectable blue box label in the diagram.

Figure 7. Pathway browser view of “Developmental Cell Lineages” subpathway

Selecting an individual Cell Lineage Path in the pathway hierarchy will display all Cell Development Steps of the selected path in the pathway diagram (Figure 8). An individual Cell is depicted with a double-layered outer compartment representing the plasma membrane and the cytosol, along with an inner blue rectangle symbolizing the nucleus.

The Description tab in the Details panel of a selected Cell Lineage Path provides additional information about the Cell Lineage Path including name, species, assigned GO Biological Process term (if applicable), and literature reference(s) (Figure 8).

reactome 3.7 Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Event Hierarchy:

- Developmental Biology
 - Maternal to zygotic transition (MZT)
 - Transcriptional regulation of pluripotent stem cells
 - Gastrulation
 - Signaling by NODAL
 - Activation of HOX genes during differentiation
 - Nervous system development
 - LGI-ADAM interactions
 - Myogenesis
 - Cardiogenesis
 - Kidney development
 - Regulation of beta-cell development
 - Transcriptional regulation of testis differentiation
 - Keratinization
 - Transcriptional regulation of granulopoiesis
 - Developmental Cell Lineages**
 - Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis**
 - Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell of basal layer
 - Transit-amplifying cell of basal layer differentiates into keratinocyte of spinosum layer
 - Keratinocyte of spinosum layer differentiates into keratinocyte of granulosum layer
 - Keratinocyte of granulosum layer differentiates into keratinocyte
 - MITF-M-regulated melanocyte development
 - Adipogenesis
 - Digestion and absorption
 - Disease

Search for a term, e.g. pten ...

Description Molecules Structures Expression Analysis Downloads

Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis in mammalian skin Id: R-HSA-972554.1 Species: Homo sapiens Review Status: C

DOI: 10.31801/R-HSA-972554.1

Summation

The interfollicular epidermis is the skin surface layer in between the adnexa (hair follicles, sweat glands, and sebaceous glands). Going from the dermal epidermal junction, the interfollicular epidermis strata include the basal layer (stratum basale), spinous layer (stratum spinosum), granular layer (stratum granulosum), and the cornified layer (stratum corneum). The basal layer consists of keratinocyte stem cells and transit amplifying cells. The spinous, granular, and cornified layers consist of spinous keratinocytes, granular keratinocytes, and corneocytes, respectively. Interfollicular epidermis has a high cell turnover rate. Keratinocyte stem cells self renew throughout adulthood and give rise to transit amplifying cells. Transit amplifying cells undergo several cell cycles before committing to differentiation. First into spinous layer keratinocytes, then into granular layer.

Figure 8. Selecting a Cell Lineage Path from the pathway hierarchy

Clicking on an individual Cell Development Step either in the pathway hierarchy or in the pathway diagram will display relevant information for the selected event in the details panel below the diagram (Figure 9). The description tab of the details panel shows input and output, which are defined by Cell instances, regulators of the event (when applicable), GO biological process, and UBERON tissue terms. It may also display preceding event(s) connecting individual Cell Development Steps within the same Cell Lineage Path (Figure 9). Details of participating Cell instances including histological terms, specific protein and RNA markers, and corresponding marker references are accessible from the description tab of Cell Development Step upon clicking on the plus sign to the right of the input/output attributes.

reactome 3.7 Pathways for: Homo sapiens

Event Hierarchy:

- Developmental Biology
 - Maternal to zygotic transition (MZT)
 - Transcriptional regulation of pluripotent stem cells
 - Gastrulation
 - Signaling by NODAL
 - Activation of HOX genes during differentiation
 - Nervous system development
 - LGI-ADAM interactions
 - Myogenesis
 - Cardiogenesis
 - Kidney development
 - Regulation of beta-cell development
 - Transcriptional regulation of testis differentiation
 - Keratinization
 - Transcriptional regulation of granulopoiesis
 - Developmental Cell Lineages**
 - Differentiation of keratinocytes in interfollicular epidermis**
 - Keratinocyte stem cell differentiates into transit amplifying cell of basal layer
 - Transit-amplifying cell of basal layer differentiates into keratinocyte of spinosum layer
 - Keratinocyte of spinosum layer differentiates into keratinocyte of granulosum layer**
 - Keratinocyte of granulosum layer differentiates into keratinocyte
 - MITF-M-regulated melanocyte development
 - Adipogenesis
 - Digestion and absorption
 - Disease

Search for a term, e.g. pten ...

Description Molecules Structures Expression Analysis Downloads

Keratinocyte of spinosum layer differentiates into keratinocyte of granulosum layer in interfollicular epidermis Id: R-HSA-9727359.1 Species: Homo sapiens Review

Input

- keratinocyte of spinosum layer of epidermis

Output

- keratinocyte of granulosum layer of epidermis

Positively regulated by

- Positive regulation by 'Ca2+' [cytosol]

Negatively regulated by

- Negative regulation by 'p53' [nucleus]

Figure 9. Selecting a Cell Development Step

Alternatively, the Cell details can be displayed in the Details panel by selecting a “Cell” icon in the diagram of the Cell Lineage Path (Figure 10). Right-clicking or clicking the blue info icon when hovering over a “Cell” icon in the pathway diagram will open a popup list of protein and RNA markers for the selected Cell (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Selecting a Cell

Figure 11. Displaying the list of Cell markers

The Molecules tab in the Details panel (Figure 12A) displays a downloadable list of all markers for a Cell and both the markers and regulators for a Cell Development Step and a Cell Lineage Path.

The Structure tab (Figure 12B) in the details panel displays the Protein Data Bank structures of molecules listed in the Molecular tab and the Expression tab shows gene expression data from Expression Atlas.

Figure 12. Displaying Molecules Tab (A)

Figure 12. Structures tab (B)

The Analysis tab (Figure 13, 14) in the details panel displays data after running the dataset analysis. Refer to (Rothfels et al. 2023) for detailed instructions on how to use the Reactome Analysis Tool.

The results of the analysis are also visualized in the pathway diagram panel, where the “Cell” icons are colored (Figure 13, 14). The colored area in the nucleus of the individual Cell corresponds to the coverage of the cell markers in the submitted data set.

In Pathway Enrichment Analysis, olive green is applied to color the nucleus of the cells in the Cell Lineage Path that contain markers from the query list. The extent of coloration is proportional to the number of markers hit (Figure 13).

The results of gene expression analysis, including Reactome Gene Set Analysis (Reactome GSA), appear as a single vertical bar of color when zoomed out representing the average expression of the markers from the query list (Figure 14a). Zooming in on the “Cell” icon reveals bars for individual cell markers with their expression values, as shown in Figure 14b. Expression values of cell markers from the query data set can be visualized in a popup information panel of protein and RNA markers for the selected Cell (Figure 14b).

Expression values for the markers of a selected cell are displayed as blue horizontal lines within the expression scale (Figure 14C). The median cell marker expression among the cell's matching markers is shown in black. On the left, when a specific marker bar is hovered over, the currently hovered marker's expression value is displayed in red, and the expression values of other markers in the same cell are shown in yellow.

Figure 13. Overrepresentation analysis displayed within the nuclei of the cells in the Cell Lineage Path

Figure 14. Gene expression analysis results are displayed within the nuclei of the cells. The level with coloration reflects the average expression value of the cell markers (A)

Figure 14. A zoomed-in view of the expression bars of individual markers (B)

Figure 14. The expression scale (C)

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9. Saelens, Wouter, Robrecht Cannoodt, Helena Todorov, and Yvan Saeys. 2019. "A Comparison of Single-Cell Trajectory Inference Methods." *Nature Biotechnology* 37 (5): 547–54.
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12. The Gene Ontology Consortium. 2019. "The Gene Ontology Resource: 20 Years and Still GOing Strong." *Nucleic Acids Research* 47 (D1): D330–38.

Review Status of Reactome Events

Reactome events (pathways and reaction-like events) undergo internal review by a member of the Reactome editorial staff and external review by a domain expert. Events that undergo both internal and external review are assigned the highest review score of 5. When such an event is revised and the revisions result in ***structural modification** to that event, the event's review score is demoted to 3. The revised event must be internally reviewed again to attain a review score of 4 and externally reviewed to regain a score of 5. The table below summarizes the definitions of each review status.

Status-based release of Reactome content

Review Score	Definition	Release status
1	Restructured after internal review	NOT RELEASED
2	Restructured after external review	NOT RELEASED
3	Internally reviewed, awaiting external review	RELEASED
4	Restructured after external review, then internally re-reviewed	RELEASED
5	Externally reviewed	RELEASED

***What is a structural modification to an event?**

A structural update involves at least one of the following modifications after the initial internal and/or external review of the event.

- Addition, removal, or replacement of a CatalystActivity, Regulator, Input, Output of a reaction-like event
- Addition, removal, or replacement of an Event of a pathway

Any one or more of these changes to an event demotes its review status and requires additional review as described in the table above in order to restore its review status.

*A Reactome event that has been internally reviewed and is still awaiting an external review after six months is publically released with a score of 3. Once reviewed, it is assigned the maximum score of 5. If an event with a score of 3 is ***structurally modified**, its score is demoted to 1 and must be internally reviewed to regain its original score of 3. If an event with a score of 4 is structurally modified, it is demoted to a score of 2 and must be internally reviewed to recover its score of 4 and externally reviewed to raise its score to 5. Reactome does not include events with a score lower than 3 on the public website.*

Where can I see the review status of a Reactome event?

The review status of an event can be seen in the upper right corner of the Pathway Browser details panel:

The screenshot shows the Reactome Pathway Browser interface. The main panel displays a pathway diagram for 'Formation of definitive endoderm' (Id: R-HSA-9823730.1). The details panel below the diagram shows the following information:

- DOI: 10.3180/R-HSA-9823730.1
- Summation: The endoderm in mammalian embryos originates from two different populations of cells: the visceral endoderm, which is present before gastrulation as the hypoblast underlying the epiblast, and the definitive endoderm, which is derived from epiblast cells ingressing through the anterior-most region of the primitive streak. After ingression, the cells of the definitive endoderm then intercalate with the cells of the visceral endoderm to form the embryonic endoderm that will give rise to the gut and visceral organs associated with the gut such as the pancreas and liver (reviewed in Lewis and Tam 2006, Nowotschin et al. 2019). In the discoid human gastrula (differs from the rodent gastrula which acquires a cup shape), the endoderm initially is organized in a flat epithelial sheet that later rolls into a tube to form the gut. Due to ethical considerations, research on gastrulation is undertaken primarily in non-human primate species (for example Bergmann et al. 2022) and stem cells (D'Amour et al. 2005, reviewed in Salehin et al. 2022), which have provided insight into germ layer formation in human

A red arrow points to the 'Review Status: 5/5' indicator in the top right corner of the details panel.

and also on the content details page reached via the search:

The screenshot shows the Reactome content details page for 'Ribavirin ADME' (R-HSA-975088). The details panel shows the following information:

- Stable Identifier: R-HSA-975088
- DOI: 10.3180/R-HSA-975088.1
- Type: Pathway
- Species: Homo sapiens
- Compartment: cytosol, extracellular region, plasma membrane
- ReviewStatus: 5/5

A red arrow points to the 'ReviewStatus: 5/5' indicator. Below the details panel, there is a section for 'Locations in the PathwayBrowser' with a link to 'Drug ADME (Homo sapiens)'. The 'General' section shows the pathway diagram and download options (SBML, BioPAX, PDF, SVG, PNG, PPTX, SBGN).

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- [5_Visualize Drugs in the Contexts of Reactome Pathways and FI Network](#)
 - [5.1_Visualize Cancer Drugs in Reactome Pathways](#)
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- [6_Perform scRNA-seq Data Analysis and Visualization](#)
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- [7_Other Features Related to the FI Network](#)
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- [7.4._Load Cancer Gene Index Annotations](#)
- [7.5._Survival Analysis](#)

Overview

The [ReactomeFIViz](#) app is designed to find pathways and network patterns related to cancer and other types of diseases. This app accesses the [Reactome](#) pathways stored in the database, help you to do pathway enrichment analysis for a set of genes, visualize hit pathways using manually laid-out pathway diagrams directly in Cytoscape, and investigate functional relationships among genes in hit pathways. The app can also access the Reactome Functional Interaction (FI) network, a highly reliable, manually curated pathway-based protein functional interaction network covering over 60% of human proteins, and allows you to construct a FI sub-network based on a set of genes, query the FI data source for the underlying evidence for the interaction, build and analyze network modules of highly-interacting groups of genes, perform functional enrichment analysis to annotate the modules, expand the network by finding genes related to the experimental data set, display pathway diagrams, and overlay with a variety of information sources such as cancer gene index annotations. Recently we have also added features to help users visualize FDA-approved cancer drugs in the contexts of the FI network and Reactome pathways, and use Boolean network models directly built from Reactome pathways to investigate potential functional impacts of displayed cancer drugs.

For an example how we use Reactome FIs for cancer data analysis, please see our publication: [A human functional protein interaction network and its application to cancer data analysis](#).

Download and Launch ReactomeFIViz

ReactomeFIViz app 6 needs Cytoscape 3.7.0 or above. If you have not installed Cytoscape 3.7.0 or above, please download it from Cytoscape's web site: <http://www.cytoscape.org>. After launching Cytoscape, use menu "Apps/App Manager" to open the "App Manager" dialog, and search for "ReactomeFI". You should see the ReactomeFIViz app listed in the middle panel (See the Figure below. You may see a different version number. **Note: The listed name of this app is "ReactomeFIPlugin"**, which is the original name of the app.). Choose the app, and then click the "Install" button at the bottom of the dialog. Follow the procedures to finish the installation.

Install ReactomeFIViz app From App Store

Use Reactome Pathways

Using the pathway visualization and analysis features, you can load pathways in the Reactome database into Cytoscape, visualize Reactome pathways in either the native pathway diagram view or the FI network view, do pathway enrichment analysis for a set of genes, and check genes from your list in hit pathways.

Explore Reactome Pathways

1. Load Reactome pathways: Use menu "Apps/Reactome FI/Reactome Pathways" to load pathways into Cytoscape. The loaded pathways are organized in a hierarchical way as in the Reactome web application (<https://reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/>), and listed in the left side "Control Panel" in the tab called "Reactome".

Reactome Pathways

2. View pathways in Reactome: After selecting a pathway in the pathway hierarchy, you can choose "View Reactome Source" from the popup menu (right click in Windows or Control-click in Macs to get the popup menu)

Pathway Popup Menu

to view its detailed annotation in Reactome. Or you can choose "View in Reactome" to view the detailed information in the Reactome web application.

Note: The ancestor pathways (container pathways) for a selected pathway are displayed in the middle panel, "Selected Event Branch", in the Reactome tab. You can click an ancestor pathway in this middle panel to view the clicked pathway's location in the original pathway hierarchical tree. However, the ancestor pathway will not be selected in the original tree. This is a designed behavior to keep the selection in the original tree.

3. Search pathways: Choose "Search" in the popup menu to bring up the search dialog. The found pathway(s) will be highlighted in blue in the pathway tree.
Note: Search will be against all loaded pathways, not limited to the selected pathway and its contained sub-pathways.

Search pathways and reactions:

 Match whole name only

OK

Cancel

Search Pathways

4. Open Reactome Reactoam: The Reactoam view provides a holistic view of all (exclude disease) human pathways in the Reactome database. Choose "Open Reactome Reactoam" in the popup menu to open the Reactome Reactoam in the default browser.

- ▶ Extracellular matrix organization
- ▼ Gene expression (Transcription)
 - ▶ RNA Polymerase II Transcription
 - ▶ RNA Polymerase II Transcription
 - ▶ RNA Polymerase II Transcription
 - ▶ Transcription from mitochondrial promoters
 - ▶ Gene Silencing by RNA
 - ▶ Epigenetic regulation of gene expression
- ▶ Hemostasis
- ▶ Immune System
- ▼ Metabolism
 - ▶ Metabolism of carbohydrates
 - ▶ Inositol phosphate metabolism
 - ▼ Metabolism of lipids
 - ▶ Regulation of lipoprotein metabolism
 - ▶ PPARA binds RXRA heterodimer
 - ▶ PPARA:RXRA heterodimer activates RXRA
 - ▶ Fatty acid metabolism

View Reactome Source
View in Reactome
Show Diagram

Search
Analyze Pathway Enrichment
Perform GSEA Analysis
Run Graphical Model Analysis
Load Graphical Model Results

View Cancer Drugs
View DrugCentral Drugs

Expand Pathway
Collapse Pathway

Open Reactome Reactoam

Open Reactoam

Note: Pressing your mouse and then holding it to a pathway box will select the pathway in the tree of ReactomeFIV automatically.

Reactome Reactoam

5. Open pathway diagram: Pathways in Reactome are organized in a hierarchical way. Not all pathways have their own pathway diagrams. A smaller pathway (called sub-pathway) may be drawn in a bigger pathway, which has its own pathway diagram. Most of top-level pathways (called modules or super pathways) are used to organize related pathways (e.g. Disease, Signaling Transduction), and therefore contain only rectangle boxes representing canonical pathways.

1. **Show Diagram:** If a selected pathway has its own pathway diagram, you can choose "Show Diagram" in the popup menu to open its pathway diagram into the central Cytoscape desktop.
2. **View in Diagram:** If a selected pathway is laid-out as a sub-pathway in a bigger one, you can choose "View in Diagram" in the popup menu to view its drawing in its container pathway. Reactions contained by the selected pathway will be highlighted in blue after the diagram is opened. For example, see pathway "G1/S DNA Damage Checkpoints" opened in pathway "Cell Cycle Checkpoints" below:

Pathway Diagram

6. Search diagram: Objects displayed in a pathway diagram can be searched using "Search Diagram" from the popup menu (Right click in Windows or Control click in Macs without selecting any Event object in the pathway diagram to get the popup menu). The found objects will be selected and highlighted in blue.

Note: Reactions will not be searched in the diagram. Use the search feature in the pathway tree to search for reactions.

- Export diagram: Displayed diagram can be exported as a PDF, JPG or PNG file. Use "Export Diagram" from the popup menu to export the displayed diagram.
- View Reactome Source or View in Reactome: Select an object, and then right-click (or control click) to get the popup menu. Choose "View Reactome Source" to view the detailed annotation for the selected object in a table (See Figure below for an example). Or choose "View in Reactome" to view the selected object in the Reactome web application.

Reactome Instance View	
classType	Complex
dbId	141440
displayName	hBUBR1:hBUB3:MAD2*:CDC20 complex [cytosol]
compartment	cytosol
hasComponent	BUB1B [cytosol]
	BUB3 [cytosol]
	CDC20 [cytosol]
	Activated MAD2L1 [cytosol]
name	hBUBR1:hBUB3:MAD2*:CDC20 complex
species	Homo sapiens
stableIdentifier	R-HSA-141440.1

Close

Reactome Instance View

- List Genes: Genes contained by a complex or protein set, or a gene related by a displayed protein can be viewed by using a menu item "List Genes" after selecting an object. For example, the following dialog shows genes contained by complex hBUBR1:hBUB3:MAD2*:CDC20. Clicking a gene symbol will bring you to the web page for that gene in the GeneCard web site.

List Genes

Display Reactome Pathways in the FI Network View

1. Display pathway in the FI network view: A Reactome pathway can be converted into a functional interaction network using the method we have established (see [A human functional protein interaction network and its application to cancer data analysis](#)). Use "Convert to FI Network" in the popup menu brought up by right-clicking (Windows) or control-clicking (Macs) an empty area without any selection in the pathway diagram panel. The original pathway diagram will be moved to the bottom-left corner, and a new FI network will be generated based on the original pathway diagram, which will be displayed in a new network panel.
Note: sub-pathways contained by the displayed pathway will be extracted into the FI network too.

Pathway in the FI Network View

2. Explore objects in the pathway and network views: Object selection in three views has been synchronized. Objects that can be selected include: events in the pathway tree view, objects in the pathway view at the bottom-left corner, and genes and FIs in the network view. You can select an object in one of three views, and corresponding objects in other two views should be selected too. Also you should use features implemented in popup menus in each individual view to explore objects as in a single view.

Note: Using Cytoscape's built-in "Saving Session" feature can save the converted FI networks from pathways. However, displayed pathways cannot be saved into a session file for the time being. We will implement this function in a future release.

Pathway Enrichment Analysis

1. **Pathway enrichment analysis:** A list of genes can be used to check if any of Reactome pathways have been enriched. To do this, use the popup menu item, "Analyze Pathway Enrichment" (below left figure), to get the dialog for choosing a gene set file (below right figure). You can use a gene set file in one of three file formats: one gene per line, all genes in the same line and delimited by commas, or all genes in the same line and delimited by tabs. You can also manually input genes by clicking the "Click to Enter" button (one line for one gene).

Note: Dependent on the size of your gene list, it may take over 1 minute for running the pathway enrichment analysis. Pathways used in this feature are different from

Reactome pathways for annotating a FI network or network modules. Here all over 2,000 pathways are used. For annotation, only a subset of Reactome pathways, which have been pre-selected for a certain size, are used.

The image shows a software interface with a list of biological pathways on the left and a context menu on the right. The pathways listed include:

- Cell Cycle
- Cell-Cell Signaling
- Cellular Response to External Stimuli
- Chromatin Replication
- Circadian Rhythm
- Development
- Digestion
- DNA Replication
- DNA Replication
- Extracellular Matrix Organization
- Gene Expression
- Hemostasis
- Immune System
- Metabolism
- Metabolism of Proteins

The context menu on the right contains the following options:

- View Reactome Source
- View in Reactome
- Show Diagram
- Search
- Analyze Pathway Enrichment** (highlighted in blue)
- Perform GSEA Analysis
- Run Graphical Model Analysis
- Load Graphical Model Results
- View Cancer Drugs
- View DrugCentral Drugs
- Expand Pathway
- Collapse Pathway

Note: To get a holistic view of the pathway enrichment analysis results, open the Reactome Reactoam after the analysis using the popup menu "Open Reactome Reactoam" for the pathway tree. You may also download the Reactoam view by clicking the download button at the top-right corner. For windows 10 users, to open the Reactoam view, you need to allow "public" access to Cytoscape by checking "public" in the settings for "Allow an app through Windows Firewall" in the "System and Security" control settings.

- View enrichment analysis results:** Pathway enrichment results are displayed as a table labeled as "Reactome Pathway Enrichment" in the "Table Panel" at the bottom of the main Cytoscape window. You can use "Views in Diagram" to view hit pathways in the pathway diagram view, and use "Export Annotations" to save the results in the table. Pathways in the Reactome pathway tree are highlighted in different colors based on their FDR values. Objects containing genes from your gene list are highlighted in a purple background with a white font in the pathway diagram view. Hit genes are displayed in a thick purple border in the FI network view for a hit pathway.

Note: Hit genes are displayed with same colors in the "Gene List" dialog from the "List Genes" feature.

Pathway Enrichment Results

- Perform GSEA analysis:** Gene Set Enrichment Analysis ([GSEA](#)) is a rank-based pathway enrichment analysis approach, widely used in pathway-based data analysis. ReactomeFIViz provides support to perform GSEA analysis for Reactome pathways using a gene score file. Gene score may be t-score from differential gene expression analysis or other type of scores that can be ranked. To perform the GSEA pathway enrichment analysis, you need to provide a tab-delimited text file containing two columns: the first for gene symbols (human only) and the second for gene scores. The first row is reserved for the column headers, and will not be imported for analysis. To perform GSEA analysis, use popup menu "Perform GSEA Analysis" in the pathway tree to bring up the GSEA configuration dialog, where you can enter the gene score file and choose the minimum and maximum size of pathways along with the permutation number.

Perform GSEA Analysis

Configure GSEA Analysis

The GSEA analysis results are displayed in the table labeled as "Reactome GSEA Analysis" in Cytoscape Table Panel. Pathways subject to GSEA analysis in the pathway tree are highlighted based on FDR values as in the gene set-based pathway enrichment analysis (See above). For details about the meanings of columns shown in the results table, please consult the original GSEA document: [GSEA Document](#).

ReactomePathway	EnrichedScore	NormalizedEnrichedScore	P-value	FDR	Direction
AUF1 (hnRNP D0) binds and destabilizes mRNA	-0.5908	-2.1683	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Activation of NF-kappaB in B cells	-0.5985	-2.3642	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Antigen processing-Cross presentation	-0.5153	-2.1741	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Autodegradation of the E3 ubiquitin ligase COP1	-0.6392	-2.2553	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
CDT1 association with the CDC6:ORC:origin co...	-0.5949	-2.2210	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Cellular response to hypoxia	-0.5755	-2.3033	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Complex I biogenesis	-0.6180	-2.3284	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Cross-presentation of soluble exogenous antig...	-0.6283	-2.2491	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Dectin-1 mediated noncanonical NF-kB signaling	-0.5694	-2.2699	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Degradation of AXIN	-0.6053	-2.2194	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Degradation of DVL	-0.6116	-2.2051	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Degradation of GLI1 by the proteasome	-0.5841	-2.1861	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Degradation of GLI2 by the proteasome	-0.5995	-2.2175	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Downstream TCR signaling	-0.5151	-2.1882	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down
Downstream signaling events of R Cell Receptor	-0.5371	-2.2207	0.0000E+00	0.0000E+00	Down

GSEA Analysis Results

- Overlay Gene Scores onto Pathways:** For significant pathways produced from the GSEA analysis, you can overlay gene scores to investigate locations of products of genes

having significant high or low scores, therefore to understand potential pathway activity impact caused by these extreme scores. To do this, use popup menu "Overlay Gene Scores" in pathway diagram view to choose the gene score file in the configuration dialog. After the file loading, entities in pathway diagrams will be highlighted based on scores. You may choose one or more genes in the right gene scores Table View to visualize related entities in the pathway diagram.

Overlay Gene Scores

Gene Score Overlay Results

Note: If an entity (e.g. a complex or an EntitySet) is composed of more than one gene, the score for the entity is the mean of all genes annotated for that entity. To remove overlaid gene scores in the pathway diagram, use popup menu "Remove Gene Scores". To view the distribution of scores for genes annotated in the displayed pathway diagram, choose "Plot View" in the "Gene Scores" tab in Cytoscape Results Panel (see below).

Gene Scores

Gene Score Distribution

■ All Genes ■ Pathway Genes

Table View

Plot View

Probabilistic Graphical Model based Pathway Analysis

We adapted the PARADIGM approach for Reactome pathways by converting reactions drawn in pathway diagrams into factors in factor graphs, a type of probabilistic graphical models (PGMs). For details about the PARADIGM approach, see: [Inference of patient-specific pathway activities from multi-dimensional cancer genomics data using PARADIGM](#). For introduction to factor graphs, see this wikipedia entry: [Factor Graph](#). For test purposes, you can download two sample data files for 100 TCGA ovarian cancer patients: [CNVs](#) and [mRNA gene expression](#). The original TCGA OV files were downloaded from [the Broad GDAC Firehose](#) web site.

1. **Run graphical model analysis in batch:** This feature is used to perform a batch graphical model analysis for all Reactome pathways having manual layout diagrams.
 1. **Start the analysis:** Choose the popup menu, "Run Graphical Model Analysis", in the pathway hierarchical tree. After choosing this menu, you will be asked to choose data files and provide parameters for inference algorithms in the following two tabs in the "Run Graphical Model Analysis" dialog:

Run Graphical Model Analysis

Specify Observation Data Set up Inference Algorithms

DNA Data

Choose CNV file:

Use empirical distribution

Choose threshold values for discretizing:

State 0: less than

State 1: less than

State 2: no less than

Gene Expression

Choose gene expression file:

Use empirical distribution

Choose threshold values for discretizing:

State 0: less than

State 1: less than

State 2: no less than

Number of permutations:

Used for pathway analysis for samples with two cases.

Choose a sample information file:

Note: A sample information file should be a text file: one line for one sample containing sample name and type separated by a tab, two types only, and no title line. Your analysis will be performed against samples in this file.

LoadData

SetUpAlgorithms

Notes:

1). If you choose "Use empirical distribution" in the data loading dialog, your loaded data will be used directly to construct factor functions without discretizing. At present, we recommend to use "Choose threshold values for discretizing".

2). It is recommended to use the default parameters for inference algorithms for a batch analysis for quick performance. You can try different parameters for some specific pathways after you find interesting pathways from the batch analysis. ***If you want to perform two-case study (e.g. case-control, drug sensitive/insensitive, etc), check the checkbox, "Used for pathway analysis for***

samples with two cases", and provide a sample information file as required. For two-case analysis, a random data set will not be generated. Results will be presented by comparing two types of samples in your uploaded data files.

2. **Run the analysis:** Click the "OK" button to start the batch analysis. Depending on your sample size, it may take hours to finish the whole analysis.
3. **Finish the analysis:** After the batch analysis done, you may see the following list if some of pathways cannot be analyzed because the inference algorithm cannot converge. Please make sure the following list is small (probably less than 10 pathways) so that you can get enough results.

FailedPathwaysList

4. **View the results:** The results from the batch analysis are displayed at the bottom table panel of the Cytoscape desktop as the following:

Table Panel

Apply Filters: FDR 0.01

ReactomePathway	AverageUpIPA	AverageDownIPA	CombinedPValue	MinimumPValue	FDR_CombinedPValue	FDR_MinimumPValue
ABC-family proteins mediated transport	NaN	-5.93E-01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
APC/C-mediated degradation of cell cy...	8.49E-02	-1.12E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Abacavir transport and metabolism	NaN	-1.67E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Aflatoxin activation and detoxification	NaN	-1.96E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Apoptotic execution phase	1.11E-01	-6.79E-01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Arachidonic acid metabolism	9.22E-02	-1.31E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Asparagine N-linked glycosylation	1.49E-01	-9.53E-01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Assembly of collagen fibrils and other ...	4.57E-01	-1.98E-01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Assembly of the primary cilium	NaN	-1.13E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Base Excision Repair	NaN	-1.84E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Bile acid and bile salt metabolism	NaN	-1.91E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Binding and Uptake of Ligands by Scav...	7.90E-02	-8.43E-01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Cell Cycle Checkpoints	1.41E-01	-9.70E-01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Cell surface interactions at the vascular ...	2.81E-01	-6.95E-01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Cellular response to heat stress	1.84E-01	-1.68E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Chromatin modifying enzymes	8.30E-02	-1.45E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00

Node Table | Edge Table | Network Table | Pathway PGM Analysis

BatchResults

Note: There are 7 columns in this table: ReactomePathway for pathway names analyzed by the App; AverageUpIPA shows how much a pathway is up-perturbed by comparing to a random background (IPA: integrated pathway activity. See the above PARADIGM paper for details); AverageDownIPA shows how much a pathway is down-perturbed; CombinedPValue is a p-value indicating how significant this pathway is perturbed based on pathway outputs and the Fisher's method; MinimumPValue is the minimum p-value for pathway outputs; the last two columns are FDRs for two p-values based on the Benjamini-Hochberg method. AverageUpIPA or AverageDownIPA may be NaN, which indicates there is no detected up or down perturbation based on this analysis. The FDR filtering works based on the FDR values displayed in the last two columns with "OR" operation.

5. **Save the results:** To keep the results, use the popup menu in the table, "Export Annotations", to save the results into an external text file. The saved results can be loaded later on by using popup menu, "Load Graphical Model Results", in the pathway tree.
2. **Run graphical model analysis for a single pathway:** This feature is used to perform a graphical model analysis for a pathway displayed in the Cytoscape desktop.
 1. **Open a pathway:** As before, you can choose a pathway in the pathway tree, and open its diagram in the Cytoscape desktop. Or you can choose an interesting pathway from the batch analysis results table by choosing popup menu, "View in Diagram".
 2. **Start the analysis:** Choose popup menu, "Run Graphical Model Analysis", from the popup menu list in the pathway diagram window. You will be asked to provide data files and set up inference algorithms as in the batch analysis. After clicking the "OK" button, you will be asked to provide a list of escape names for entities in the pathway that will not be considered in the graphical model (e.g. ATP, ADP, etc) in the following dialog:

EscapeNameDialog

Note: If you have loaded data files, you may choose to use the loaded data files without displaying the data loading dialog.

- View the results:** After the analysis is done, three tabs are displayed in the table pane of Cytoscape: IPA Pathway Analysis, IPA Sample Analysis and IPA Node Values. IPA Pathway analysis displays inference results for entities in the pathway by comparing samples in your data files and in a random data set generated dynamically by the App based on your data files. IPA Sample Analysis shows results for each individual samples as up or down perturbation. You may choose to show/hide p-values and FDR values for samples in the table. IPA Node Values show inference results for selected entities in the pathway diagram for each sample. Entities in the pathway diagram are highlighted based on values in the MeanDiff column in the IPA Pathway Analysis tab.

CellCycleCheckPointsResults

Note: You may change the color spectrum mapping for pathway diagram highlighting by double-clicking the color spectrum bar at the bottom of pathway diagram window to get the dialog for setting min/max values. You can save the analysis results for a pathway by using popup menu, "Save Analysis Results", and load the results back later on by "Open Analysis Results".

4. **Analyze gene level results:** The up or down perturbation results are inferred based on genomic data files for individual genes. The App provides features to analyze observation results and inference results for individual genes. You can view gene-level observation and inference results for the whole pathway by using popup menus, "Show Gene Level Analysis Results" and "Show Observations". You can also view these results for genes contained by an entity displayed in the pathway diagram after selecting that entity and then using these two popup menus. The following two dialogs show gene level observations and inference results for genes whose products are contained by complex "hBUBR1:hBUB3:MAD2*:CDC20 complex [cytosol]" in the cell cycle checkpoints pathway:

ObservationsForEntity

GeneLevelResultsForEntity

- Analyze and visualize results for individual samples:** The inference results and loaded observation data are displayed in the right "Results Panel" (see below). By checking "Highlight pathway for sample", entities in the displayed

pathway diagram will be highlighted based on inferred IPA values for the selected sample displayed in the "Choose sample" box. You can also enable animation by clicking the play button. There are two tabs in the "Results Panel": "Inference" for showing inferred IPA values, and "Observation" tab for loaded observed data related to entities in the pathway (Note: if you choose "discretizing", the displayed observation values are discretized: 0 for lower than normal, 1 for normal, and 2 for higher normal). Objects in three views (pathway diagram, inference table, and observation table) are synchronized for selection.

PGM Sample View: Inference

PGM Sample View: Observation

- Compare analysis results for two samples:** You can compare observation data and inference results for two samples. To do this, choose two samples in the "IPA Sample Analysis" tab in the bottom results pane, and use popup menu "Compare Samples" to bring out another tab called "Sample Comparison". You can view comparing results for inference and observation data.

Two Sample Comparison

Boolean Network Based Pathway Analysis

We have developed an approach (Manuscript in preparation) to convert biochemical reactions-based Reactome pathways into Boolean networks and then perform pathway simulation based on the constrained fuzzy logic method according to [Training Signaling Pathway Maps to Biochemical Data with Constrained Fuzzy Logic: Quantitative Analysis of Liver Cell Responses to Inflammatory Stimuli](#) and [Querying quantitative logic models \(Q2LM\) to study intracellular signaling networks and cell-cytokine interactions](#). Based on this approach, the user can perform pathway simulation inside Cytoscape using rich Reactome pathways based on fuzzy logic built upon Boolean networks.

1. **Set up and run logic model simulation:** Choose popup menu "Run Logic Model Analysis" in the Pathway Diagram View to get the New Simulation dialog. Enter a name for the simulation and the default value, which usually should be 1.0 to enable that the simulation can proceed, and then choose either PROD or MIN for the AND gate mode (the default choice PROD usually should be fine).

Note: You may also choose an Transfer Function and adjust parameters for Hill

function. However, for simplicity, it is suggested to use "Identity Function" first. For how to apply drugs for logic model simulation, see below.

The image shows a screenshot of a software application's menu. The menu is organized into several sections, each separated by a horizontal line. The first section contains the option "Convert to FI Network". The second section, which is highlighted with a blue background, contains "Run Logic Model Analysis". The third section contains "Remove Analysis Results". The fourth section contains "Run Graphical Model Analysis", "Show Gene Level Analysis Results", "Show Observation", "Save Analysis Results", and "Open Analysis Results". The fifth section contains "Overlay Gene Scores" and "Remove Gene Scores". The sixth section contains "Fetch Cancer Drugs", "Fetch DrugCentral Drugs", and "Filter Drugs". The seventh section contains "Search Entities", "Search Reactions", and "Export Diagram".

- Convert to FI Network
- Run Logic Model Analysis
- Remove Analysis Results
- Run Graphical Model Analysis
- Show Gene Level Analysis Results
- Show Observation
- Save Analysis Results
- Open Analysis Results
- Overlay Gene Scores
- Remove Gene Scores
- Fetch Cancer Drugs
- Fetch DrugCentral Drugs
- Filter Drugs
- Search Entities
- Search Reactions
- Export Diagram

New BN Simulation

After clicking the OK button in the New Simulation dialog, the default initial configuration will be displayed in the Results Panel. You may change the variable Type and Modification in the set up table by clicking the cell for the selected variable. To run the simulation, click the Simulate button in the Results Panel.

Results Panel

Boolean Network Modelling

Entity	Type	Initial	Modification	Strength
PP2A-B56-beta,gamma [cyto...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PP2A-B56-beta,gamma:IER3:...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN gene [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN mRNA [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN mRNA:miR-26A RISC [c...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
Pi [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
RPS6KB2 [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
THEM4/TRIB3 [plasma membr...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
TORC2 complex [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
TP53 Tetramer [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
TP53 Tetramer:PTEN Gene [n...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
TSC2 [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
miR-26A RISC [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-FOXO1,p-FOXO3,p-FOXO4...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S-AKT:PDPK1:PIP3 [plasma ...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0

Use larger values for stimulation variables

*: Simulation for PIP3 activates AKT signaling

Set up Boolean Network Analysis

Entity	Type	Initial	Modification	Strength
PP2A-B56-beta,gamma [cyto...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PP2A-B56-beta,gamma:IER3:...	Stimulation	0	None	0.0
PTEN [cytosol]	Respondent	0	None	0.0
PTEN gene [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0

Choose BN Variable Type

Entity	Type	Initial	Modification	Strength
PP2A-B56-beta,gamma [cyto...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PP2A-B56-beta,gamma:IER3:...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN gene [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN mRNA [cytosol]	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
PTEN mRNA:miR-26A RISC [c...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0

Choose BN Modification Type

2. **Visualize the simulation results:** After the simulation is done, entities in the pathway diagram will be highlighted based on simulated values, which should be between 0 and 1. You may choose one or more entities to visualize their temporal behaviors inside the Table Panel at the bottom of Cytoscape. Attractors computed from the simulation are also listed in the right columns in the original set up table inside the Results Panel. **Note:** After simulation, you will not be able to modify any initial configuration.

Boolean Network Simulation Results

Note: To avoid clutter, if too many time steps have been generated for a logic model simulation, only the last 20 time steps are displayed in the table. However, the plot

shows all time steps. You may choose different columns to display in the table by use popup menu "Configure Columns" after selecting any variables in the table.

3. **Perform pathway simulation via modification:** Simulation with Boolean network can help users uncover the impact of modification of entity activities (e.g. inhibition or activation caused by somatic mutation) on the pathway behaviors. For example, in PIP3 activates AKT signaling, Complex AKT:PIP3 forms a complex with EntitySet THEM4/TRIB3 to form another complex, which inhibits the activation of AKT (For details see [Reactome PIP3 activates AKT signaling](#)). To perform simulation with modification, choose modification type in the simulation set up table and assign the strength to the modification.

Choose Inhibition for Boolean Network Simulation

Clicking the Simulate button invokes the constrained fuzzy logic model simulation with this configured inhibition. You can compare the simulation results between the two configurations by selecting an entity and then toggling the simulation result tables at the bottom of Cytoscape.

Active AKT in Inhibition

Active AKT in Default

You can also use the "Compare" button in the Results Panel to get the comparison dialog and then choose two simulations for comparison. The comparison results are displayed in a new table listed at the bottom Table Panel.

The 'Compare Simulations' dialog box prompts the user to select two simulations for comparison. Simulation I is set to 'THEM4/TRIB3_Inhibition' and Simulation II is set to 'Default'. The dialog includes 'OK' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Comparison Dialog

The Table Panel displays the results of the comparison between 'THEM4/TRIB3_Inhibition' and 'Default'. The summary indicates 35 outputs, a sum of output absolute difference of 1.84e+01, and an average of 5.2448e-01. The table lists various entities and their values for both simulations, along with relative differences.

Entity	THEM4/TRIB3_I...	Default:Type	THEM4/TRIB3_I...	Default:Initial	THEM4/TRIB3_I...	Default:Modifica...	THEM4/TRIB3_I...	Default:Strength	RelativeDiffe...
p-S-AKT-PIP3 [pl...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.97342192691...
p-S-AKT-PDPK1.P...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.96039603960...
p-T,p-S-AKT [cyt...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94719471947...
p-T,p-S-AKT [nu...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94684385382...
p-S109-MKRN1 [...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-S166,S188-MD...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-S183,T246-AK...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-S196-CASP9(L...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-S9/21-GSK3 [c...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-S939,T1462-T...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-S99-BAD [cyto...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-T-AKT [cytosol]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-T-CDKN1A/B [...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
p-T23-CHUK [cyt...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94648829431...
ADP [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94612794612...
p-S133-CREB1 [n...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94612794612...
p-S15,S356-RPS...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94612794612...
p-S351-NR4A1 [...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94612794612...
p-T24,S256,S319...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.94612794612...
ADP [cytosol]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.0
AKT [cytosol]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.0
AKT1 [cytosol]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.0

Active AKT in Comparison

Note: The RelativeDifference in the comparison result table is calculated based on relative change for each fuzzy logic variable, calculated as $(\text{valueInSim2} - \text{valueInSim1}) / (\text{valueInSim2} + \text{valueInSim1})$. The time course may be interpolated based on the attractor until this relative difference converges.

4. To remove all displayed constrained fuzzy logic simulation results, use popup menu, "Remove Analysis Results" under "Run Logic Model Analysis". The pathway diagram should be reset to the original colors, and all tables related to logic model simulations will be deleted.

Visualization of Structural Variants in the Context of Reactome Pathways

By collaborating with Drs. Francesco Raimondi and Rob Russell at the University of Heidelberg to utilize protein-protein interaction 3D structures provided by [Mechismo](#), a platform developed by [Dr. Russell's group](#) to study the contributions of individual amino acid residues to protein structure and function, we have systematically analyzed mutations in the TCGA dataset and collected a set of reactions and functional interactions that involve proteins significantly enriched with mutations in their interaction interfaces (manuscript in preparation). We have added features to ReactomeFIViz to visualize these 3D structures and mutated residues in the contexts of Reactome pathways, reactions, and interactions.

1. **Visualize analysis results in the context of a pathway and its reactions:** In the opened pathway diagram view (See [Explore Reactome Pathways](#) for how to open a pathway diagram), use the popup menu "Load Mechismo Results" to load the analysis results into the opened pathway diagram. After the results are loaded, reactions are colored based on FDR values as listed in the bottom table labeled as "Mechismo Reaction".

Mechismo Reaction View

Note: You may choose results from a different cancer type or pancancer by clicking the list at the top of the bottom tab labeled as "Choose a cancer type to highlight reactions based on FDRs in the table". Some of reactions are not highlighted by any color since there are no structural variants found for proteins annotated for these reactions. To remove the loaded results from the pathway diagram, use another popup menu "Remove Mechismo Results".

2. **Visualize analysis results in the context of a pathway FI network:** After the Mechismo results are loaded into the pathway diagram, you can convert the diagram into a FI network by using popup menu "Convert to FI Network" as usual. The edges displayed in the FI network view are highlighted based on FDR values listed in the bottom table labeled as "Mechismo Interaction".

Mechismo Interaction View

Note: To make the FI network view simpler, check "Show FIs Only for Selected" at the left-bottom corner for the pathway diagram view. You may choose a reaction or complex and then view extracted FIs for the selected object in the pathway diagram view. Some of reactions and complexes may not contain any FI (e.g. a complex composed of a protein and a chemical or a reaction between a protein and a chemical).

3. **Visualize structural variants in the protein-protein 3D structures:** In the FI network view, choose the popup menu called "Fetch Mechismo Results" to bring the view for protein-protein interaction 3D models. Structural variants collected from the TCGA data set are mapped to the original protein-protein interaction 3D structures based on the [Mechismo](#) platform.

Mechismo Structure View

Note: In the structure view, amino acid residues whose coordinates are mapped to structural variants are displayed in balls. The residues that are mapped to the selected rows in the bottom table are highlighted in yellow. ReactomeFIViz uses [Jmol](http://www.jmol.org/) for protein 3D structure visualization. For more information about how to use Jmol, see its documentation: <http://jmol.sourceforge.net/docs/>.

Use the Reactome Functional Interaction (FI) Network

After the ReactomeFIViz app installed, you should see a menu item called "Reactome FI" under the Apps menu. Clicking this menu, you will see 6 sub-menus: [Gene Set/Mutation Analysis](#), [PGM Impact Analysis](#), [Microarray Data Analysis](#), [Reactome Pathways](#) and [User Guide](#). Gene set/mutation analysis is for doing FI network-based data analysis for a set of genes or a mutation data file, PGM Impact analysis for performing functional impact analysis based on a probabilistic graphical model for the Reactome FI network using multiple omics data types, HotNet mutation analysis for the HotNet algorithm to search for network modules (see <http://compbio.cs.brown.edu/projects/hotnet/>), microarray data analysis for doing MCL (Markov Graph Clustering, <http://micans.org/mcl/>) based FI network clustering analysis by converting a non-weighted FI network to weighted network using correlations among genes in the network, Reactome pathways for loading pathways from the Reactome database, visualizing Reactome pathways directly in Cytoscape in a their native way, and doing pathway enrichment analysis, and user guide brings you to this user guide.

Gene Set/Mutation Analysis

1. You can enter a list of genes directly into ReactomeFIViz by clicking the "Enter" button, or load it from a local file. Currently ReactomeFIViz supports three file formats for gene set/mutation analysis:
 1. **Simple gene set:** one line per gene. For example, [GWASFuzzyGenes.txt](#), a list of T2D GWAS genes.
 2. **Gene/sample number pair.** For example, [GeneSampleNumber.txt](#), which contains two required columns, gene and number of samples having gene mutated, and an optional third column listing sample names (delimited by ";").
 3. **NCI MAF (mutation annotation file).** For example, [GlioblastomaMutationTable.txt](#), the mutation file from the TCGA GBM project.
2. Choose a FI network version from listed three versions.
Note: you may get different results using different FI network versions because a later version may contain more proteins/genes and more FIs. But based on our experience, a significant FI network module is usually stable across multiple versions.
3. Enter genes directly by clicking the "Enter" button or choose a file containing genes you want to use to construct a functional interaction network. To choose a file, select an appropriate file format and parameters to load genes and construct FI network in the dialog. Click the "OK" button to start the FI network building process.

ReactomeFIViz

Gene Set/Mutation Analysis

Reactome FI Network Version

2018 2017 2016

** Different versions of the FI network may produce different results.*

Gene Set Parameters

Choose data file:

Or enter gene set:

Specify format: Gene set
 Gene/sample number pair
 NCI MAF (Mutation Annotation File)

Choose sample cutoff:

** Genes altered in 2 or more samples will be chosen if '2' is entered.*

Choose genes mutated at both alleles

FI Network Construction Parameters

Fetch FI annotations
** Annotations may be fetched later.*

Use linker genes

Show genes not linked to others

- The constructed FI network will be displayed in the network view panel. A FI specific visual style will be created automatically for the FI network.

Reactome FI Sub-Network

- The main features of Reactome FI plug-in should be invoked from a popup menu, which can be displayed by right clicking an empty space in the network view panel.

- Fetch FI annotations:** query detailed information on selected FIs. Three FI related edge attributes will be created: FI Annotation, FI Direction, and FI Score. Edges will be displayed based on FI direction attribute values. In the following screenshot, "->" for activating/catalyzing, "-|" for inhibition, "-" for FIs extracted from complexes or inputs, and "---" for predicted FIs. See the "VizMapper" tab, Edge Source Arrow Shape and Edge Target Arrow Shape values for details.

FI Annotations

Note: Here is a short explanation about displayed columns: GeneSet for pathways collected in the Reactome FI network hit by the query gene list; RatioOfProteinInGeneSet for ratios of numbers of genes contained in pathways to total genes in the Reactome FI network; NumberOfProteinInGeneSet for numbers of genes in pathways;

ProteinFromNetwork for numbers of hit genes from the query gene list; P-value for p-values calculated based on binomial test; FDR for FDRs calculated based on p-values using Benjamini-Hochberg method; Nodes for hit genes in pathways.

- Analyze network functions:** pathway or GO term enrichment analysis for the displayed network. You can choose to filter enrichment results by a FDR cutoff value. Also you can choose to display nodes in the network panel for a selected row or rows by checking "Hide nodes in not selected rows". The letter in parentheses after each pathway gene set name corresponds to the source of the pathway annotations: C - CellMap, R - Reactome, K - KEGG, N - NCI PID, P - Panther, and B - BioCarta. The following screenshot shows results from a pathway enrichment analysis.

GeneSet	RatioOfProteinInGeneSet	NumberOfProteinInGeneSet	ProteinFromNetwork	P-value	FDR	Nodes
ViralCholera_infection(K)	0.0050	51	5	9.7200E-06	1.8355E-03	ATP6V0E1, PRKACB, KCNQ1, ...
MicroRNAs in cancer(K)	0.0291	297	12	1.0840E-05	1.8659E-03	E2F3, CCNE2, SPRY2, CDKN2, ...
Rheumatoid arthritis(K)	0.0087	89	7	1.4083E-05	1.8659E-03	ATP6V0E1, LTB, VEGFA, TNF, ...
HTLV-I infection(K)	0.0253	258	11	1.5906E-05	1.8659E-03	E2F3, TLN2, CDKN2A, PRKAC, ...
Protein processing in endop...	0.0165	169	9	1.7941E-05	1.8659E-03	SEC24A, SSR1, MAP3K5, SAR, ...
Type II diabetes mellitus(K)	0.0047	48	5	6.8563E-05	5.9650E-03	KCNJ11, PRKCE, IRS1, TNF, A, ...
Focal adhesion(K)	0.0203	207	9	8.5129E-05	6.2996E-03	TLN2, BCAR1, ACTN1, VEGFA, ...
Collecting duct acid secreto...	0.0026	27	4	9.9692E-05	6.4800E-03	ATP6V0E1, ATP6V1G2, ATP, ...
FGF signaling pathway(P)	0.0090	92	6	1.6391E-04	9.3745E-03	SPRY4, SPRY2, MAP3K5, PRK, ...
Natural killer cell mediated ...	0.0131	134	7	1.8028E-04	9.3745E-03	HLA-C, HLA-B, TNF, PTK2B, P, ...
ROS, RNS production in res...	0.0033	34	4	2.3933E-04	0.0112	ATP6V0E1, ATP6V1G2, ATP, ...
Pre-NOTCH Expression and...	0.0037	38	4	3.6370E-04	0.0136	E2F3, FURIN, NOTCH2, NOT, ...
MAPK signaling pathway(K)	0.0250	255	9	3.9634E-04	0.0136	MAP3K5, PRKACB, ARRB1, T, ...
Phagosome(K)	0.0150	153	7	3.9939E-04	0.0136	ATP6V0E1, HLA-C, HLA-B, A, ...
Iron uptake and transport(R)	0.0038	39	4	4.0086E-04	0.0136	ATP6V0E1, ATP6V1G2, ATP, ...
Integrin signalling pathway(P)	0.0155	158	7	4.8305E-04	0.0145	BCAR1, MAP3K5, ACTN1, PT, ...
Bladder cancer(K)	0.0040	41	4	4.8321E-04	0.0145	E2F3, CDKN2A, VEGFA, RAF1, ...

Pathways in FI Sub-Network

Tip: To analyze pathway or GO term enrichment on a set of genes that are not linked together, select the "Show genes not linked to others" option in the "Set Parameters for FI Network" dialog.

- Cluster FI network:** run a network clustering algorithm (spectral partition based network clustering by [Newman 2006](#)) on the displayed FI network. Nodes in different network modules will be shown in different colors (different colors used only for first 15 modules based on sizes).

Network Modules

- **Analyze module functions:** pathway or GO term enrichment analysis for each individual network modules. You can select a size cutoff to filter out network modules that are too small, choose a FDR cutoff to view enriched pathways or GO terms under a certain FDR value, and view nodes in a selected row or rows only in the network diagram.
- **Analyze functions for a set of selected genes:** select a set of nodes displayed in the network view and then choose the popup menu, Analyze Nodes Functions, to perform pathway or GO term enrichment analysis. The results will be displayed in a dialog.
- **Load Cancer Gene Index:** load cancer gene index annotations. For details, see section [Load Cancer Gene Index](#).

PGM Impact Analysis

1. We have developed a probabilistic graphical model (PGM)-based functional impact analysis using the Reactome FI network by integrating multiple omics data types together. The current version of ReactomeFIViz supports four omics data types: CNV, mRNA expression, DNA methylation, and somatic mutation. PGMs used for this analysis are based on [Markov random field \(MRF\)](#). Currently we support two types of MRFs: [Pairwise MRF](#) and [Nearest neighbor Gibbs MRF](#). You can choose one of these two models. We recommend pair-wise MRF for its simplicity.

- To perform PGM-based functional impact analysis, choose menu, Apps/Reactome FI/PGM Impact Analysis/Analyze. You can enter your omics data by using the PGM configuration dialog.

Reactome FI Network Version

2018 2017 2016

** Different versions of the FI network may produce different results.*

Data Parameters

Choose data file: FIPlugIns/test_data/ImpactAnalysis/ov.mRNA.txt

Specify data type: mRNA_EXP

Specify distribution: Discrete based on thresholds

Note: Values <-1.96 or values >1.96 as abnormal

The following data will be used for impact analysis:

Data File Name	Data Type	Abnormal Distribution
/Users/wug/Documents/wgm/work/...	Mutation	Empirical
/Users/wug/Documents/wgm/work/...	Methylation	<-1.96 or >1.96
/Users/wug/Documents/wgm/work/...	CNV	<-1.96 or >1.96
/Users/wug/Documents/wgm/work/...	mRNA_EXP	<-1.96 or >1.96

Number of permutations: 100

FI-PGM Configuration Dialog

Notes:

- 1). ReactomeFIViz supports continuous observation variables without discretizing by choosing "Use empirical distribution" in the configuration. For somatic mutation, currently it supports NCI MAF file format only and requires a specific column named "MA_FI.score" for mutation function impact score collected from [Mutation Assessor](#) or from some other sources.
- 2). The default MRF model used is PairwiseMRF. You can choose the default setting for the first test.
- 3). Several parameters are needed for MRF models. We have tuned these parameters based on a small toy model. In the current version of ReactomeFIViz, these parameters cannot be changed.

3. It may take several hours to finish the whole analysis. The actual running time will be dependent on the size of your data. The progress of the job running is displayed in the following progress pane. You can cancel the running at any time.

Progress of FI PGM Running

4. After the analysis is finished, you should see the result dialog similar to the following screenshot. You can use filtering features to filter to a list of genes that you want to use to construct a FI subnetwork for further analysis.

FI-PGM Result Dialog

Note: If you select one or more genes in the result table, only these selected genes will be used to construct a FI sub-network. You can save the full analysis results by clicking the "Save" button (Results for all genes, not just displayed ones, will be saved). We strongly recommend to save your results first before clicking the "OK" button so that you can visit your results back.

- After choosing the "OK" button, a FI subnetwork will be constructed and displayed in a network view. The sizes of displayed nodes are proportional to impact scores inferred from the FI-PGM model. To view impact scores and loaded observation data, you can choose a sample in the Sample List tab in the Results Panel. You can also enable sample-based network visualization of the network by checking "Highlight network for sample" in the Sample List tab. If you want to review the original results used to construct the FI subnetwork, click "Show All Results" in the "Impact Gene Values" tab in "Table Panel".

FI-PGM Result Network

Microarray Data Analysis

The ReactomeFIViz app can load gene expression data file, calculate correlations among genes involved in the same FIs, use the calculated correlations as weights for edges (i.e. FIs) in the whole FI network, apply MCL graph clustering algorithm to the weighted FI network, and generate a sub-network for a list of selected network modules based on module size and average correlation. The generated FI sub-network will be displayed in the network panel, and can be used for analysis as in Gene Set/Mutation Analysis. For details about this method, please see our publication: [A network module-based method for identifying cancer prognostic signatures](#).

An array data file should be a tab-delimited text file with table headers. The first column should be gene names. All other columns should be expression values in different samples. **The data set in the file should be pre-normalized.** For example, see this gene expression file for breast cancer: [NejmLogRatioNormGlobalZScore_070111.txt.zip](#). This data set was download from [van de Vijver et al in 2002](#), and has been normalized.

1. **Select a microarray data file and run MCL network clustering:** After selecting sub-menu "Microarray Data Analysis" from menu Plugins/Reactome FIs, you should see the following dialog. Choose a microarray data file, check if you want to use absolute values as weights for edges, and input an inflation parameter (-I) for the MCL clustering algorithm. The smaller the inflation parameter is, the bigger the average size of generated network modules. Based on our own experience, we use 5.0 for the inflation parameter, the highest recommended value, and choose the absolute value for edge weights. For more details on how to choose the inflation parameter, please see <http://micans.org/mcl/>. After you have set these parameters, click the OK button to load the data file, calculate correlations, and apply the MCL clustering algorithm.

Reactome FI Network Version

2018 2017 2016

** Different versions of the FI network may produce different results.*

File Parameters

Choose data file:

Note: The array file should be a tab-delimited text file with table header. The first column should be gene names. All other columns should be expression values in samples. One column for one sample. All values should be pre-normalized.

Correlation

Correlation calculation method:

Use absolute value (checked is preferred)

Network Clustering

Network clustering algorithm:

Set inflation parameter (-I) for MCL: 1.2 - 5.0 (default 5.0)

Set Parameters for Microarray Data Analysis

2. **Select network modules and build a FI sub-network:** The generated network modules are listed in the MCL clustering results dialog (see below). Only modules having more than 2 genes can be listed, and used in the FI sub-network building. You can choose a module size or an average correlation value (absolute value if absolute has been checked before) to filter out modules that may not be significant (Note: after set these cutoff values, please press the "Enter" key to commit your changes.). In our analysis, we choose modules having 7 or more genes with average correlation values no less than 0.25. These values have been used as default in the dialog. In the dialog, you can see how many modules and genes will be chosen for building FI sub-network under your selected filter values. Click the OK button to start the sub-network building. The built sub-network will be displayed, and can be analyzed as with sub-networks generated from the gene set/mutation analysis.

Choose MCL Modules

Visualize Drugs in the Contexts of Reactome Pathways and FI Network

ReactomeFIViz provide a suite of features to assist users to visualize drugs in the contexts of Reactome pathways and networks. The drug data sources include two: Cancer Targetome ([Blucher et al 2017](#)), which collected all FDA-approved cancer drugs (prior to 2018) and their

target interactions from four sources, including DrugBank, Therapeutic Targets Database, IUPHAR, and BindingDB; [DrugCentral](#), a comprehensive drug database supported by [NIH IDG program](#).

Visualize Drugs in Reactome Pathways

1. **List all FDA approved cancer drugs:** Use popup menu "View Cancer Drugs" in the Reactome pathway tree to get the list of all FDA approved cancer drugs collected in Cancer Targetome in a table dialog.

View Cancer Drugs

A screenshot of this drug list is shown below:

DrugName	ApprovalDate	ATC_Class_ID	ATC_Class_Name	EPC_Class_ID	EPC_Class_Name	Synonyms
Gemtuzumab Ozogamicin	2000-05-17			N0000175571	CD33-directed Cytotoxin	CMA-676, GEMTUZUMAB...
Glucarpidase	2012-01-17	V03AF	Detoxifying agents for a...	N0000184013	Carboxypeptidase	carboxypeptidase-G2, C...
Goserelin Acetate	1989-12-29	L02AE	Gonadotropin releasing ...			GOSERELIN ACETATE, go...
Hydroxyurea	1967-12-07	L01XX	Other antineoplastic age...	N0000180853	Antimetabolite	Onco-Carbide, SQ-1089...
Ibritumomab Tiuxetan	2002-02-19			N0000175658	CD20-directed Radiother...	Ibritumomab Tiuxetan, i...
Ibrutinib	2013-11-13	L01XE	Protein kinase inhibitors	N0000175605	Kinase Inhibitor	BTK_Inhibitor_PCI-3276...
Idarubicin Hydrochloride	1990-09-27	L01DB	Anthracyclines and relat...	N0000175414	Anthracycline Topoisom...	Idarubicin hydrochloride...
Idelalisib	2014-07-23	L01XX	Other antineoplastic age...	N0000175605	Kinase Inhibitor	Zydelig, PI3K-delta_Inhib...
Ifosfamide	1988-12-30	L01AA	Nitrogen mustard analog...	N0000175558	Alkylating Drug	Ifosfamidum, Tronoxal, ...
Imatinib Mesylate	2001-05-10	L01XE	Protein kinase inhibitors	N0000175605	Kinase Inhibitor	Imatinib, STI571, CGP57...
Imiquimod	1997-02-27	D06BB	Antivirals			S 26308, Imiquimod, 4-A...
Ipilimumab	2011-03-25	L01XC	Monoclonal antibodies	N0000182635	CTLA-4-directed Blockin...	BMS-734016, MDX-010, ...
Irinotecan Hydrochloride	1996-06-14	L01XX	Other antineoplastic age...	N0000175609	Topoisomerase Inhibitor	Camptothecin 11, IRINO...
Ixabepilone	2007-10-16	L01DC	Other cytotoxic antibiotics	N0000175592	Microtubule Inhibitor	ixabepilone, Eपोथिलone-...
Ixazomib Citrate	2015-11-20	L01XX	Other antineoplastic age...	N0000175604	Proteasome Inhibitor	IXAZOMIB, MLN9708, ML...
Lanreotide Acetate	2007-08-30	H01CB	Somatostatin and analog...	N0000175904	Somatostatin Analog	LANREOTIDE ACETATE, ...
Lapatinib Ditosylate	2011-03-13	L01XE	Protein kinase inhibitors	N0000175605	Kinase Inhibitor	LAPATINIB, GW572016, I...
Lenalidomide	2005-12-27	L04AX	Other immunosuppressa...	N0000184014	Thalidomide Analog	CC5013, CDC 501, CC-5...
Lenvatinib Mesylate	2015-02-13	L01XE	Protein kinase inhibitors	N0000175605	Kinase Inhibitor	E7080, Lenvatinib Mesyla...
Letrozole	1997-07-25	L02BG	Aromatase inhibitors	N0000175563	Aromatase Inhibitor	letrozole, CCS 20267, Fe...
Leucovorin Calcium	1952-06-20	V03AF	Detoxifying agents for a...	N0000178369	Folate Analog	Calfolex, Leucovorin, Foli...
Leuprolied Acetate	1985-04-09	L02AE	Gonadotropin releasing ...	N0000175655	Gonadotropin Releasing ...	Enantone, leuprolied ace...
Lomustine	1976-08-04	L01AD	Nitrosoureas	N0000175558	Alkylating Drug	1-Nitrosourea, 1-(2-chl...
Mechlorethamine Hydroc...	1949-03-15	L01AA	Nitrogen mustard analog...	N0000175558	Alkylating Drug	Mechlorethamine, Musta...

Filter Drugs:

Google View Targets Run Pathway Impact Analysis Close

List of Cancer Drugs

2. **View drug/target interactions:** Select a drug in the drug table (See Figure above) to perform Google search, or view its targets by clicking one of buttons in the dialog. Two views are provided for drug/target interactions. Drug targets table view (below) shows targets for the selected drug with collected binding affinities, which are divided into different categories (e.g.): KD, IC50, Ki, and EC50. The displayed targets are pre-filtered using a set of default filters. You may change the default filters in the Drug/Target Interaction Filter dialog by clicking the "Filter" button.

ID	Drug	Target	InteractionType	KD (nM)	EC50 (nM)	IC50 (nM)	Ki (nM)
1373	Imatinib Mesylate	ABCG2					500
6	Imatinib Mesylate	ABL1	Inhibition	1.1	90	1.1	13
617	Imatinib Mesylate	ABL2		10			
811	Imatinib Mesylate	BLK		520			
2172	Imatinib Mesylate	CA1					31.9
2181	Imatinib Mesylate	CA12					980
2183	Imatinib Mesylate	CA14					468
2173	Imatinib Mesylate	CA2					30.2
2174	Imatinib Mesylate	CA3					528
2178	Imatinib Mesylate	CA6					392
2179	Imatinib Mesylate	CA7					109
2180	Imatinib Mesylate	CA9					75.7
402	Imatinib Mesylate	CSF1R		11			291
404	Imatinib Mesylate	DDR1		0.7			43
1273	Imatinib Mesylate	DDR2		15			141
823	Imatinib Mesylate	EGFR		76			
925	Imatinib Mesylate	GAK		1,000			
4466	Imatinib Mesylate	HIPK4		960			
399	Imatinib Mesylate	KIT		13	100		46
842	Imatinib Mesylate	LCK		40			160

View Details Filter Overlay Targets to Pathways

Close

Drug Targets Table View

The image shows a dialog box titled "Drug/Target Interaction Filter" with a standard macOS-style title bar (red, yellow, green buttons). The dialog is divided into three main sections:

- Choose support source:** A checkbox labeled "pubmed" is checked.
- Choose affinities (Unit: nM. Empty means all):** Four rows of controls, each with a checked checkbox and a text input field:
 - KD: KD, operator " \leq ", dropdown arrow, value "100.0"
 - IC50: IC50, operator " \leq ", dropdown arrow, value "100.0"
 - Ki: Ki, operator " \leq ", dropdown arrow, value "100.0"
 - EC50: EC50, operator " \leq ", dropdown arrow, value "100.0"
- Choose drugs:** A text input field is empty. Below it is an unchecked checkbox labeled "Match whole name only".

At the bottom right of the dialog are two buttons: "Apply" and "Close".

Drug Target Interaction Filter

In the Drug targets table view, you can choose an interaction and then click the "View Details" button to view the detailed information for the selected interaction. In the details view, you can browse the original pubmed references for experimental evidence, Gene Card entry for target, or Google drug by clicking the hyper links.

Imatinib Mesylate - ABL1	
Drug	Imatinib Mesylate
Target	ABL1
Interaction type	Inhibition
Source (pubmed)	DrugBank: 15799618 , 15917650 , 15949566 , 16153117 , 16205964
	EC50=90 (BindingDB: 16678414)
	IC50=1.1 (BindingDB: 20166671)
	IC50=20 (BindingDB: 23773153)
	IC50=38 (BindingDB: 16220969 , 23473682 , NA_BindingDB_ChEMBL)
	IC50=40 (BindingDB: 12951113 , 17572088)
	IC50=98 (BindingDB: 18447379 , 23301703)
	IC50=110 (BindingDB: 18554909)
	IC50=116 (BindingDB: 24280068)
	IC50=188 (BindingDB: 16783341)

Close

Cancer Drug Interaction Details View

You can also select multiple rows in the table to perform pathway enrichment analysis by clicking "Overlay Targets to Pathways". See [Pathway Enrichment Analysis](#) for details about pathway enrichment analysis results.

Drug targets plot view (below) provides a staged plot of bar charts for evidence-supported interactions between the selected drug and all its targets, suggesting primary target(s) and secondary targets in a single graphical view.

Drug Targets Plot View

3. **View cancer drugs in pathway diagrams:** Cancer drugs can be overlaid directly onto displayed pathway diagrams using the popup menu, "Fetch Cancer Drugs", in the [Pathway Diagram View](#). The fetched cancer drugs are displayed in the pathway diagram, linked to entities containing targets for the displayed drugs.

Fetch Cancer Drugs

Drugs in Pathway Diagram

Note: Use Popup menu "Filter Drugs" to adjust filters to select drugs and interactions in the pathway diagram view; Use "Remove Overlaid Interactions" to remove displayed

drugs; You may choose a displayed entity in the pathway diagram and then use popup menu "Fetch Cancer Drugs" to display drugs targeted to the selected entity only.

To view the detailed information about the interaction between the displayed drug and its targeted entity, choose the link and use popup menu "Show Details" to bring up the drug targets view.

View Details

4. **Perform systems pathway impact analysis:** In the cancer drug list table (see above), you may perform pathway impact analysis for all Reactome pathways having entity level view drawn by choosing the "Run Pathway Impact Analysis" button. After the analysis is done, the impact results are displayed in the table labeled with the selected drug in the Cytoscape Table Panel. See below for an example of the results for Imatinib:

Table Panel

Pathway impact analysis results for Imatinib Mesylate

ReactomePathway	SumOfTotalOutputImpacts	AverageOfOutputImpacts	TargetProteins
Erythrocytes take up carbon dioxide and r...	6.521632981779275	0.5928757256162978	CA1,CA2,CA4
PIP3 activates AKT signaling	10.94286066134701	0.3218488429807944	EGFR,FYN,IRAK1,KIT,LCK,PDGFRA,PDGFRB...
Platelet Adhesion to exposed collagen	1.7465018460045534	0.2910836410007589	FYN,LYN
DAP12 interactions	10.012821889660117	0.2781339413794477	FYN,LCK,SYK
Costimulation by the CD28 family	10.061893217992408	0.2515473304498102	FYN,LCK,LYN,SYK
GPVI-mediated activation cascade	6.727675136817475	0.22425583789391584	FYN,LCK,LYN,SYK
Myogenesis	3.3541869347018114	0.2096366834188632	ABL1,MAPK14
Signaling by PDGF	7.250304061766759	0.20139733504907664	PDGFRA,PDGFRB,SRC
Fc epsilon receptor (FCER1) signaling	14.58269916920086	0.19976300231782	FYN,LYN,MAPK10,MAPK8,MAPK9,SYK
Signalling by NGF	12.971144523882828	0.19653249278610344	IRAK1,MAPK8
Nephrin family interactions	2.7266633827366356	0.19476167019547397	FYN
Other interleukin signaling	3.6740072852363057	0.1837003642618153	CSF1R,FLT3,TYK2
TCR signaling	9.251166667742609	0.16527083335254658	LCK
Erythrocytes take up oxygen and release c...	1.2647913338954686	0.15809891673693358	CA1,CA2,CA4
Cilium Assembly	9.774046224590643	0.1458812869341887	PLK4
GP1b-IX-V activation signalling	1.1402074664775863	0.1425259333096983	RAF1,SYK
Reelin signalling pathway	0.6754443243308631	0.1350888648661726	FYN

Node Table Edge Table Network Table Imatinib Mesylate

Pathway Impact Analysis Results

Note: You may open the pathway diagram using popup menu "View in Diagram" and export the table into a text file using menu "Export Table" in the results table.

Visualize Cancer Drugs in the FI Network

The Reactome FI network provides a network-based view among proteins/genes, where each gene/protein is displayed only once. Visualizing cancer drugs in a FI network context shows a simplified relationship between cancer drugs and their targets. In the [FI Network View](#), use popup menu, "Reactome FI/Overlay Cancer Drugs/Fetch Cancer Drugs", to load cancer drugs for proteins/genes displayed in the FI network. The loaded drugs and interactions between drugs and proteins/genes are rendered in green diamonds and blue edges, respectively.

Note: To remove overlaid drugs in the FI network view, use popup menu, "Reactome FI/Overlay Cancer Drugs/Remove Drugs"; As in the Pathway diagram view, you can also apply filters by using "Filter Drugs" popup menu; To view the details about an interaction between a drug and a target, select the edge, and then use popup menu "Reactome FI/Show Drug/Target Interaction Details". (You may need to zoom into the selected edge.)

Visualize DrugCentral Drugs

Visualize drugs collected in DrugCentral is similar with cancer drugs collected in Cancer Targetome. You can use popup menu "View DrugCentral Drugs" in the pathway tree to list all drugs collected in the DrugCentral database, "Fetch DrugCentral Drugs" popup menu in the pathway diagram view to overlay drugs onto pathways, or "ReactomeFI/Overlay Drugs/Fetch DrugCentral Drugs" to overlay drugs onto the FI network in the network view.

Simulate Impact of Drugs on Pathway Activities

Overlaying cancer drugs onto the contexts of Reactome pathways and its FI network helps users to understand the potential impact of applying drugs on the pathway activities and network behavior. However, the actual perturbation of drugs on pathways may be much more complicated. Performing pathway simulation may help users to understand the actual impact. ReactomeFIViz implements features to assist users to perform Boolean network-based drug simulation. Before you do drug simulation, please read section [Boolean Network Based Pathway Analysis](#) first. In this section, we will use pathway [HDR through Homologous](#)

[Recombination \(HR\) or Single Strand Annealing \(SSA\)](#) and drug Imatinib as an example (Note: To get the following screenshot, open diagram for this pathway, and then fetch cancer drugs and filter drugs to Imatinib using the name filter).

Imatinib in Pathway

1. **Set up new simulation for drug:** In the pathway diagram view, use popup menu, "Run Logic Model Analysis". In the New Simulation dialog, enter a name (e.g. Imatinib) and default value for the simulation, and then choose the mode for the AND gate as in the regular logic model simulation. To perform drug simulation, choose the Drug Application tab and a drug data source, and then click the "... " button to bring up the Drug Selection dialog.

Note: You will need to adjust the drug filters to show all targets for Imatinib as displayed in the following screenshot. Based on the collected annotations for interactions between cancer drugs and their targets, default modification types will be selected (as expected, most of them are inhibition). Strengths of modifications are pre-configured based on affinities collected in our aggregated drug/target database.

Imatinib BN Simulation I

Imatinib BN Simulation II

Choose drugs by selecting: Imatinib Mesylate

ID	Drug	Target	KD (nM)	IC50 (nM)	Ki (nM)	EC50 (nM)	Modification	Strength
2017	Dasatinib	CHEK1					Inhibition	
5	Dasatinib	ABL1	0.016		0.2		Inhibition	0.99
1557	Erlotinib Hydrochloride	CHEK1					Inhibition	
3224	Erlotinib Hydrochloride	CDK2					Inhibition	
802	Erlotinib Hydrochloride	ABL1		16			Inhibition	0.7
1634	Gefitinib	CHEK1					Inhibition	
1463	Gefitinib	ABL1		230			Inhibition	0.5
3667	Gefitinib	CDK2					Inhibition	
1451	Imatinib Mesylate	CHEK1					Inhibition	
1334	Imatinib Mesylate	CDK2					Inhibition	
6	Imatinib Mesylate	ABL1		1.1	1.1	13	90 Inhibition	0.9
2613	Lapatinib Ditosylate	CDK2			11,000		Inhibition	0.1
1944	Lapatinib Ditosylate	CHEK1					Inhibition	
1450	Lapatinib Ditosylate	ABL1			23,000		Inhibition	0.1
1960	Nilotinib	CHEK1					Inhibition	

View Details Filter Targets OK Close

Select Drugs for BN Simulation

Note: Since no affinities can be found for interactions between Imatinib and CHEK1 or CDK2, CHEK1 and CDK2 are not listed in the New Simulation dialog. Checking "Filter

members in sets to drug targets" will select members in EntitySet instances that are targeted by drugs to force showing of potential pathway impact caused by drugs.

2. **Perform simulation with drug:** The configuration for drug in the Drug Selection dialog will be copied into the Boolean Network configuration table displayed in the Results Panel. Click the "Simulate" button to perform simulation. After the simulation is done, Entities in the pathway diagrams are highlighted in different colors based on values in the attractor with detailed temporal values displayed in the table at the bottom Table Panel.

Results Panel

Boolean Network Modelling

Simulate New Delete Compare

Entity	Type	Initial	Modification	Strength
p-5S-BRCA1:...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-MRN [nucle...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-RPA hetero...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S102-WHS...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S1981,Ac-...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S25,S1778...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S317,S345...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S327,T847,...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S406-FAM...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0
p-S456-ABL1...	Respondent	1.0	Inhibition	0.9
p-S990,Ac-K...	Respondent	1.0	None	0.0

Use larger values for stimulation variables

*: Simulation for HDR through Homologous Recombination (HR) or Single Strand Annealing (SSA) (focused on ABL1) (Imatinib Mesylate)

Default Imatinib

Imatinib BN Setup

HDR Through HR or SSA Default Results

To see the drug impact to the activity of an entity displayed in the pathway, choose that entity and check its temporal behavior in both BN:Default and BN:Imatinib tables. For example, below a complex (see above screenshot) related to ABL1 is selected (Up for imatinib applied and down for default without drug):

Imatinib One Variable

Default One Variable

You may also use the "Compare" button to check the detailed difference in the computed attractors from two simulations.

Entity	Imatinib Type	Default Type	Imatinib Initial	Default Initial	Imatinib Modification	Default Modification	Imatinib Strength	Default Strength	Relative Difference
D-Loop p-MRN-p-S1981-Ac-K3016-ATM.K...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	1.2
p-Y104-RAD52 heptamer [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.965456590686562
p-Y104-RAD52 p-RPA-ATR-ATRIP-3' overha...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.9590620648408352
p-S456-ABL1 [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	Inhibition	None	0.9	0.0	0.9000000000000002
D-Loop p-MRN-p-S1981-Ac-K3016-ATM.K...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.8571428571428571
RAD51 p-Y104-RAD52 p-RPA-ATR-ATRIP-3'	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.5454545454545454
dsDNA with inter-SSA deletion [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.5
Flap [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.5
PPI [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.5
SSB-dsDNA with inter-SSA deletion [nucleo...	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.5
RAD51 p-Y104-RAD52 p-RPA-ATR-ATRIP.D...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.461538461538461...
RAD51 [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.461538461538461...
Cleaved D-Loop p-MRN-p-S1981-Ac-K3016...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.4
Extended D-Loop p-MRN-p-S1981-Ac-K30...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.4
p-T309-RAD51 [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.363636363636363...
dsDNA [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.3333333333333333
ss-gap-reannealed DNA [nucleoplasm]	Respondent	Respondent	0.0	0.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.3333333333333333
Cleaved Holliday Junction p-MRN-p-S1981...	Respondent	Respondent	1.0	1.0	None	None	0.0	0.0	0.2857142857142857

p-S456-ABL1 Values

Note: From the above comparison, we can see that application of imatinib will significantly impact the formation of the complex in HDR, an effect of imatinib on DNA repair pathway has been reported by others (e.g. [Imatinib \(STI571\) induces DNA damage in BCR/ABL-expressing leukemic cells but not in normal lymphocytes](#)). You may see a little bit different simulation results because of update in pathway annotations in new versions of ReactomeFIViz.

Perform scRNA-seq Data Analysis and Visualization

ReactomeFIViz implements a suite of features for users to conduct scRNA-seq data analysis and visualization. To do this, we have packaged several popular Python packages developed for scRNA-seq data analysis and visualization together into a Python standalone application. These packages include [scanpy](#) for routine scRNA-seq data analysis and visualization and [scVelo](#) for RNA velocity based data analysis and visualization.

Note: For scRNA-seq data analysis and visualization, you need to have Python 3.7 installed at your computer. If you have not installed Python at your computer, you can do so by downloading an installer from <https://www.python.org/downloads> for your computer. We have tested Python 3.7 only and therefore suggest that you use 3.7 for these features. However, you don't need to install our standalone Python application independently from ReactomeFIViz.

When needed, ReactomeFIViz will automatically download and update the application for you as long as you point to the correct Python application path (i.e. directory and application file).

Standard Analysis via Scanpy

1. **Set up the analysis:** The Python package, [scanpy](#), provides a set of powerful analysis and visualization features for scRNA-seq data. ReactomeFIViz wraps these features for users to take advantage of pathway and network analysis and visualization facilities provided by Cytoscape in general and ReactomeFIViz in particular. To conduct a scRNA-seq analysis using scanpy, choose menu Apps/Reactome FI/Single Cell Analysis/Analyze to get the configuration window as shown below:

ReactomeFIViz

Single Cell Data Analysis

Approach

Choose an approach: Standard analysis via Scanpy
 RNA Velocity Analysis via scVelo

Note: Analysis steps and their parameters will be logged into /Users/wug/CytoscapeConfiguration/ReactomeFIViz/ReactomeFIViz.2020-11-17.log.

Data Information

Choose a folder or file:

Specify a species: human
 mouse

Specify a format: 10x-Genomics-mtx
 h5ad

Preprocess

Choose an imputation method: MAGIC

Choose attributes for regressout: total_counts
 pct_counts_mt

scRNA-seq Analysis Configuration

ReactomeFIViz supports scRNA-seq data generated from mouse and human. You should choose the species for your data and the format. If your data is in the 10x-Genomics-mtx format, you should choose the directory containing the files in that format. You may check an imputation method. Currently, ReactomeFIViz supports the [MAGIC](#) approach only. You may also check `total_counts` and/or `pct_counts_mt` for [regress out](#) to control unwanted variations.

Note: All analysis steps and their parameters are logged into

CytoscapeConfiguration/ReactomeFIViz/ReactomeFIViz.{date}.log in your user folder for your review.

2. **Configure Python for ReactomeFIViz:** If you have not done so, you will be asked to set up Python for ReactomeFIViz using the following configuration dialog when ReactomeFIViz downloads the Reactome Python app for scRNA-seq data analysis and visualization.

Set up Python

Note: Currently only Python 3.7 is supported.

ReactomeFIViz uses the functions provided by scanpy for pre-processing, normalization, UMAP analysis, cell clustering and all other scRNA-seq analysis except imputation, which is handled by [MAGIC](#), if checked. See details in the scanpy document: <https://scanpy.readthedocs.io/en/stable/api/index.html>. For parameters used for these functions, open the ReactomeFIViz.{data}.log file (see above).

3. **Visualize Cell Networks:** Dependent on the sample size and the computing power, it may take several minutes to finish the analysis. After that, two networks, one for cell clusters and another for single cells, are displayed in Cytoscape and listed under "SingleCellClusterNetwork" and "SingleCellNetwork" in the left-side, Network tab, respectively.

ScRNA-seq Cluster Network

ScRNA-seq Cell Network

Note: You may use the built-in Cytoscape Style features and other configuration properties to adjust the rendering of these two networks. See Cytoscape's user manual by clicking menu Help/User Manual. To show or hide edges in the networks, use popup menu Reactome FI/Show Edges (see below for a screenshot). Cluster in the cell cluster network are named based on the rank of cell clusters sorted by cell numbers in the clusters. For example, cluster0 has the largest number of cells.

4. **Analyze scRNA-seq Data:** To explore the loaded scRNA-seq data and perform further analysis, you can use the popup menu provided in the cell cluster or single cell network view as shown below:

ScRNA-seq Standard Analysis Popup Menus

- **Load Gene Expression:** Overlay expression value for a gene onto the network. You may enter the gene name from the input dialog after clicking this menu.
Note: Cell clusters use the median values of cells in the clusters for coloring for gene expression and cell features (below).
- **Load Cell Features:** Overlay cell features by choosing a sub-menu, e.g., `n_genes` (total genes), `n_genes_by_counts` (total genes having counts), `total_counts`, `total_count_mt` (for mitochondrial genes), `pct_counts_mt` (percent of mitochondria genes), and `leiden` (network clustering results based on the [Leiden](#) algorithm).
Note: Both the cell cluster network and the single cell network are colored based on the `leiden` clustering results when they are rendered after the analysis. To get back to the original colors, choose Load Cell Feature/`leiden`.
- **CytoTrace Analysis:** Perform CytoTrace analysis to predict the differential state of cells based on the number of detected expressed genes per cell. ReactomeFIViz provides a Python implementation of CytoTrace based on the original R code published in <https://cytotrace.stanford.edu>. For details about CytoTrace, see the original paper: [Single-cell transcriptional diversity is a hallmark of developmental potential](#). You can find more information in the CytoTrace's web site: <https://cytotrace.stanford.edu>.

Note: The analysis may take several minutes. After the analysis, cells will be colored based on predicted differential state values scaled between 0 and 1: 0 for most differentiated (yellow) and 1 for least differentiated (blue). The analysis results are cached in ReactomeFIViz and listed in a new column called "cytotrace" in the Node Table at the bottom. When you choose this menu again after the analysis, the results will be overlaid without performing another analysis. A new menu item called "cytotrace" will be added to the "Load Cell Features" popup menu too so that you can load these results directly.

Note: You may not see this menu item after the analysis. Try to switch to another network view and then come back to refresh the menu items.

- **Diffusion Pseudotime Analysis (DPT):** Perform cell trajectory inference based on network diffusion. For details about the algorithm, see scanpy.tl.dpt and the original paper: [PAGA: graph abstraction reconciles clustering with trajectory inference through a topology preserving map of single cells](#). To conduct this analysis, the id of a cell that should be regarded as the root of the trajectory is needed. If you have some idea what this cell is, you may enter it directly in the following dialog. If you don't know what it is but have some idea in which cluster or clusters the root may reside, you can enter the cluster(s) in the second text field. ReactomeFIViz will try to infer a possible cell root for you in your specified cluster(s) based on [PageRank](#). For details about the cell root inference algorithm, see [infer cell root](#).

Choose Cell Root

Provide the id of a cell as the root:

Or enter clusters to infer a root:

Note: You may enter more than one cluster by delimiting them with ",". To use all clusters, enter "all". If you enter information for both text boxes, the information in the cell root box will be used.

OK Cancel

Configure Cell Root for DPT

Note: If you don't have any idea what the cell root is, you may try several approaches. If you have conducted a CytoTrace analysis, you may choose the cell having the largest CytoTrace value as the cell root. You may also try the cell having the largest number of detected genes as the root for exploration data

analysis. To choose cell clusters for inferring the cell root, you should choose clusters having the largest CytoTrace values or gene numbers. If you have enter values into both text fields in the above dialog, the value in the first text field will be used as the cell root.

After the DPT analysis, cells will be colored based on DPT values ranged from 0 to 1 with 0 as the earliest cell (yellow) in the trajectory and 1 as the latest (blue). A new column called "dpt_pseudotime" will be added into the Node Table at the bottom and "dpt_pseudotime" will be registered as a new item under "Load Cell Feature" popup menu for loading without repeating the analysis.

Note: You may not see this menu item after the analysis. Try to switch to another network view and then come back to refresh the menu items.

- **Differential Expression Analysis:** Perform differential gene expression analysis between a cell cluster (group) and another cell cluster or all other cell clusters using [t-test_overestim_var](#). To conduct this analysis, you need to choose two groups of cells first: The group of cell for analysis based on clustering results and another group as the reference. You may choose another cell cluster or all other cells as the reference.

Choose Cell Groups for Differentila Expression Analysis

The differential expression analysis result is displayed in the following table. You may choose one or more filteres by clicking the "Add" button to filter genes displayed in the table. To create a FI network for the filtered genes displayed in the table, click the "Build FI Network" button. To conduct a pathway enrichment analysis, you can choose Binomial_test or [GSEA](#). The Binomial_test will use the

filtered, displayed genes in the table while the GSEA analysis will use gene rank by the score, including genes that are not displayed in the table.

Differential Expression Analysis: 0 vs 1

Filter rows by: FDR <= 0.01 Add Filter

Filter rows by: LogFoldChange >= for abs 4 Remove

Filter rows by: Score >= for abs 10 Remove

Gene	Score	LogFoldChange	pValue	FDR
Pnliprp1	-231.506	-9.879	0	0
Cpa2	-224.006	-9.385	0	0
Cips	-191.454	-10.044	0	0
Ctrb1	-184.024	-10.214	0	0
Cpa1	-175.638	-9.842	0	0
Reep5	-159.028	-8.471	0	0
Arhgdig	-139.489	-6.243	0	0
Lgals4	132.19	6.425	0	0
Cps1	119.734	7.621	0	0
Cela1	-119.533	-7.129	0	0
Cel	-116.72	-9.528	0	0
Nupr1	-112.839	-8.578	0	0
Lypd8	108.963	6.679	0	0
Tspan8	108.116	6.723	0	0
Fkbp11	-103.981	-5.234	0	0
Oat	101.233	4.939	0	0
Cela3b	-98.987	-9.56	0	0
Rbpjl	-97.83	-8.428	0	0
Serpini2	-94.747	-9.611	0	0

Total genes displayed: 463

Function analysis: Reactome pathway analysis by GSEA Analyze Build FI Network Close

Differential Expression Analysis Result

Note: Genes in the FI network constructed from the selected genes are colored based on gene scores. For more information on how to use the features for the FI network, see [Gene Set/Mutation Analysis](#). You may open a pathway diagram when a network view is shown. To get back to the previous network view, close all displayed pathway diagrams and then select the network in the Network tab in the left, control panel. Reactome mouse pathways are predicted from human pathways based on the panther orthologous mapping file. For details, see: [Inferred Events in Reactome](#). The mouse human functional interaction network is predicted from the human functional interaction network using the mapping file provided by [MGI](#), downloaded using this link: http://www.informatics.jax.org/downloads/reports/HOM_MouseHumanSequence.rpt. One human gene may be mapped to multiple mouse genes. Therefore, the mouse FI network may show a node that is annotated with multiple mouse genes. For example, see below: The original human KLK3 is mapped to Klk1b9, Klk1b21, and many others, which are all listed in the node table at the bottom and in the network view as the label for that node. Currently links to these nodes in the FI network point to human genes (e.g. GeneCard).

One Human Gene Mapped to Multiple Mouse Genes

- **Build Regulatory Network:** Infer an underlying gene regulatory network between transcriptional factors (TFs) and their targets for one or more cell clusters. This approach is inspired by Qiu et al's [Inferring Causal Gene Regulatory Networks from Coupled Single-Cell Expression Dynamics Using Scribe](#). However, the current implementation provided by ReactomeFIViz uses time-delayed gene co-expression to infer potential causal relationships between TFs and their targets instead of "restricted directed information (RDI)" and limits the causal relationships search between TFs and their targets based on TF/target interactions provided by [dorothea](#). To perform this analysis, set up parameters in the following dialog:

Regulatory Network Configuration

Choose correlation method: Spearman

Select TF/Target interactions with correlations:
 Absolute value \geq 0.05 and p-Value \leq 0.05

Choose cell time type: dpt_pseudotime

Choose time delay: 7

Choose cell groups: all, 0, 1, 2, 3

Selected cell groups: all

OK Cancel

Gene Regulatory Network Inference Setup

Note: You may choose Spearman, Pearson, or Kendal for gene expression correlation calculation. The cell time type is one of latent_time, velocity_pseudotime, cytotime or dpt_pseudotime, which are cell properties calculated during trajectory inference. The first two types are generated during an RNA velocity analysis (See below). If ReactomeFIViz cannot find any of these variables, you will be asked to perform the dpt_pseudotime analysis first. The time delay is used to conduct a delayed gene co-expression calculation. For example, the expression of a TF is [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] and the expression of one of its target is [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. If the time delay = 4, the correlation between [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] and [15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20] is calculated. The time delay in the above dialog is for the maximum time delay. Therefore, if you enter 7 for the time delay, the actual time delay values used for correlation calculation are [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. The correlation is calculated 7 times and the maximum value of those calculated correlation values is used. For the cell groups, you may choose all, one of cell clusters, or multiple cell clusters (hold the command key under Mac or the control key under Windows). It may take several minutes to calculate the correlation for all TF/target

interactions and then build the regulatory network. The following is an example showing how a final gene regulatory network looks like:

Partial Gene Regulatory Network

Note: A style called "Regulatory Network Style" is created for rendering the generated gene regulatory network. With this style, TFs are rendered as diamonds while their targets as circles. The original [dorothea](#) interactions provide annotation: -> for activation and -| for inhibition. Red for positive correlation while blue for negative correlation. The calculated correlation may not match the original annotation in dorothea. For example, in the above figure, the interaction between Insm1, a TF and one of its target, Scg3, is annotated as an inhibition. However, the actual calculated Spearman correlation is positive. The edge width is proportional to the absolute correlation value. You may investigate this style inside Cytoscape for more information.

- **Project New Data:** Project another data set onto the displayed network. This feature uses the [ingest](#) function in scanpy to integrate a new dataset onto the dataset used to generate the network, showing where cells in the new dataset

can be mapped to the displayed network. To perform this analysis, enter the data file in the following dialog:

Project New Data Configuration

Note: You cannot choose the approach in this dialog. It is expected that the same approach should be used to project a new dataset onto the existing network. After projecting, a new popup menu called "Toggle Projected Data" is added under the "Project New Data" menu for toggling the display of the projected cells. The following two figures show the cell network before (left) and after (right) a new dataset is projected. As shown, the majority of cells in the new dataset are projected onto the cell clusters displayed in green, salmon and rosy brown around the middle and top-right regions.

- **Save Analysis Results:** All analysis results may be saved into a local file in the [h5ad](#) format. The saved file can be opened using the main menu, Apps/Reactome FI/Single Cell Analysis/Open.

RNA Velocity Analysis via scVelo

RNA velocity analysis is a powerful approach to quantitatively model dynamic behavior of mRNA transcription of genes based on count ratios between unspliced and spliced forms of mRNAs ([La Manno et al 2018](#)). [scVelo](#) provides an enhanced implementation of the original approach in Python. ReactomeFIViz packages scVelo for you to conduct this analysis in Cytoscape using graphic user interfaces without scripting. For more information about RNA velocity and scVelo, see the original scVelo document: <https://scvelo.readthedocs.io>.

1. **Set up the analysis:** Select "RNA Velocity Analysis via scVelo" for Approach in the following scRNA-seq analysis action dialog and choose one of RNA velocity modes. To see the differences among the three modes listed in dialog, see the original scVelo paper, [Generalizing RNA velocity to transient cell states through dynamical modeling](#). The default is "stochastic". However, if you want to get more dynamic information, choose "dynamical". For what you can do with the dynamical model, see [Dynamical Modeling with scVelo](#). The data file required by this analysis should be pre-processed specifically by using velocityto or loompy/kallisto pipeline and contain two matrices for unspliced and spliced abundances. For more information on how to get started, see this scVelo tutorial: [Getting Started](#).

ReactomeFIViz

Single Cell Data Analysis

Approach

Choose an approach: Standard analysis via Scanpy
 RNA Velocity Analysis via scVelo

Note: Analysis steps and their parameters will be logged into /Users/wug/CytoscapeConfiguration/ReactomeFIViz/ReactomeFIViz.2020-11-25.log.

Velocity Mode

Choose an RNA velocity mode: stochastic
 dynamical
 deterministic

Data Information

Choose a folder or file:

Specify a species: human
 mouse

Preprocess

For the RNA velocity analysis, the input data should contain two matrices for unspliced and spliced abundances, which can be generated using velocityto or loompy/kallisto pipeline. For details, see https://scvelo.readthedocs.io/getting_started.html.

RNA Velocity Analysis Configuration

2. **Visualize the RNA velocity analysis results:** Dependent on the mode you choose, it may take a while to conduct the RNA velocity analysis. The outputs are the same as ones from a standard analysis using scanpy except that the single cell cluster network is displayed as directed, weighted network with directions corresponding to times in the inferred trajectory based on the [PAGA](#) approach and weights for the connectivities between cell clusters. The following figure shows an example of such a weighted, directed cell cluster network.

RNA Velocity Cluster Network

Note: It is expected that you see different results from the RNA velocity analysis than ones from the standard analysis.

3. **Analyze the RNA velocity results:** Most of analysis features for the displayed networks generated from the RNA velocity analysis are the same as ones from the standard analysis via scanpy. However, the RNA velocity analysis provides much more cell features than the standard analysis as shown in the following popup menu:

RNA Velocity Cell Features Popup Menu

Note: To understand the meanings of these RNA velocity specific cell features, please refer to the original scVelo tutorials: [scVelo tutorials](#). In addition to the above RNA velocity specific cell features, a new popup menu group is added for you to conduct some RNA velocity specific data analysis and visualization as shown below:

RNA Velocity Popup Menu

Note: Refer to this scVelo tutorial for Embedding, Embedding Grid, Embedding Stream, and Gene Velocity: [RNA Velocity Basics](#). ReactomeFIViz utilizes scVelo's visualization features to generate image files for these plots and then automatically open them. To keep these files for your record, you may have to save them into your designated files. Otherwise, they will be automatically deleted when you close Cytoscape.

- **Rank Velocity Genes:** Ranks genes in individual cell clusters based on differential expression analysis using scVelo's `rank_velocity_genes` function: [rank_velocity_genes](#). Top 250 genes for individual clusters returned from this analysis are displayed in a table as shown in the following figure. You may conduct pathway enrichment analysis using a binomial test or build a FI network for a selected cell cluster.

Cluster Specific Velocity Genes

Filter rows for gene: contains Filter

Rank	cluster0	cluster1	cluster2	cluster3	cluster4	cluster5	cluster6	cluster7	cluster8	cluster9	cluster10	cluster11	cluster12	cluster13	cluster14	cluster15	cluster16	cluster17	cluster18
0	Slt3	Pcsk5	Kif20b	Tm4s4	Cdk14	Hbegf	Mast2	Slc8a1	Tead2	Abcc8	Stgfnac3	Rfx6	Fcgbp	Cubn	Dmbt1	Phactr1	Pcb4	Prr5l	Sic24a3
1	Nr5a2	Ros1	Top2a	Slt3	Sic38a11	Sic12a2	Rimbp2	Kcnj3	Rbms1	Ap1s2	Dlc1	Kcnj3	Ceacam1	Pcsk5	Smoc2	Mapt	Nrxn1	Nox4	Prkg1
2	Irga6	Cidec	Hbegf	Gnas	Cnksr2	Cps1	Cadps	Gm30524	Zcchc11	Gipr	Pdzrn3	Dnah9	Cdca8	Cps1	Car8	Entpd3	Sez6l	Kih29	Kih29
3	Rbpj	Apob	Edn1	Mts1	Scn3a	Cenpe	Cacna1a	Arhgef38	Pamr1	Baiap3	Cdh11	Pcln	Aurka	Pde3a	Topbp1	Kih32	Wipi1	Aldh18a1	Adam19
4	Dnm1	Dnm1	Topbp1	Nfia	Pde11a	Kif11	Nbea	Stxbp5	Amotl2	Pax6	Col6a3	Pex5l	Cnn2	Edn1	Onecut2	Col6a6	Auts2	Clec2h	Iga9
5	Ero1lb	Creb3l3	Cluh	Xylt1	Rgs7	Smoc2	Sic8a1	Cacna1a	Enah	Dst	Pcdh7	Kih32	Kif20b	Tle4	Kif20b	Api1s2	Myk	Pcy2	Sdk1
6	Eldaradd	Dgat2	Cps1	Foxp2	Mss1	Top2a	Etv1	Kif1a	Igf1r	Ccdc88a	Meis1	Cadps	Cenpe	Prr5l	Tle4	Paps2	Dnah9	Sec16b	Gm26632
7	Prom1	Tle4	Ncaph	Chst15	Dlg2	Edn1	Rgs7	Adgrg4	Adamts1	Pak3	Piezo2	Irs1	Tle4	Adtrp	Hbegf	Sdk2	Pde11a	Eps82	Pcdh7
8	Mcc	Fabp2	Pcsk5	Krt7	Gria3	Noc2l	Pcln	Sgip1	Lamb1	Ncoa7	Gli3	Adam23	Edn1	Dnm1	Kif14	Acvr1c	Slc30a8	Cubn	Chrm2
9	Xylt1	Ephx2	Pde3a	Cpb1	Rasa2	Kif20b	Kif7	Nbea	Notch2	Sobp	Fbn1	Cacna1a	Areg	Acvr1c	Aurka	Slc30a8	Myt1	Pla2g6	Jph2
10	Mgll	Eps82	Areg	Mgll	Syt1	Areg	Arhgef38	Paps2	Nfib	Gnao1	Tenn4	Irga4	Car8	Eps82	Rab3c	Lrp8	Runx1t1	Dnm1	Ryr2
11	Igf1	Adtrp	Tle4	Apoe	Stxbp5l	Ncapp	Onecut3	Pde3a	Climn	Zcchc11	Tshz2	Pax6	Mcoln2	Renbp	Ceacam1	Chic1	Syne1	Snx8	Dgkb
12	Meis1	Pde3a	Kif11	Cclal	Grik4	Cluh	Cacna2d1	Syt7	Adgrg6	Syt7	Zeb1	Gnao1	Kif11	Hbegf	Pgr	Ero1lb	Nrp2	Igsf9	Nrp2
13	Nphts1	Aldh18a1	Cdca8	Igf1	Ill1r1	Tle4	Gnao1	Onecut3	Fn1	Chc1	Nfia	Prosh2	Clap2l	S100a6	Mast2	Emb	Trpm2	Samd9l	Myocd
14	Hes1	Pcy2	Atad2	Runx1t1	Ablim1	Topbp1	Zeb1	Mast2	Pitpnc1	Syt13	Fbn2	Vwa5b2	Ncaph	Climn	Tm4s4	Sobp	Climn	Acs1l	Samd4
15	Meis2	Sec16b	Kif14	Pcb4	Pex5l	Ncaph	Map2	Scn11a	Pprrs	Ncam1	Unc5c	Mast2	Mki67	Aldh18a1	Cdca8	Ins2	Sgip1	Neat1	Filip1
16	Edem1	Lct	Noc2l	Gse1	Map3k15	Pcsk5	Runx1t1	Rgs7	Igf1bp5	Gria2	Boc	Nbea	Cps1	Adamts15	Isl1	Dnah9	Pcln	Slc17a5	Hdgf3
17	Slc26a9	Mtp	Cenpe	Synpo2	Cacna2d1	Pde3a	Hepacam2	Map2	Prom1	Kcnk3	Gjc1	Rimbp2	Atad2	Myk	Chga	Gipr	Fnbp1	Acs15	Myh11
18	Svil	Adamts15	Ncapp	Tns1	Trpm2	Kif14	Adam23	Sis	Tenn4	Entpd3	Lama4	Slc8a1	Cluh	Cyr61	Cps1	Abcc8	Gnao1	Slc18a1	Pdzrn3
19	Pdia2	S100a6	Smoc2	Cpa2	Ubr4	Aurka	Stxbp5	Nav1	Nr2f2	Tmem185a	Cellf2	Syt13	S100a6	Areg	Rimbp2	Filip1	Rtn1	Rab11fp5	Gli3
20	Chst15	Areg	Nfib	Pitpnc1	Cadps	Nfib	Zbtb10	Ctnnap2	Tns1	Map2	Hdgf3	Mum1l1	Cyr61	Chc1	Rfx6	Slt1	Kit	Rbp2	Mw1
21	Cckar	Aurka	Iga1	Zbtb10	Atad2	Dclk2	Rimbp2	Ctnbp2	Vwa5b2	Slt2	Pdzrn3	Pde3a	Dgat2	Cyr61	Pex5l	Ncam1	Npl	Syne1	Syne1

Total displayed rows: 250

Function analysis: Reactome pathway analysis by Binomial_Test Analyze Build FI Network for cluster 0 Close

RNA Velocity Rank Gene Table

Note: You may filter genes displayed in the table. However, for pathway enrichment analysis or building a FI network, all 250 genes for a selected cell cluster are used.

- o **Rank Dynamic Genes:** If you choose the dynamic mode for your RNA velocity analysis, you can also do "Rank Dynamic Genes". This feature is based on scVelo function, [rank dynamical genes](#). The output and the functions are the same as "Rank Velocity Genes".

Other Features Related to the FI Network

Query FI Source

Select an edge and right click it to get the popup menu for edge. Select a menu called "Reactome FI/Query FI Source". If a FI is extracted from curated pathways or reactions, a dialog for the original data source(s) will be displayed. Double click a row in the displayed table to show a detailed web page for the source of the FI. If the selected FI is a predicted one, the evidence for this FI should be displayed.

Query FI Source

Interaction: EGFR - TP53

Reactome Sources

Reactome ID	Type	Data Source
817621	TARGETED_INTERACTION	TREP

Open Reactome Source

ReactomeFIViz app Menu

Fetch FIs for Node

All FIs for a node can be queried. Select a node in the network panel, and right click it to get the popup menu for node. Select a menu called "Reactome FI/ Fetch FIs". FI partners for the selected node will be displayed in two sections: partners have been displayed in the network and partners not displayed in the network. You can select partners from the second sections to expand the displayed network.

Query Node FIs

Total FI partners for "GAB2": 98

Partners in network: 1

EGFR

Partners not in network: 97

AKT1	AKT2	AKT3
BCL10	BCR	CARD11
CD28	CD80	CD86
CRK	CRKL	DKFZB434N031

Add selected partner(s) to network

Close

Show Node FIs

Show Pathway Diagram

Pathway diagrams can be shown for pathway hits. Select a pathway in the "Pathways in Network" or "Pathways in Modules" tab, and right click to get the popup menu for pathway. Select "Show Pathway Diagram" from the popup menu

ECM-receptor interaction(K)	0.0112
Focal adhesion(K)	0.0266
Wnt signaling pathway(K)	0.0277
Integrin signalling pathway(K)	0.0277
Dilated cardiomyopathy(K)	0.0277
Calcium signaling pathway(K)	0.0277

Export Annotations

Show Pathway Detail

Show Pathway Diagram

Show Pathway Diagram

. If pathways are imported from KEGG, KEGG pathway diagram pages will be shown in a browser with node genes listed in the "Nodes" column highlighted in red (for text and borders in pathway diagrams). If pathways are from Reactome or other non-KEGG databases, pathway diagrams should be shown in a separated window. If pathways are curated by the Reactome project, human laid-out diagrams should be displayed if any. Otherwise, auto-laid-out diagrams should be displayed. Genes or proteins from the displayed network should be highlighted in blue. Detailed annotations for nodes and reactions displayed in the diagram window can be viewed by using a popup menu called "View Instance". Diagrams displayed can be zoomed in/out using the zoom slider at the bottom of the window. The diagram can be panned by the overview window at the top-right corner.

Select Nodes

Fetch FI Annotations

Analyze Network Functions ▶

Cluster FI Network

Analyze Module Functions ▶

Load Cancer Gene Index

By using the first method, the user can load the tree of NCI disease terms and display the tree in the left panel. The user can select disease term in the tree, all genes or proteins have been annotated for the selected disease and its sub-terms will be selected.

Cancer Gene Index Overlay

By using the second method, the user can view detailed annotations for the selected gene or protein. The user can sort these annotations based on PubMedID, Cancer type, and annotation status, and also filter annotations based on several criteria.

Cancer Gene Index Annotations for Node

Survival Analysis

Survival analysis is based on a server-side R script to do either coxph or Kaplan-Meier survival analysis. To do survival analysis, a tab-delimited text file containing at least three columns should be provided. The names of three columns should be: Samples, OSDURATION, and OSEVENT. For example, see this survival information file downloaded from [van de Vijver et al in 2002: *Nejm Clin Simple.txt*](#), which has been simplified for our analysis purpose. To do survival analysis, use the popup menu "Analyze Module Functions/Survival Analysis..." (see below)

Survival Analysis Menu

In the survival analysis dialog (below), double click the text field to select a file containing survival information for samples used to build the displayed FI sub-network (Note: you cannot do survival analysis if you use a gene set file only to construct the displayed FI subnetwork). You can choose either coxph or Kaplan-Meier model to do survival analysis. If you choose the Kaplan-Meier model, you have to select a module for analysis. In the Kaplan-Meier analysis, all samples will be divided into two groups: samples having no mutated genes in the selected module (group 1) and samples having mutated genes in module (group 2). It is recommended to run the coxph module first without selecting any module in order to see which module is most significantly related to survival times. After that, you can focus on some specific modules for survival analysis.

Survival Analysis Dialog

The results from survival analysis will be displayed in the right Results Panel with a tab labeled "Survival Analysis" (below left). You can do multiple survival analyses. All results returned from the server-side R script will be displayed in this panel with labels based on your parameter selections in the survival analysis dialog. The last result will be selected as default. At most three sections are displayed in the result panel for each analysis: Output, Error, and Plot. If no warning or error returned from an analysis, the error section may not be shown. Rows for modules having p-values less than 0.05 from coxph (all modules) analysis are displayed in blue with text underlined. You can click these modules to do a quick single-module based survival analysis without going through the above steps. Single module-based Kaplan-Meier analysis will show a plot file. You can click the file to view the actual plot (below right). You may need to save the plot file for your future use.

Survival Analysis

Analysis: Coxph (all modules)

----Output----

Note: Click underlined modules in blue for single module-based analysis. You may not see any underlined module if all p-values > 0.05.

Module	Coefficient	P-value
<u>0</u>	<u>-0.6142421</u>	<u>0.0015</u>
<u>1</u>	<u>1.308675</u>	<u>2.7e-10</u>
<u>2</u>	<u>0.4908374</u>	<u>0.015</u>
3	0.3854999	0.071
4	0.1916897	0.38
<u>5</u>	<u>1.015691</u>	<u>4.4e-07</u>
6	-0.06630745	0.71
7	-0.01376751	0.94
8	0.4978022	0.053
<u>9</u>	<u>0.948809</u>	<u>3.8e-06</u>
<u>10</u>	<u>0.6773846</u>	<u>0.024</u>
11	0.09736692	0.61
<u>12</u>	<u>-0.6155788</u>	<u>0.00033</u>
13	-0.2256969	0.36
14	-0.3347327	0.06
15	0.4208109	0.1
16	-0.01732149	0.92
17	0.1678460	0.36
18	0.2896866	0.1
19	0.1894892	0.4
20	-0.2718141	0.41
21	-0.05986156	0.73
22	0.2390645	0.22
<u>23</u>	<u>0.7035622</u>	<u>0.0024</u>
24	0.1875984	0.55
25	-0.262039	0.24
<u>26</u>	<u>1.253171</u>	<u>2e-05</u>
27	0.09362757	0.52
28	-0.1431601	0.47
29	0.1243625	0.62
30	-0.1239745	0.55
31	-0.2194841	0.19
32	0.2943090	0.19
33	0.07583841	0.69

Analysis: Kaplan-Meier (module 1)

----Output----

Call:

survdif(formula = surv.tmp ~ scores)

	N	Observed	Expected	(O-E)^2/E	(O-E)^2/V
scores=1	147	17	44.9	17.3	40.7
scores=2	148	62	34.1	22.8	40.7

Chisq= 40.7 on 1 degrees of freedom, p= 1.81e-10

----Plot (click to open)----

[1303430857717_plot.pdf](#)

Close

